

UWS – University of the West of Scotland

**A study to explore the alignment of
business competencies in Higher Education degrees and
the requirements for employment in
an international arena**

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Summary

The focus of this research project is on the alignment of business competencies in Higher Education degrees and the requirements for employment in an international arena. The context of this study is a Dutch BBA-programme, its curriculum and the 14 competencies that are used by 14 Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands. The aim of this research project is to compare the actual competencies in this curriculum with the desired competencies of business organisations, investigate why any gaps exist and explore how these gaps can be bridged. The main research question is: how should the gap between offered competencies by HEIs and the required competencies when working as a middle manager in the Dutch German business environment be managed?

Analysis of the discourse in the literature shows that the concepts “internationalisation” and “globalisation” are used interchangeably and that there is debate on what competencies are when looking beyond the first “superficial” definition of the concept. It is therefore not surprising that there seems to be no clear definition of “international competencies”. In addition to this, research shows that there are no models available in literature that focus on alignment between what is done within HEIs and what is asked by business organisations. Furthermore, literature research also indicates that HEIs have problems keeping up with the changes in business environments.

The outcome of this research with six HEI specialists representing 14 Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands shows that there is no common way of dealing with internationalisation. It is difficult to develop measures and therefore common standards without a definition of internationalisation. The HEI specialists in this research had different views regarding which competencies are internationally important, from which two perspectives emerged: the “competency-based approach” and the “context-based approach”. Moreover, HEIs consider their student to be their major stakeholder, thus overshadowing business organisations as major stakeholders.

The survey response of 392 Dutch business organisations indicates that the contact frequency between HEIs and business organisations is low and that there is room for improvement regarding the quality of the contacts. The conclusion can be drawn that other aspects of the curriculum, besides knowledge and skills, have to be developed within HEIs. According to business organisations HEIs have to recognise business organisations as major stakeholders. Without this step, it cannot be expected that any alignment activity will be successful.

This thesis concludes that alignment between HEI provision and business organisation needs is impeded by a lack of agreement at the basic level, including definitions of competency and internationalisation and recognition of relevant stakeholders. The researcher recommends these areas as a first priority for HEIs and business organisations. Then, in order to build on this foundation, an Alignment Model is proposed to manage the gaps in alignment between HEIs and business organisations in relation to business competencies in an international environment.

Table of Content

Summary	i
Table of Content	iii
List of tables	v
List of figures	vi
List of abbreviations	viii
List of appendices	ix
Acknowledgements	x
Declaration of originality	xii
1.0 Introduction	1
1.1 Context and scope of the research	1
1.1.1 Context	1
1.1.2 Globalisation or internationalisation	3
1.1.3 Competence or competency	5
1.1.4 Research scope.....	9
1.2 Research goal and research questions	11
1.3 Guide for the reader	12
2.0 Literature analysis and theoretical framework	14
2.1 Introduction	14
2.2 Higher education in the Netherlands	14
2.2.1 The Netherlands in Europe	14
2.2.2 The higher education system in the Netherlands	18
2.2.3 Research bachelor.....	20
2.2.4 Professional bachelor	21
2.2.5 Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA)	22
2.2.6 The curriculum	24
2.2.7 The BBA-curriculum.....	26
2.2.8 Dutch qualification frameworks and quality management.....	32
2.3 Middle management	35
2.4 Competencies	38
2.4.1 Introduction	38
2.4.2 Classification of competencies.....	38
2.4.3 Categorisation of competencies	46
2.4.4 Competencies within HEIs	47
2.4.5 Competencies in an international working environment	52
2.4.6 Key developments: from the European Union to the Netherlands	55
2.4.7 Alignment between higher education and organisations	60
2.4.8 Identification of gaps	72
2.5 Conclusions literature analysis	76
2.6 Theoretical framework and input for research design	79
3.0 Research methodology	82
3.1 Research structure and research philosophy	82
3.2 Research methodology literature	85
3.3 Research methodology HEIs	90
3.3.1 Research aim.....	90
3.3.2 Research approach interviews HEI specialists.....	90

3.3.3 Data analysis interviews HEI specialists	99
3.4 Research methodology business organisations.....	100
3.4.1 Research aim.....	100
3.4.2 Research approach survey business organisations	101
3.4.3 Data analysis survey business organisations	109
3.5 Ethics	110
3.5.1 Ethics interviews HEIs	110
3.5.2 Ethics survey business organisations	111
3.6 Data security	111
4.0 Competencies in Higher Education Institutes	113
4.1 Introduction	113
4.2 Presentation of research results and analysis	113
4.2.1 Research execution versus planning	113
4.2.2 Research results of HEI interviews	115
4.3 Conclusions research competencies in HEIs.....	127
4.4 Input for survey competencies Dutch organisations.....	129
5.0 Competencies in Dutch organisations	130
5.1 Introduction	130
5.2 Presentation of research results and analysis	130
5.2.1 Research execution versus planning	130
5.2.2 Research response.....	132
5.2.3 Coding research data.....	134
5.2.4 Research results and data analysis survey	136
5.2.5 Alignment from a quality perspective	171
5.3 Conclusions survey organisations	174
6.0 Discussion	176
6.1 Introduction	176
6.2 What competencies are considered internationally important looking at the BBA programme offered by HEIs in the Netherlands?.....	176
6.3 What are the required competencies for middle managers working in the German-Dutch business environment?.....	179
6.4 What are the similarities and discrepancies between the BBA competencies offered in the Netherlands and the required competencies for middle managers working in the German-Dutch business environment?	182
6.4.1 Gap analysis results.....	182
6.4.2 Literature and HEI perspective on competencies	182
6.4.3 HEI perspective and competencies in BBA - HEI perspective and perspective organisations	185
6.4.4 Competencies in BBA and perspective of organisations	185
6.5 The Alignment model	187
7.0 Conclusion	192
7.1 Contribution to knowledge	192
7.2 Implications for HEIs	194
7.3 Implications for business organisations	196
7.4 Limitations and opportunities for further research.....	197
7.5 Reflection	197
References	201
Appendices	215

List of tables

<i>Table 2.1: Trends, translated from curriculum description BBA, depicted by researcher (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014)</i>	29
<i>Table 2.2: Task competencies BBA, depicted by researcher (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014)</i>	31
<i>Table 2.3: Generic competencies BBA, depicted by researcher (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014)</i>	31
<i>Table 2.4: Iceberg level description and related questions, depicted by researcher (NHS London Leadership Academy 2017)</i>	44
<i>Table 2.5: 21st century Skills, depicted by researcher (SLO/ Kennisnet 2016)</i>	58
<i>Table 3.1: Research approach “middle management”, depicted by researcher.</i>	88
<i>Table 3.2: Research approach "competency, competencies", depicted by researcher.</i>	89
<i>Table 3.3: Comparison of total number of students in the Netherlands with all students of 14 HEIs, depicted by researcher.</i>	97
<i>Table 3.4: Sample size survey organisations, depicted by researcher.</i>	104
<i>Table 4.1: Coverage of consulted Universities of Applied Sciences, depicted by researcher.</i>	113
<i>Table 4.2: Codes HEI-interviews and frequencies, depicted by researcher.</i>	115
<i>Table 5.1: Comparison of national data employees per organisation versus survey data, depicted by researcher.</i>	137
<i>Table 5.2: Response sector comparison, depicted by researcher.</i>	138
<i>Table 5.3: Numbered 14 competencies, depicted by researcher.</i>	155

List of figures

Figure 1.1: Research scope, depicted by researcher.	1
Figure 2.1: The Iceberg model of competencies, depicted by researcher, adapted from NHS London Leadership Academy (NHS London Leadership Academy 2017).....	43
Figure 2.2: Productivity, depicted by researcher, adapted from Competence at work - Spencer & Spencer (Spencer 1993, p. 293)	50
Figure 2.3: SERVQUAL - Gaps model of service quality, depicted by researcher, adapted from Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Berry (1985)	72
Figure 3.1: Research process steps, depicted by researcher.	82
Figure 3.2: Gap analysis overview, depicted by researcher.	83
Figure 4.1: Competency-based approach, depicted by researcher.	125
Figure 4.2: Context-based approach, depicted by researcher.	125
Figure 5.1: Univariate analysis of the organisation sizes of the participants, depicted by researcher (n=392).	137
Figure 5.2: Univariate analysis of the response per sector (n=392)	138
Figure 5.3: Univariate analysis of the response per role in organisation, depicted by researcher (n=392)	139
Figure 5.4: Univariate analysis of doing business with Germany, depicted by researcher (n=392) ...	140
Figure 5.5: Bi-variate analysis number of employees versus doing business in Germany, depicted by researcher (n=392)	141
Figure 5.6: Uni-variate analysis contacts with HEI, depicted by researcher (n=392)	142
Figure 5.7: Uni-variate analysis contact regarding participation in advisory boards, depicted by researcher (n=392)	143
Figure 5.8: Uni-variate analysis contact regarding apprentices, depicted by researcher (n=392).....	143
Figure 5.9: Uni-variate analysis contact regarding guest lectures, depicted by researcher (n=392) ..	144
Figure 5.10: Uni-variate analysis contact in a teaching role, depicted by researcher (n=392)	144
Figure 5.11: Uni-variate analysis contact regarding graduates, depicted by researcher (n=392)	145
Figure 5.12: Uni-variate analysis other forms of contact, depicted by researcher (n=392)	145
Figure 5.13: Uni-variate analysis employees with a BBA-degree, depicted by researcher (n=392)...	147
Figure 5.14: Uni-variate analysis HEI-awareness, depicted by researcher (n=392).....	148
Figure 5.15: Uni-variate analysis “not good or bad” answers, depicted by researcher (n=76).	149
Figure 5.16: Bi-variate analysis HEI-awareness versus age of respondents, depicted by researcher (n=392)	151
Figure 5.17: Bi-variate analysis HEI-awareness versus role of respondents, depicted by researcher (n=392)	152
Figure 5.18: Mean per competency regarding importance, depicted by researcher (n=392)	153
Figure 5.19: Mean per competency regarding satisfaction, depicted by researcher (n=392)	154
Figure 5.20: Bi-variate analysis importance and satisfaction of 14 competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392).	156

<i>Figure 5.21: Bi-variate analysis importance and satisfaction of 14 competencies in scatter diagram, depicted by researcher (n=392).</i>	156
<i>Figure 5.22: Bi-variate analysis of importance and satisfaction of 14 competencies zooming in on scatter diagram, depicted by researcher (n=392).</i>	157
<i>Figure 5.23: Bi-variate analysis satisfaction levels of 14 competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392).</i>	158
<i>Figure 5.24: Bi-variate analysis importance levels of 14 competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392).</i>	159
<i>Figure 5.25: Uni-variate analysis missing knowledge, skills or behavioural aspects, depicted by researcher (n=124).</i>	160
<i>Figure 5.26: Uni-variate analysis missing knowledge, skills or behavioural aspects, depicted by researcher (n=124).</i>	161
<i>Figure 5.27: Uni-variate analysis preference for knowledge or skills, depicted by researcher (n=392)</i>	164
<i>Figure 5.28: The SERVQUAL Gap analysis, depicted by researcher (n=206)</i>	172
<i>Figure 6.1: Gap analysis overview, depicted by researcher.</i>	182
<i>Figure 6.2: Alignment model, depicted by researcher and modified from Spencer & Spencer (Spencer 1993).</i>	188
<i>Figure 10.1: Bi-variate analysis frequency of contact versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)</i>	247
<i>Figure 10.2: Bi-variate analysis size of organisation versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)</i>	247
<i>Figure 10.3: Doing business with Germany versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)</i>	248
<i>Figure 10.4: Employees with a BBA degree versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)</i>	248
<i>Figure 10.5: Gender versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)</i>	249

List of abbreviations

B2B	Business to Business
BaMa	Bachelor Master
BA	Business Administration
BBA	Bachelor of Business Administration
Bsc	Bachelor of Science
CEO	Chief Executive Officer
CFO	Chief Financial Officer
CIO	Chief Information Officer
COO	Chief Operating Officer
e.g.	exempli gratia (Latin for “for example”)
ECTS	European Credit and Transfer System
EHEA	European Higher Education Area
et al.	et alii/et aliae/ et alia (Latin for “and others”)
etc.	et cetera (Latin for “and so on”)
EQF	European Qualification Framework
EU	European Union
FTE	Full-time equivalent
HBO	Dutch: “Hoger Beroepsonderwijs”; Higher Education
HE	Higher Education
HEI	Higher Education Institute
HRM	Human Resources Management
i.e.	id est (Latin for “that is”)
IBL	International Business and Languages
IBMS	International Business and Management Studies
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
k	kilo = thousand
LLB	Bachelor of Laws
MBA	Master of Business Administration
Msc	Master of Sciences
n.d.	no date
n.n.	no name
NLQF	Netherlands Qualification Framework
No.	Number
p.	page
pp.	pages
UCS	University Credit Units
UK	United Kingdom
vs.	versus

List of appendices

- Appendix 1 Ethics approval (English)
- Appendix 2 Invitation mail HEI interviews (Dutch)
- Appendix 3 Participant Information form HEI interviews (English)
- Appendix 4 Participation Consent Form HEI-Interviews (English))
- Appendix 5 Questionnaire semi structured interviews HEIs (Dutch and English)
- Appendix 6 Example interview frequency analysis "culture" (Dutch)
- Appendix 7 Questionnaire Dutch business organisations (Dutch and English)
- Appendix 8 Example of survey analysis, question 12 that deals with the motivation of the given answers regarding the awareness of HEIs (Dutch and English)
- Appendix 9 Cronbach's Alpha and Pearson Correlation analysis (English)
- Appendix 10 Graphs and tables field survey organisations (English)

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April 2020,
Jan-Kees van Dijk.

Declaration of originality

This is to certify that I am responsible for the work submitted in this thesis, that the original work is my own except as specified in acknowledgements, and that neither the thesis nor the original work contained therein was submitted to this or any other institution for a degree.

Signed:

Breda, the Netherlands.

Date: April 2020.

1.0 Introduction

1.1 Context and scope of the research

1.1.1 Context

This study aims to explore the alignment of business competencies in Higher Education (HE) degrees and the requirements for employment in an international arena. In this study, the researcher puts the focus on fit, the extent to which the competencies facilitated in HE curricula and the competencies regarded as important by employers, align. Figure 1.1. visualises the scope of this study.

Figure 1.1: Research scope, depicted by researcher.

Both key stakeholders, HEIs and business organisations, bear responsibilities regarding the (continuous) improvement of alignment. The focus of this research is on business environment and on higher education and will highlight differences as well as similarities. The researcher expects that there will not always be a common kind of language and that models used in this thesis will be a mix of both worlds. To understand the setting of this research, a description of the context is required and given in this first section. Sections 1.1.2 and 1.1.3 will provide an explanation on how the most important concepts in this research (globalisation, internationalisation, competences and competencies) are understood in the literature. These definitions are followed by the research scope in Section 1.1.4.

Doing business in an international environment is growing, which has implications for the employees of the involved organisations. The “Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek” (Statistics Netherlands; CBS) recognises this trend in the Netherlands. CBS is the Dutch authority that is responsible for the collection, processing and publication of statistics for government, science and business (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek 2018a). Every quarter, CBS

publicises the “Internationaliserings-monitor” which describes trends regarding internationalisation that are relevant for the Dutch economy. Another document that was made public in 2018 focuses on the relationship between employment and internationalisation and states that 10% of the jobs in foreign-controlled organisations and organisations not dealing with international trade are occupied by employees that are not from the Netherlands. Furthermore, 30% of the Dutch employment in 2016 was generated by indirect and direct exports, representing 2.1 million full time employees. Organisations that have trade as their main business are known to have a higher growth rate regarding jobs compared to all other organisations. According to the CBS, research shows that changes in technology and legislation not only create but also destroy jobs, which means that it is difficult to predict what the exact effect of globalisation will be in the Dutch employment market (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek 2018b). The conclusion can nevertheless be drawn that the number of employees that work in an international environment is significant and growing. The Economist Intelligence Unit (2012, p. 4) commissioned KMPG International to conduct a study of 418 executives worldwide. The executives indicated how their workforce had evolved geographically during a period of 3 years. According to the survey, 71% of the participants indicated that working across borders (e.g. collaboration among teams in different geographies) has increased. International reporting lines and talent flows are two other developments that have become more common. The study concludes that new Human Resources (HR) policies are needed to address the increased global nature of workforce. The Boston Consulting Group (2012) concluded in that same year that many HR professionals not only miss a global mind-set, but also international education, international work experience, and knowledge regarding international (labour) laws. Two years later another report shows progress in this area (Boston Consulting Group 2014), and advises HR specialists to initiate partnerships with internal and external stakeholders. One of the external stakeholders are HEIs.

Similar trends can be seen in Higher Education (HE), as seen in reports from the International Association of Universities (IAU) (2006) and the European University Association (EUA). The EUA published the document: “Trends 2010: a decade of change in European Higher Education” (European University Association 2010, p. 8). As part of this study, institutions were asked to identify the most important developments that shaped their strategy. Of the three receiving the highest value, the Bologna Process (Conference of European Ministers Responsible for Higher Education 2005; Curaj 2012), which entails meetings of European Ministers during which agreements are made in the European Higher Education Area (EHEA), comes first (78%), quality assurance reforms second (63%) and internationalisation third (61%) (Smidt 2010). Internationalisation is a trend that has been

growing in importance for years (Jones 2016; Knight 2008; OECD 2012), and will probably continue to grow in the coming years. HEIs might therefore be attracted to this development. The growth in domestic HE capacity in some countries (e.g. China) compensates the growth in HE demand worldwide, which is probably one of the reasons why international student mobility shows a lower growth rate compared to the fast growing worldwide demand in Higher Education (UK HE International Unit 2013).

This trend in business and in HE can also be found in literature, as seen in the following research results that focus on investigating the status and activities of Higher Education Institutes (HEIs) regarding internationalisation and globalisation. Abraham and Karns (2009) state that business schools should do more to align their curricula with the desires of businesses. According to them, there is a gap between the needs in business and what is taught in HEIs. Aggarwal (2011, pp. 51-69) indicates that most business schools have a low level of globalisation. The alignment of the skills of business school students with the broader goals of international business education is thus likely to be very challenging. One of the reasons for this low level is culture, according to research of Aggarwal and Goodell (2014). Some stakeholders may not willingly replace existing material with more global content. Therefore, globalisation will often only be part of the regular updating process of the curricula. Other internal and external obstacles are limited financial resources, the level of experience and expertise of HEI-staff, the absence of public funding and language (International Association of Universities 2014). Aggarwal and Goodell (2014) describe another challenge regarding business schools and globalisation: the demands of globalisation and national accreditation requirements are sometimes conflicting.

Clear definitions of “internationalisation” and “competencies” are needed to avoid misunderstanding, since “internationalisation” and “globalisation” are both used in international business and in higher education. Furthermore, the English language includes both “competence” and “competency”. This is different in the Dutch language where only “competentie” is used. The researcher will therefore explore how these terms are defined and used in the literature, and clarify how they will be used throughout this thesis.

1.1.2 Globalisation or internationalisation

To obtain recent sources, the time frame for the search for definitions for and the differences between globalisation and internationalisation is limited to the period 2005 until 2018. The search was executed online and offline, using Beluga and Google Scholar as search engines and the UWS library in Paisley, the Helmut Schmidt University library in Hamburg and the library of the Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften Hamburg as physical sources of

the academic and grey literature. Grey literature is produced by non-traditional organisations regarding academic research such as non-governmental organisations (NGO's), government departments and agencies, private companies and consultants (Lawrence 2014). Older sources were added when there was an added value according to the researcher. The keywords "globalisation", "internationalisation", "difference" and "definition" are used as single words or combined with other relevant topics.

The execution of this approach made clear that although there are similarities between globalisation and internationalisation, they are ultimately not the same. Teichler states that internationalisation deals with the interaction between nations or countries, and leaves the borders of the country intact. This is different from globalisation, which in fact leads to the erasure of borders between countries. Globalisation can also be described as global integration (Teichler 2009). Globalisation affects Higher Education and has taken different forms, such as: borderless education, education across borders, global education, offshore education and international trade in educational services (de Wit 2011a). Knight defines globalisation as a neutral concept which leads to a more interconnected and interdependent world. According to Knight (1997, 2004), internationalisation changes higher education, and globalisation changes internationalisation. Altbach (2009) states that internationalisation in HE can be described as a variety of activities, organised as a response to globalisation. This is a rather generic definition of the concept. Yemini (2015) adds a global perspective to the definition; her definition of internationalisation is:

The process of encouraging the integration of multicultural, multilingual, and global dimensions within the education system, with the aim of instilling in learners a sense of global citizenship.

This definition combines globalisation with internationalisation. Knight developed a definition in 2003 which is still in use with the International Association of Universities (IAU), the definition (International Association of Universities 2003, p. 7):

Internationalization at the national, sector, and institutional levels is defined as the process of integrating an international, intercultural, or global dimension into the purpose, functions or delivery of (postsecondary) education.

This definition addresses the "delivery of education", but says nothing about the quality of this delivery or who the customer is or should be. The definition does not address quality in the eyes of the customer. Quality is defined by customer satisfaction as will be explained in more detail in section 2.2.8; the level of the satisfaction of the customer depends on the quality of the delivered services. This topic is not covered in this definition. De Wit addresses customers and a contribution to society in his definition of internationalisation (de Wit 2015):

The intentional process of integrating an international, intercultural or global dimension into the purpose, functions and delivery of post-secondary education, in

order to enhance the quality of education and research for all students and staff, and to make a meaningful contribution to society.

De Wit talks about quality and the necessity of a meaningful contribution to society. This puts the emphasis on customers. Who the customers are or should be in this definition is not clear, which is of interest as it defines requirements regarding competencies.

It can be said that internationalisation and globalisation are related, but that they are not the same (Altbach, PG, and Knight, J. 2007). Research regarding internationalisation in Higher Education has increased during the last 10 to 30 years (Brandenburg 2015; Yemini, M, and Sagie, N., 2016). Despite this increase, there is still not enough data to execute good analysis for decision-making (European Parliament 2015). The concept internationalisation seems to have a complex and interdependent character (Wihlborg 2018) and can be divided in two options regarding delivery: 1) abroad/ cross-border or 2) at home (Knight 2012). This research aims to explore internationalisation as a concept, which is why the researcher has to decide which concept will be used. The focal point of this research study is “internationalisation” and not on “globalisation”, as the scope of this research deals with the trade between two countries: the Netherlands and Germany. This will be explained later in more detail. However, as both concepts are used interchangeably in literature, the researcher will include “globalisation” in the research when it contributes to the research aim. Internationalisation is an important trend within HEIs and will be explored in this thesis alongside with research on competences or competencies that measure the learning progress of students.

The concepts “competence” and “competency” are both used in English literature. The concepts are explored by executing literature research in the next section and a choice will be made on how they will be used in this research project.

1.1.3 Competence or competency

The first question is which description should be used: “competence” or “competency”? To make this decision the researcher obtained sources in the time frame 2005 until 2018. The search was executed online and offline, using Beluga and Google Scholar as search engines and the UWS library in Paisley, the Helmut Schmidt University library in Hamburg and the library of the Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften (HAW) as physical sources of the academic and grey literature as defined earlier in this section. Older sources were added when there was an added value according to the researcher. The used keywords are “competence”, “competency”, “difference” and “definition”; they were used as single words or combined with other relevant topics.

The results show that “competency” and “competence” are comparable but not always the same. According to the Merriam-Webster dictionary, the meanings of the two words are comparable.

Competence: the ability to do something well: the quality or state of being competent (Merriam-Webster n.d.-a).

Competency: an ability or skill (Merriam-Webster n.d.-b)

Dictionary.com even refers the definition of “competency” back to the word “competence”.

Competence: the quality of being competent; adequacy; possession of required skill, knowledge, qualification, or capacity (Dictionary.com n.d.-a). Competence does not have a plural form.

Competency: competence (Dictionary.com n.d.-b).

The word “competency” originally comes from the Latin word “competentia” (etymonline.com 2016), and means “authorised to judge” and “the right to speak”.

One of the first to discuss competency in the seventies was McClelland. Regarded as individual characteristics, he defined them as predictors of employee performance and success (Mc. Clelland 1973). Another definition is provided by Richard Boyatzis (1982, p. 21). He executed a study of 2000 managers with 41 different jobs and 12 organisations which led to the following definition of “competency”:

An underlying characteristic of a person, which results in effective and/ or superior performance in a job.

Similar to that of McClelland, his definition also focuses on performance.

Dessler (2004) adds new aspects to these definitions; he defines competencies as demonstrable characteristics of the person that enable performance. Job competencies are always observable and measurable. He also states that there is confusion on what competencies are when looking beyond the first “simple” description of the concept. Sometimes competencies are the set of knowledge, or skills or abilities that a person needs in order to be able to do a certain job. The other definition according to Dessler is that competencies are measurable behaviours, a set of required aspects to perform well in a job, to be competent. Instead of focusing on what should be accomplished, competencies focus

more on “how” the job objectives should be reached. Therefore, the competence approach focuses more on the employee.

The approach used by Theodorescu (2006) is that “competence” should be seen as the desired end state for individual performance. Organisations only want behaviour and actions that provide added value. To check this value, it is important to look at the output of these actions. The bottom line, according to Theodorescu, is that organisations reward their employees for results, not for their behaviour. This fits with the view of Torrington, Taylor and Hall (2014). They define “competence” as the ability to carry out specific tasks, often related to job standards. This concept is output-oriented and performance-based, whereas “competency” refers to behaviour, instead of being able to achieve a certain task. Torrington, Taylor and Hall (2014) state that behavioural competencies are often seen as a way to describe the aspects that the organisations find important, and as characteristics that lead to superior performances as well as to provide a tool that supports the execution of strategic Human Resources Management (HRM). According to them, a competency framework is often used for recruitment, selection, training, performance management and reward. These frameworks provide a consistent way of communication with employees on what behaviour is valued within the organisation and what is expected from every employee. Another advantage according to Torrington, Taylor and Hall is the fact that these competencies can be measured and therefore can be used by (external) assessors for assessment and training. The measurement method of competence is more backward looking than future-oriented. Employees are mostly evaluated upon their last year’s behaviour and performance; the results are defined as the results of personal behaviour.

This definition is supported by Boyatzis, who defined competency in 2007 as a capability or ability (Boyatzis 2007, p. 6). He refers to competency as a behaviour that is organised around a construct. This is what he calls the “intent”. Different manifestations are related to different situations. Behaviour, therefore, depends on the intent and on the context. A few years later (2011, p. 91), Boyatzis defined “competence” as the ability to carry out specific tasks, often related to job standards. In contrast to “competency”, this definition is output-oriented and based upon performance. These differences are supported by Sanghi (2016), who states that competences refer to a skill or a certain level reached, while competencies refer to the behaviour by which it is achieved. He indicates that the main difference is that “competence” is related to being competent and that “competency” is related to behaviour. The first describes what people can do and the other describes how they do it. Therefore, competencies must be shown, and can be observed. By demonstrating certain behaviour, a person differentiates from others by doing, executing. Sanghi also states that there is no

need to differentiate between generic and functional competencies as they cannot be restricted to a single job.

The conclusion can be made that “competency” should be preferred when looking at alignment with business needs. It is important to be able to show certain behaviour regarding a specific construct that leads to results. As the concept “competence” focuses more on whether or not you can do it, the “competency” definition relates to results of behaviour, which is considered to be a crucial aspect according to sources in literature. Therefore, the researcher will from now on use the concept “competency” in this research project.

Not all sorts of competencies are in scope of this study. When looking at competencies, different groups can be identified. Prahalad and Hamel (1990, p. 79) have classified competencies into three kinds:

1. Organisational competencies: these contain unique factors that distinguish one organisation from another and make the organisation competitive.
2. Job and role competencies: the demonstration of these competencies results in effective jobs, roles, functions or tasks. Here the input is defined for the job or role.
3. Personal competencies: these competencies contain the ability to perform the actions necessary within the job or role. Here the achievements or output are defined.

This study aims to focus on personal competencies needed in an international business environment. Therefore, organisational competencies are out of scope. Job and role competencies are in scope; they are important as they comprise the requirements defined by organisations. Personal competencies are also relevant as they are used in HEIs and their curricula.

In summary, it can be said that there is no consensus in literature regarding the definitions of internationalisation versus globalisation and competency versus competence. A short logic explanation reveals that a definition of international competencies does not exist either. Accepting the existence of international competencies would namely also result in the existence of another concept: national competencies. There are national competency standards, but so far no one has developed a definition for national competencies. Competencies are present in both national and international environments. The conclusion could be drawn that “international competencies” do not exist. However, competencies important in an international arena do exist. This statement will be explored further in this research project.

The next step is to define the scope of this research project by briefly reviewing the status of alignment in Higher Education in the Netherlands and defining which curriculum will be the subject of this study and why.

1.1.4 Research scope

The topic of this study deals with the alignment between what higher education institutes teach their students and the requirements in the business arena. Hiring the right people is difficult for any organisation. However, filling a vacancy sometimes seems to be the sole method for measuring the effectiveness of higher education. Filling a vacancy is a quantitative performance indicator but does not say anything about the quality of the hire. A good quality means that the new employee has the required competencies to perform well and is immediately productive. Literature analysis regarding employability skills of HE-graduates by Suleman indicates that there seems to be no agreement on which skills are required in business and that some employers suggest that graduates are not well prepared (Suleman 2016). Research executed by IBM Global Services (2015) indicates that 49% of industry and academic leaders in the USA believe that higher education meets the needs of students in general. Another 41% have indicated that they find that higher education meets industry needs. Finally, 43% of the participants believe that higher education prepares students with the skills needed in their future working environment. The question if these results are good or bad is difficult to answer and requires more research. However, the conclusion can be made that there is room for improvement.

Looking at higher education in the Netherlands, the situation is not much different. A joint initiative of three Dutch professors and their research groups concerning internationalisation of higher education has resulted in a study on how students of six International Business and Management Studies (IBMS) are prepared for an international career (Kosteljik 2015). The IBMS study is part of the Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA) domain in the Netherlands, and has eight professional and eight generic competencies (National Platform IBMS 2011). In this survey, the main criticism of alumni went into the direction of four competencies; they felt there was not a good match between what was learned in higher education and the required professional needs in: 1) leadership 2) international HRM 3) international business and management accounting and financial management 4) international operations management – IT component. None of the four competencies, for which the match between professional needs and education were measured in this study, scored better than 50% regarding satisfaction with the match between what was learned in HE and the required professional needs. The reasons for these seemingly low levels have not been investigated. One might argue that these are low scores and that stakeholders are

likely not happy with these results. These scores also spur the question as to why organisations are not reacting more critically and vigilantly. IBM researchers (King, M, Marshall, A. and Zaharchuk, D. 2015) found out that major stakeholders are optimistic that the alignment will improve soon. They expect that HEIs may show significant improvements in the upcoming years. However, there seem to be no signs that academic leaders prioritise the right actions that are needed to realise these improvements regarding alignment. This research focuses on this alignment and its dynamics in the Netherlands.

To have a clear scope and to be able to execute an in-depth analysis, one curriculum is selected. The focal point regarding Higher Education Institutes is on those in the Netherlands with a strong link to practice and where the students consequently execute practice-oriented research during their studies: Universities of Applied Sciences. From this group, a state recognised and accredited bachelor programme was chosen, as only these are formally described in the Bologna process (European Union 1999) and are used across borders in Europe. To increase the value of the study, the choice was made to choose a curriculum that is used by multiple HEIs and has therefore an above average number of students. The national education profile “Opleidingsprofiel Bacheloropleiding Bedrijfskunde Management Economie en Recht (MER)” was developed by 14 Universities of Applied Sciences. This curriculum is used for a Dutch BBA programme (MER 2014) and describes three roles for future graduates; an advice role, a managerial role and a research role. In the managerial role, the BBA graduate will be responsible for a certain defined business field and for results in this area and will therefore manage employees and business processes. The aim of the curriculum is to develop students for middle management positions, which is why the focus of this research project will be on roles in middle management.

When looking at this curriculum of 2014, internationalisation seems to get more attention compared with the previous version. There is more emphasis on topics such as cultural differences, the English language and international perspectives within different knowledge areas such as Human Resources Management. The profile consists of competencies that are described and agreed upon at a national level. One of the goals of this new profile is to create a standard in the Netherlands and to give the programme recognition in the international arena. On closer scrutiny, areas such as cross-cultural or inter-cultural aspects are missing in the profile. The question is, therefore, whether future managers are being educated in such a way that they are prepared to work in international environments. Answering this question belongs to the aim of research executed in this project.

To further reduce the scope and to be able to execute an in-depth analysis, the focal point of the study will be the Dutch-German business environment. The Dutch-German trade volume is one of the largest in the world, with 161,3 billion euro in 2014 (Federal Foreign Office Germany). Germany is the most important trade partner for the Netherlands, for both import and export. The Netherlands is the second largest trade partner for Germany, just after France. According to the Federal Foreign Office, only the USA and Canada have a larger trade volume.

Finally, alignment between HEIs and organisations can be viewed from different angles. Students may choose a bachelor programme based upon their own interest, and are probably also influenced by families, friends and relatives. This may result in a situation where many students opt for social studies and less students for technical studies. This has consequences for the labour market. Alumni of certain studies may stay unemployed for a long time because the market does not offer enough vacancies. This is problematic for HEIs and for students, because it is sometimes difficult to predict which business areas will develop during the years of study. This alignment challenge is out of scope for this project. In scope is the comparison of offered competencies by HEIs with those demanded by the future employers of the students, and more specifically the identification of business administration competencies that are important in an international work environment.

Summarising the previous sections, this research focuses on internationalisation, competency and competencies, alignment and one curriculum that is used by 14 HEIs in the Netherlands. This is done by looking at middle management of Dutch organisations that conduct business with Germany. The researcher executed a literature review and a literature analysis in order to produce the theoretical framework which underpins the field research. The research starts with the following research questions that will structure the research project.

1.2 Research goal and research questions

The primary aim of this study is to investigate the gap between offered competencies within HEIs in the Netherlands, and the competencies needed when working in an international environment, looking at middle management in the Netherlands.

The main research question is:

How should the gap between offered competencies by HEIs and the required competencies when working as a middle manager in the Dutch German business environment be managed?

Sub questions literature research:

1. What is the definition of higher education in the Netherlands?
2. What is a BBA?
3. What is middle management?
4. What are (international) competencies?

The literature research results and the theoretical framework are described in chapter two.

Sub questions field research:

1. What competencies are considered internationally important looking at the BBA programme offered by HEIs in the Netherlands?
2. What are the required competencies for middle managers working in the German-Dutch business environment?
3. What are the similarities and discrepancies between the BBA competencies offered in the Netherlands and the required competencies for middle managers working in the German-Dutch business environment?

The literature research methodology and the field research approach related to all sub questions can be found in chapter three.

1.3 Guide for the reader

In chapter one, an introduction is given regarding the topic and context of the research. Literature research was executed to identify the differences between “internationalisation” and “globalisation” and between “competence” and “competency”, which helped define a clear scope of the research project. This is then followed by the research goal and the research questions.

Chapter two contains the main results of the executed literature research and analysis and concludes with a summary of the findings, the theoretical framework and a description of the input for the field research methodology. This chapter answers the four literature research sub questions.

The third chapter first describes the overall research approach and methodology. The research project is divided in process steps that are described and depicted in a graphic overview. In addition, an overview of the potential gaps is provided that will be investigated in this study. This chapter also describes the detailed research methods of all sub questions.

In chapter four, the first field research question is answered, which addresses which competencies are considered internationally important when looking at the selected BBA curriculum offered by HEIs in the Netherlands.

Chapter five deals with field research sub question two and provides an answer to the question what the required competencies are for middle managers working in the German-Dutch business environment. This question is answered by executing a survey and analysing the results.

In chapter six, the discussion is described together with the findings of the research and the GAP analysis. This chapter addresses the similarities and differences in competencies when looking at offered competencies within HEIs in the Netherlands and the competencies needed working as a middle manager in an international business environment. This chapter will answer the third field research sub question by describing the gaps. Synthesising the results and analysis from literature review and field research, the researcher presents the resulting views and a proposal on how to manage the gaps.

Finally, in chapter 7, contributions to knowledge, implications for higher education and business organisations, and limitations and opportunities for further research are described. This research project closes with a personal reflection.

2.0 Literature analysis and theoretical framework

2.1 Introduction

This chapter aims to develop a theoretical framework regarding “higher education in the Netherlands”, “BBA” and “middle management”, and to investigate “competencies” in-depth as this is the main focus of this research. By looking at the findings of studies regarding “competencies”, the researcher aims to improve the understanding regarding this topic. The results of this research led to the theoretical framework that was used in the field research design; it forms the foundation for further field research with specialists in HEIs and with representatives of organisations in practice. The analysis presented in this chapter provides an overview of what is currently known about “competencies” and aims to identify gaps in literature. Finally, conclusions were drawn and recommendations were made on how to manage the described gaps.

This chapter presents the critical analysis of the literature to define the concepts “higher education in the Netherlands”, “BBA”, “middle management” and “competencies”. Regarding “middle management”, “higher education” and “BBA”, the aim was to find fitting definitions that are used in the following research methods to ensure the use of clear concepts in this research project. “Competency” and the plural “competencies” were researched in relation to HEIs and the international working environment. The focus of this research is on Higher Education in the Netherlands, a country that is part of the European Union and therefore influenced by European policies. The scope of the research is on the generalisability of results within the EHEA-region (European Higher Education Area).

At the end of the literature part, a short summary is given regarding the findings, i.e. gaps. This summary is followed by the theoretical framework and a description of aspects from literature research that are used as input for the field research design.

The next section describes the results regarding the first and second sub question that deal with higher education in the Netherlands in general and the BBA in particular.

2.2 Higher education in the Netherlands

2.2.1 The Netherlands in Europe

The education profiles in the Netherlands are based on competencies that are described on a European level. The Bologna Process is an initiative of France, Germany, Italy and the UK and was set up in 1998. More countries joined one year later with the launch of the Bologna Declaration (European Union 1999). The process is assessed every three years in ministerial

conferences (European Commission 2012). The aim was to introduce one comparable, compatible and coherent system for European higher education.

The degree structure in EHEA consists of three study cycles: Bachelor, Masters and Doctorates. These cycles are supported by a joint credit system, the European credit transfer system (ECTS). Other aims of the system are mobility of students and staff and internationalisation of higher education systems and institutions (European Higher Education Area 2014). The latter focuses on international visibility of the EHEA. This focal point is also called “Bologna in a global setting” or “international attractiveness”. The Bologna process also entails the development of European standards for internal and external quality assurance within EHEA (European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education 2009). The EHEA consists of 48 members plus the European Commission. Although most of them are countries in Europe (European Higher Education Area 2016) there are also countries that do not belong to the EU such as the Russian Federation and Norway. The progress with the EHEA is managed and monitored by Ministerial Conferences. These are organised every two to three years. Every country has its own system for higher education. Decision-making, quality alignment or any other aspect within the EHEA might therefore be a challenge due to the high number of members.

Most entities with the European Union use the word “competence” instead of “competency” in their communication. This lack of clarity is unfavourable, and it is not clear why this choice was made. The information obtained from EU-sources will therefore contain “competence” and “competences” next to “competency” and “competencies”. This is not a major limitation, because both “competence” and “competency” are used interchangeable and usually have the same meaning in EU-sources. In addition, the researcher will identify and analyse differences between the two when necessary.

One of the methods that was initiated to enable countries within the EHEA to work together more closely is to find a common “currency”. The European credit transfer and accumulation system (ECTS) is therefore an important part of the Bologna process. The aim of the ECTS (European Commission 2018a) is to increase the mobility of students in Europe and across EU-member states. Another aim is to make national systems compatible with each other. When national systems are different from each other, transferring from one university to one in another country can be problematic. This is why it is important to increase the transparency of qualifications. By using one common way of measuring what was learned and achieved within the EHEA, the mobility of students is made easier. The ECTS-credits are based upon workload and learning outcomes. Learning Outcome is defined within the EHEA by Cedefop (2008, p. 164) as:

Statements of what a learner knows, understands and is able to do on completion of learning process, which are defined in terms of knowledge, skills and competence.

When the ECTS is the common currency, learning outcomes can be defined as the common language within education-programmes in the EHEA-region. Compared with competencies, learning outcomes are more specific than competencies. Competencies are used to define the desired set of knowledge, skills and attitudes for graduates at the end of an academic programme. One competency can contain multiple detailed learning outcomes. A learning outcome should align with assessment tools at the modular level.

One academic year equals 60 credits, which usually is split into different components. The first cycle relates to the Bachelor degree and consists of 180 (3 years) to 240 (four years) credit points. The second cycle is the Master degree and usually consists of 90 to 120 credits with a minimum of 60 ECTS. The third cycle consists of a variety of doctoral study programmes and fully independent research. The usage of ECTS in this cycle varies and depends on the relevant country. For example, a full academic year's workload in the UK is 120 University Credit Units (UCS). The European equivalent is 60 ECTS (European Commission 2015).

In the years following 2000, many countries in Europe took the initiative to change from a knowledge approach to a competence approach in their curricula. The competence approach provided a broader view on student development. For this reason, the 2006 Recommendation on Key Competences for Lifelong Learning and European Reference Framework of Key Competences for Lifelong Learning (European Commission 2006) was developed. This document supported processes in many countries in Europe towards the competence approach.

The defined key competences have the aim to develop students to a level that may help them in their adult life. They provide the basis for further development throughout their lives. Key competences should ideally be developed on a continuous basis.

The following are described as key competences in the European Reference Framework of Key Competences for Lifelong Learning (European Commission 2018c, p. 13):

- *“Communication in the mother tongue”;*
- *“Communication in foreign languages”;*
- *“Mathematical competence and basic competences in science and technology”;*
- *“Digital competence”;*
- *“Learning to learn”;*

- *“Social and civic competences”;*
- *“Sense of initiative and entrepreneurship”;* and
- *“Cultural awareness and expression”.*

All competences are ranked with the same importance. The competences are defined as the combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes. Each defined key competence definition describes the required knowledge, skills and attitudes. The key competences support learning outcomes and are to be translated into national curricula and/ or learning programmes.

The following definitions (European Commission 2018c, p. 7) are used for knowledge, skills and attitudes:

- *“Knowledge: facts and figures, concepts, ideas and theories which are already established und support the understanding of a certain area or subject”;*
- *“Skills: the ability and capacity to carry out processes and use the existing knowledge to achieve results”;*
- *“Attitudes: disposition and mind-sets to act/ react to ideas, persons or situations; in the European Framework of Key Competences also including values, thoughts and beliefs”.*

After defining what competences are, it is also important to identify which competences are relevant and why. The European Commission wants to connect education with social developments in Europe. For this reason, a reflection paper in 2017 about the social dimension of Europe was written, describing that the world continues to develop and many changes have altered the European Union since 2006. The global financial crisis that started in 2007/ 2008 and the Brexit are just two examples of major changes. Likewise, tech companies have influenced societies and economies in Europe via i.e. digitalisation. In addition, major changes in demographics, mobility and the labour market have their influences as new jobs develop whilst others vanish. Furthermore, new forms of communication have evolved and climate change is inevitable. Because of the ongoing rapid changes and developments, the European Commission suggests that all humans in the world and in Europe should focus on sustainable development for all activities (European Commission 2017). As a result, societies and economies in Europe are in need of highly competent people, whilst at the same time, the required competences are continually changing. Furthermore, the report therefore highlights the importance of several skills; i.e. creativity, critical thinking, initiative taking and problem solving, in addition to the already identified skills such as literacy, numeracy and basic digital skills. The *“Reflection paper on*

the Social Dimension of Europe” stresses the importance of developing the right set of skills and competences. This is needed to maintain and develop living standards in Europe (European Commission 2017).

The above-mentioned developments in the world require a new perspective on Lifelong learning, which has to replace the 2006 recommendation. In January 2018, the European Commission published a document that provides background information and evidence for necessary improvements regarding Key Competences for Lifelong Learning (European Commission 2018c, p. 36). The Commission consulted different stakeholders and defined actions that are needed to update these existing Key Competences. The following three points were identified:

- *“(More) support for learners in all areas, including formal and informal learning and improve the development of key competences for life-long learning”;*
- *“The reference framework has to be updated to current and future needs”;*
- *“Active promotion of competence-oriented education, training and learning in life-long learning. More support for all actors, and start assessing and validating competence development”.*

The focal point is on the education of people of all ages.

The conclusion can be made that the (development of) Key Competences for Lifelong Learning is not very concrete. Although all relevant developments seem to be recognised, key-measures to support HEIs in their alignment activities are lacking. The review period of more than 10 years (12 years in this specific situation) does not seem to be enough to keep track of major developments in business and other environments occurring at a fast pace. The action to update the reference framework shows that this still has to be done. Continuous improvement based upon steady and real input from the environment of Higher Education seems to be the better option, but is not in place at the moment.

2.2.2 The higher education system in the Netherlands

As discussed in section 2.2.1, the higher education system in the Netherlands consists of three cycles. The change towards this new structure was realised in September 2002 (Nuffic 2018) with the implementation of the European Credit Transfer System (ECTS) which was implemented at the same time. With these changes, the Dutch government realised the importance of a quality system to monitor the quality of all bachelor and master programmes. As a result, a law was developed and implemented that ensured this quality approach. This new law, the Accreditation Law (Dutch: “Wet op de accreditatie”) was introduced in July 2002. With this law, a new organisation was set up which is responsible for the accreditation

activities: the Netherlands Accreditation Organisation or in Dutch the “Nederlandse Accreditatie Organisatie” (NAO) established to take responsibility for quality governance and accreditation activities. With this new organisation, the first accreditations were performed. Accreditation in the Netherlands means that the bachelor or master programme is state-recognised. In the year 2005, the NAO started to cooperate with the Dutch-speaking part of Belgium and became the NVAO: the “Nederlands-Vlaamse Accreditatie Organisatie” (Nederlands Vlaamse Accreditatie Organisatie 2018a).

The Dutch education system consists of three types of institutes. Higher education institutes (HEIs) can be divided into the group of HEIs that receive their budget from the state and a group that does not receive any money from the Dutch government. In total, 14 Universities and more than 50 Universities of Applied Sciences are government-funded institutes in the Netherlands. These institutes have the right by law to award official, state-recognised degrees. The tuition fees for the bachelor and master programmes in these HEIs are therefore defined by law.

Then there is the group of HEIs that receive no funding from the Dutch government, but have a formal approval to award state-recognised degrees. These are the so-called “aangewezen” or assigned Higher Education Institutes. These HEIs define their own tuition fees and are not bound by law in this area.

The third group of HEIs are called the private institutes. In the Netherlands, most organisations in this group are foreign HEIs. They are not formally linked to Dutch Law. However, they may request to go for a NVAO accreditation, but only when some specific requirements are met (Nuffic 2018).

The assigned and private HEIs are mostly commercially driven, active with internationalisation and are developing strategies (Coelen 2013). These HEIs are likely to be more pro-active compared to state-funded HEIs due to the commercial focus on organisations where their students are working.

In addition, the Netherlands has six large Institutes for International Education (IE’s). These institutes are part of a research university and offer a range of programmes. These programmes may lead to a Master degree and later a PhD degree. The approach of these institutes is to focus on the exchange of knowledge in a limited setting. Groups with different intercultural backgrounds are guided by experienced teachers who have worked in developing countries around the globe (Nuffic 2018).

All Dutch universities have structured their studies into three cycles. The division that was made is based upon the bachelor-master structure. The first cycle is the bachelor programme. This cycle is followed by a master programme with a standard duration of one

year. Depending on the chosen specialisation, the master may also take two years or three years. Finally, the student may choose to study further and take part in a research or a doctor's degree programme. This last programme usually does not provide any European credit points (ECTS) and has a duration of four years.

Higher education in the Netherlands has a binary system. This means that on the one hand research universities offer research oriented education and on the other hand universities of applied sciences offer higher professional education. The main difference between these two is the difference between the theory and the practice orientation of HEIs (Nuffic 2018). These two groups are labelled as research oriented HEIs and professional education oriented HEIs. The difference can be clearly explained when using the bachelor as an example. Universities of Applied Sciences focus more on the combination of theory and practice in their programmes. Students usually work with real-life problems and have to apply theory in practice. The bachelor in these HEIs has a duration of four years, and provide 240 ECTS. Research Universities focus more on theory and less on practice. The more scientific oriented Research University bachelor programmes have a duration of three years, and provide 180 ECTS (Nuffic 2018).

The Dutch Qualifications Framework (NLQF) has put the bachelor at Level 6. The master programmes are on Level 7 (Dutch Qualifications Framework 2018b). The doctorate study is on Level 8.

The object of this research is the Bachelor of Business Administration and is typically a study that fits in the professional education category. The following two paragraphs will explain the differences in more detail. It is important to understand the difference between the two to be able to clearly understand the research methods, instruments and questions in this research project.

2.2.3 Research bachelor

The main aim of research universities is to teach the student to work with academic knowledge and to work on independent academic research. The first university in the Netherlands, Leiden University (2018) was founded in 1575 by William of Orange. The 14 research universities offer different study programmes, such as economics, medicine, language and culture, law and public administration. One university is specialised in agriculture and three are specialised in technical studies.

The first cycle in a research university leads to either a Bachelor of Arts (BA) or Bachelor of Science (BSc) degree. Students who finish their law study successfully obtain the title Bachelor of Laws (LLB). The bachelor programme at a research university has a duration of

three years. Some universities divide their bachelor programme into a “propedeutische fase”, which is the first year, and the main part of the study, which comprises the other two years. Students at some universities have to obtain a minimum number of ECTS in the first year to be able to continue their studies. Every bachelor degree gives access to a master programme that has a similar study field. This does not have to be the same university. Students are allowed to choose another research university.

2.2.4 Professional bachelor

Dutch Universities of applied sciences offer higher professional education and programmes in seven disciplines: economics, teacher training, healthcare education, social work studies, engineering, agriculture and arts. Students have the choice from different educational programmes that are offered in almost all universities of applied sciences. Some institutes are specialised in one of these disciplines (Nuffic 2018).

As stated earlier, higher professional education consists of two cycles. The first cycle is the bachelor programme, with a total of 240 ECTS and a duration of four years. This cycle is followed by a master programme with a normal duration of one year, and 60 ECTS. Depending on the chosen specialisation, the master may also take two years (120 ECTS). The master degree may provide access to a doctoral programme, the third cycle in higher education. Access depends on the specialisation of the chosen bachelor and master programmes.

Students in professional higher education in the Netherlands may obtain the titles Bachelor of Arts or Bachelor of Science (BA/ BSc) or a bachelor title that includes the study direction, i.e. Bachelor of Economics or Bachelor of Education. All universities of applied sciences start their bachelor programmes with a “propedeuse”. This is the first year, which is followed by the main study programme of another three years. Some Universities of Applied Sciences set rules regarding the number of ECTS points that have to be reached after one year. This varies and usually lies between 40 and 60 ECTS points. When the student is not able to reach this minimum, he or she has to leave the programme. When the student reaches the final level for all competencies he or she has reached the final level of the bachelor study. An internship is compulsory for students in professional education. The purpose is to gain practical experience. The internship is usually planned in the third year of the study programme. The final study year includes writing a final research paper, which is focused on a real-life problem within an organisation.

The second cycle in professional higher education is the master programme. This cycle leads to the title Master of Arts or Master of Science (MA/ MSc) or a master title that includes the study direction, i.e. Master of Economics or Master of Education. In this second cycle, the student specialises further in a specific study direction. Part of the master is either a graduation project, or a final research paper which emphasises applied research.

The main aim of higher professional education is the transfer of theoretical knowledge towards a professional practice environment and related skills development. Per 1 September 2002, all former Dutch education programmes were converted into bachelor programmes in line with the European Bachelor-Master-structure (BaMa). The programmes are recognised by Dutch law, whilst quality assurance is covered by the NVAO (Nuffic 2018).

To complete the overview of the structure in the Netherlands regarding offers in higher education, a new level was introduced. In addition to bachelor and master programmes, professional higher education also offers associate degree (Ad) programmes. An associate degree is a two-year study in higher professional education. Students may transfer directly to the bachelor degree programme that is in line with the associate degree. This programme was offered and accredited by law since 1 January 2018 as an independent, function or professional-oriented course and has Level 5 (Dutch Qualifications Framework 2018b).

2.2.5 Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA)

The Bachelor of Business administration is part of the Bologna structure. The Netherlands (Nederlands Vlaamse Accreditatie Organisatie 2016) has defined four bachelor segments. All bachelor programmes in the Netherlands can be assigned to one of these four groups:

1. Bachelor of Arts (BA): focusing mainly on economics, languages, management, marketing and communication
2. Bachelor of Sciences (BSc): focusing mainly on accountancy, finance, informatics and communication systems
3. Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA): focusing mainly on business administration
4. Bachelor of Laws (LLB): focusing mainly on law

The scope of this research is a BBA programme. This BBA programme and its curriculum are based upon the so-called Dublin Descriptors. The Dublin Descriptors are a set of shared competencies for European countries that have adopted the BaMa-structure in Bologna. These shared competencies were described and formalised in Dublin in 2004 (Joint Quality Initiative Meeting), and describe qualifications awarded to students that signify completion of

the bachelor (BBA) level in this case. The descriptors are used as competence levels and are described in a broad way. The goal is to increase the mobility of students by using the same (definition of) competencies. Learning outcomes are not considered; instead the achievements and abilities are associated with the end of each Bologna level (i.e. bachelor and master). The disadvantage is that HEIs depend on competence descriptions set in Europe and for all relevant countries. Due to the fact that the descriptions are fairly generic, there is some but not much room to adapt them to the country specifics.

All Bachelors of Business Administration in the Netherlands are based on four pillars:

1. Sound theoretical basis
2. Research capabilities
3. Professionalism
4. Ethics and environmental sensitiveness

All higher education programmes in the Netherlands receive a number from the “Centraal Register Opleidingen Hoger Onderwijs” (CROHO) once they have successfully been accredited by the NVAO (Rijksoverheid 2016). This register contains the list of all state recognised higher education programmes in the Netherlands. These numbers can be found online via the website of Dienst Uitvoering Onderwijs (DUO) (2016).

A BBA-programme covers many areas and has a wide focus. The core topics usually comprise accounting, business law and ethics, economics, finance, management information systems, marketing, operations management, organisational behaviour, quantitative techniques (business statistics, financial mathematics, operations research) and strategic management. This large number of topics is both an advantage and a disadvantage. The BBA alumni leave the University of Applied Sciences with a broad foundation and are able to secure employment within multiple sectors, organisations and positions. The disadvantage is that the curriculum leaves no room for specialisation, and makes it therefore difficult to align with specific roles and responsibilities in practice. The result is that alumni must learn more on the job or via extra additional courses in the first years of their life as an employee when compared to bachelors with a smaller, more specialised scope. In contrast, alumni of the Bachelor of Laws know that the Dutch law is their working environment which will not be different in one law firm or the other. The job location will almost always be in the Netherlands. BBA alumni, however, can find work within i.e. trade, logistics, the tourist industry and industry in any country (Nuffic 2018).

2.2.6 The curriculum

The curriculum of the Bachelor of Business Administration is comprised of the modules that have to be taught and learned. Each module has pre-defined goals that should be reached. The Ministry of Education, Culture and Science in the Netherlands sets the standard. This standard is checked and assessed regarding the quality by the “Nederlands Vlaamse Accreditatie Organisatie” (NVAO), the Dutch Flemish Accreditation Organisation (Nederlands Vlaamse Accreditatie Organisatie 2018b). The curriculum of the BBA contains the competencies that are being researched, which is why it is important to understand what a curriculum is and how these are developed. Furthermore, since the curriculum contains all competencies to be taught, it is important to understand the curriculum concept and how it relates to alignment.

A curriculum can be defined in different ways. Kelly (2009) states that the concept “curriculum” is used for many sorts of programmes, teaching and instructions. He stresses that it should be made clear which definition is used when using the concept. Wiles (2009) agrees that the term “curriculum” has many meanings and different definitions. Looking at the definitions, a distinction can be made between four approaches. The first approach defines curriculum as a set of written books and syllabi. A certain set of knowledge has to be taught and learned. This is the oldest and according to Wiles the most used definition. The product approach defines the concept as a description of activities and attempts to achieve certain ends in students. Education products are defined belonging to the curriculum. This approach includes extra-curricular activities. The third approach is the process view, which is connected to pre-set goals. The process approach means that a series of activities were chosen that must be executed in a planned way whilst focusing on the goals that have to be reached. The last approach is a further development of the process approach and focuses on the outcome; specific knowledge, skills and attitudes have to be gathered to be able to achieve the aims. This combined development of knowledge, skills and attitudes is in line with the definition used within the European Union as described earlier. The last group of definitions accepts change, variables in planning and has a more practical approach (Wiles 2009). This approach does not take other personal aspects such as motivation into account.

Another definition developed by Harford, Director Education at Ofsted, the Office for Standards in Education, Children’s Services and Skills in the UK, divides the curriculum in three elements: 1) intent 2) implementation and 3) impact/ achievement (Harford 2018). He defines curriculum as a framework for setting out the aims of an education programme, including the knowledge and understanding to be gained at each stage (intent); for translating that framework over time into a structure and narrative, within an institutional

context (implementation) and for evaluating what knowledge and understanding pupils have gained against expectations (impact/ achievement). One important added value of this definition is the evaluation of activities against a pre-set aim. This definition has a functional approach and does not include a method on how the aims should be defined.

Although the term “curriculum” is likely used by many HEIs, the question what a curriculum is seems to be difficult to define. According to Young (2014) there is little consensus in literature; there is not one agreed definition. In addition, it seems that the discourse in literature lacks the discussion regarding the original purpose of the curriculum, which is developing students to the required level in the job market. Curriculum theory and practice originates from a context of education and seems to have stayed there.

Curriculum development deals with developing and improving the (existing) curriculum. The curriculum is developed and managed by HEIs. Questions that have to be answered when designing a curriculum according to Tyler (1949) are objectives, content, methods and evaluation. Based upon these four elements Kelly (2009, p. 15) suggests four fundamental questions, relevant for the development of any curriculum:

- which purposes should be defined and why?
- what content should be included, and what not? Why is certain content more important and other content less? Which learning methodologies have to be used and why?
- what are the implications for teaching, learning and organising?
- how to determine whether the purposes are reached?

After having answered these and other questions the curriculum is established. This planned and developed product is also called the formal curriculum. The opposite of the formal curriculum is the informal curriculum, which relates to the informal activities in a learning environment such as sports and societies. Kelly indicates that these are regularly called “extracurricular” activities. Another form is the hidden curriculum, defined by Kelly (2009) as the sometimes unexpected learning effects of the planned work within a school. Social roles are an example of the hidden curriculum. By working in groups or just going through the programme, students interact with each other and develop their social skills.

Another version is the null curriculum, which is considered to be that what is not taught (Eisner 1985). As a result, students may conclude that these subjects are not important in the education programme and/ or in our society. The reason for the absence of certain topics in the curriculum can be that the HEI has intentionally decided that due to several reasons certain subjects will not be taught. The HEI may also simply not be aware of the importance

of a certain subjects and has therefore not considered including these subjects into the formal curriculum. Eisner (1985) indicates three reasons for the last point. The first reason can be the absence of considerations or perspectives. The second one relates to not being able to use processes that evaluate the potential (importance of the) material for the curriculum. His third reason is plain ignorance on the side of the HEI. Whatever the reason, the null curriculum does have consequences. What students do not process as a result of the absence of certain subjects in the programme cannot be learned and may have consequences for their lives. If the null curriculum for example exists of competencies that are important for working in an international environment and are required by business organisations it has a direct impact on alignment. Related to internationalisation, Coelen (2015) suggests that subjects important for working in an international environment should intentionally be planned in the curriculum.

John Dewey in his role as reformer of education has described his ideas regarding the role of education and how it should be executed. In his work “The child and the curriculum” (1911), he states that effective education is realised by presenting content using a methodology that enables the student to combine the given information with prior experiences. This way the way of learning is deepened. This emphasises the necessity to not only think about what needs to be learned, but also how it should be learned. Dewey has warned against using the definition of the curriculum that only focuses on that what needs to be taught, also from a practice point of view. The difference between the planned curriculum and the received curriculum has to be minimised in order to be successful in connecting theory to practice. A large gap between theory and practice would mean that the offered theory does not always match the real-life situations in practice and the context of the student.

The next chapter describes the BBA-curriculum that is used in this research, how it was developed and how it is linked with the future working environment of the students in the programme.

2.2.7 The BBA-curriculum

The BBA-curriculum referred to in this study is used by 14 Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands. The complete title of the selected bachelor study is: “Bacheloropleiding Bedrijfskunde MER” or Bachelor of Business Administration (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014). The relevant CROHO number for the Bachelor programme in this study is 34319. BKM stands for “Bedrijfskunde Management MER” (“management, economie en recht”); in English: Business Administration, Management and Law. A successful completion of this study programme leads to the degree Bachelor of Business Administration (BBA).

The commission that reviews this curriculum every six years is called the National Education Commission for the Business Administration Programme (Dutch: “Landelijk opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde MER”; the abbreviation is LLO BKM). This document with the described profile forms the basis for the business administration curricula of all 14 HEIs in the Netherlands (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014). It is a strategic document which shows which part of the labour market is the target group, and which job positions are targeted with this curriculum. The profile also describes the ambition of the programme. On a tactical level this document provides a framework that can be used to align the demands of employers and the offer provided by the relevant HEIs. “On the job” or work-based learning can be aligned with learning in a HEI environment. The profile consists of three parts.

The first part of the profile refers to the trends and developments in professional practice, as well as the demand in the job market. This profile is written in the form of an offer. What is expected of the BKM programme is defined by describing the professional practice and the roles of BKM graduates at the present. Trends in higher economic education are used to motivate choices that were made regarding the content of the programme.

The second part of the profile contains the basic descriptions in the profile. This description shows how HEIs want to meet the expectations of the organisations where their graduates are going to work. Competencies are used to describe the aims regarding the professional skills of the graduates. Here the emphasis lies on theoretical knowledge, the research cycle and the role as a knowledge worker.

The third part of the profile describes the choices that were made in the curriculum and how these were made accountable.

The description in the curriculum regarding job opportunities conveys a diverse picture. It states that any graduate in business administration may find a large field of work opportunities. The choice regarding positions and business is very diverse which is both an opportunity and a disadvantage. One of the opportunities is that the programme sets a wide basis upon which the student can decide later in which directions and specialisations he or she wants to go. This requires an extra step, however, for example a Master study. This is one of the disadvantages of the BBA-study: it provides a wide basis without much room for specialisation; another study is required to deepen the knowledge or the student has to make the choice to go for learning & development on the job after graduation. The authors of the curriculum provide some examples regarding opportunities for graduates. These can be found in the management of business processes, in knowledge intensive services and in network organisations who are very service-orientated. The professional practice covers all sectors of society. Jobs are found in:

- Organisations in specific private business environments
- Social enterprises
- Governmental and non-governmental organisations
- Network organisations

This is a rather broad description of sectors in which alumni might find a job.

Jobs relate more to content and what needs to be done while a role is more related to the context of the work and how value is added (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014). Job descriptions are updated more quickly due to rapidly changing responsibilities resulting from changes in the environment. Rapid changes in the environment are just one of the reasons why roles should replace “jobs” and “professions”. There are a number of factors that are identified by the authors of the curriculum that fuel these changes; a list of these trends can be found in table 2.1.

Research by the curriculum developers resulted in three groups of roles within the previously described job areas:

- Consultancy role
- Leadership and result-oriented role
- Research role

The curriculum tends to be built on trends in society that have to be managed by the graduates. The programme focuses on the development of knowledge and skills that have to work with the identified trends. The following trends were used for motivating the choices made in the curriculum regarding the required BBA knowledge and skills (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014):

Number	Description of the trend
1.	Innovation management
2.	Knowledge management and contributing to the knowledge economy
3.	Guiding and coaching employees in innovations
4.	Change management in organisations regarding products, services and
5.	ICT to optimise company processes
6.	Initiate ICT-processes, guidance and implementation
7.	Internationalisation
8.	Developments abroad
9.	Cultural awareness
10.	International literature and knowledge of the English language

11.	Quality control and quality improvement
12.	Project- and programme management
13.	Governance, risk management and compliance

Table 2.1: Trends, translated from curriculum description BBA, depicted by researcher (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014)

It is remarkable that “internationalisation” is listed, but “globalisation” is missing, because both are important developments. No explanation was found in the curriculum for this absence. There seems to be an overlap between “ICT” and the “initiation of ICT-processes”. In addition, there also seems to be an overlap between “developments abroad” and “internationalisation”. Furthermore, “guiding and coaching employees” could partly cover “change management in organisations”. The general point that the authors want to make with all these trends is the importance of leadership and coaching within organisations.

The authors of the curriculum also pay attention to developments in higher education. As a result, the quality of education will be improved by focusing on four pillars:

- A solid theoretical knowledge base;
- Research ability;
- Professional craftsmanship;
- Professional ethics and social orientation.

The focal point of any business administration student in this curriculum is on improving and renewing business processes. This should be done by analysing, designing and implementing processes in and between organisations. The bachelor programme teaches students to look at organisations from a broad perspective which will lead to versatile graduates. This core promise and the core competencies are the backbone of the competency profile. The competencies are split in five task competencies and nine generic competencies. Together they form the final qualifications for the business administration student.

The task competences are derived from the “regulatory cycle”: problem identification-diagnosis-design-change-evaluation. This is a practice-oriented method developed by van Strien (1986). The word “regulatory” means that the cycle is aimed at intervention in practice and at decision-making. This is the approach used for the business administration cycle in this curriculum.

The task-competencies in the following table are listed in the Dutch language and translated in English. These five focus on acting in business administration environments. The word “Bedrijfskundig Management” and abbreviation “BKM” has not been translated in table 2.2 and can be read as: business administration.

No.	Taakcompetentie (Dutch)	Task competencies (English)
1.	De BKM-professional is in staat om problemen van organisatorische aard te herkennen, te formuleren en consistent operationeel uit te werken tot een organisatievraagstuk en dit bij beslissers onder de aandacht te brengen.	The BKM-professional is capable of recognising organisational problems, formulating them and working them out consistently operationally into an organisational issue and bringing this to the attention of decision-makers.
2.	De BKM-professional is door onderzoek in staat een diagnose te stellen over de effectiviteit van een organisatie en de achtergronden, oorzaken en samenhangen van het disfunctioneren.	By conducting research, the BKM-professional is able to make a diagnosis about the effectiveness of an organisation and the backgrounds, causes and correlations of areas of dysfunction.
3.	De BKM-professional is in staat om de effectiviteit van een organisatie te verbeteren door op basis een programma van eisen en evidence based practice bedrijfsprocessen te (her) ontwerpen.	The BKM professional is capable of improving the effectiveness of an organisation by (re-)designing business processes based on a programme of requirements and evidence based practice.
4.	De BKM-professional is in staat om (complexe) veranderingsprocessen vorm te geven en te (bege)leiden, waardoor de gewenste situatie voor de organisatie wordt gecreëerd. Hij hanteert hierbij een integrale en op draagvlak gerichte aanpak.	The BKM professional is capable of shaping and leading (complex) change processes, thereby creating the desired situation for the organisation. He uses an integral approach based on support.
5.	De BKM-professional is in staat om door onderzoek de effectiviteit van verbeteracties te beoordelen en advies te geven over eventueel	The BKM professional is capable of assessing the effectiveness of improvement actions through research and advising on possible

	vervolgonderzoek. De evaluatie is gericht op de juistheid van de diagnose, oplossingsrichting (ontwerp) en de implementatie.	follow-up research. The evaluation focuses on the correctness of the diagnosis, solution direction (design) and implementation.
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Table 2.2: Task competencies BBA, depicted by researcher (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014)

The above listed competencies will obtain value for the student by using and applying theoretical knowledge for real life practical problems. During operations, the professional shows his or her professionalism and research capabilities. A business administration professional does not only demonstrate being competent in business. He or she is also a highly educated professional who has corresponding generic skills. When exercising his or her duties, he or she therefore also appeals to the nine generic competencies.

No.	Generieke competenties (Dutch)	Generic competencies (English)
1.	Methodisch handelen	Acting methodically
2.	Schakelen en verbinden	Switch and connect
3.	Adviseren	Advise
4.	Innoveren	Innovate
5.	Samenwerken/ netwerken	Cooperation / networking
6.	Communiceren	Communicate
7.	Verantwoord handelen	Act responsibly
8.	Professionaliseren	Professionalisation
9.	ICT-vaardig	ICT-skilled

Table 2.3: Generic competencies BBA, depicted by researcher (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014)

These generic competencies are in line with the Dutch standard regarding business administration which was determined on 15th of June 2012 by the “HBO-raad”, the Dutch association of Universities of Applied Sciences (HBO-raad 2012). This standard is applicable for all higher professional education in the Economic Sector. It has the aim to increase the quality of education. The quality can be linked to the Dutch Qualification Network (NLQF) and the associated Dublin descriptors (Joint Quality Initiative Meeting 2004). The latter relates to the following quality categories:

1. Knowledge and insight
2. Application of knowledge and insight
3. Judgment

4. Communication

5. Learning skills

The research subject for this project concerns a BBA-curriculum that can be tracked from European standards to Dutch national standards, and finally to a standard that is used by fourteen universities of applied sciences. The 14 competencies of this curriculum are used in this thesis.

According to the authors of the BBA profile, input was sought and obtained by 1) representatives of regional organisations, 2) representatives of universities of applied sciences and 3) the Association of Universities of Applied Sciences. The document does not provide a clear view on how alignment is sought with organisations in the field on a regular basis. The assumption is that this is done by a “werkveldadviesraad”, an advisory board with representatives from the field.

The conclusion can be drawn that the competencies on a high level do relate to the international standard. Additionally, enough input seems to be obtained by representatives of peer universities, but the alignment with the job environment of the graduates does not get much attention. Developing a bachelor programme in line with national quality standard seems to be more important.

2.2.8 Dutch qualification frameworks and quality management

In recent years, the European Higher Education Area paid much attention to qualification frameworks. The two main aims were to encourage mobility of students and their teachers and to support the recognition of qualifications. Learning outcomes were used as the common denominator. The 2008 EQF recommendation (European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training 2018) uses the definition as can be found in section 2.2.1. The Qualifications Framework of the European Higher Education Area (QF-EHEA) was developed as a part of the Bologna process (Bologna Process Coordination Group for Qualifications Framework 2016) with the aim to stimulate mobility of employees and learners within the EHEA region. The Dutch national framework NLQF is based upon the European Qualifications Framework for Lifelong learning (EQF). This framework describes the knowledge, skills and autonomy-responsibility that can be linked to all eight levels. The EQF is a tool developed with the purpose of supporting and stimulating the acceptance of qualifications from different countries in the EHEA-region. Each country has to place specific qualifications in all levels, thus creating a national qualification framework. These descriptions are based upon secondary, higher and vocational training and non-formal educational programmes and adult education. An important factor is the alignment between

EQF and NQF. The NLQF was formally aligned to EQF in 2012 via a formal referencing process (Nationaal Coördinatiepunt NLQF 2011). Since then, a National Coordination Point (NCP) monitors progress and managing the qualifications in the framework (Dutch qualifications framework 2018a).

Programmes in higher education are recognised by Dutch law under the condition that quality control is executed by the NVAO. The main task is to monitor the quality in the Netherlands and in the Dutch-speaking part of Belgium. The quality is defined by the tasks described in the Higher Education and Research Act; in Dutch, the “WHW”. The two main tasks are monitoring and assessing quality of study programmes in higher education. A formal state accreditation is not obligatory. However, student loans and grants are only provided to students who are registered in an accredited study programme.

The process roughly follows the following steps. First, a review committee is appointed by the HEI which assesses the quality of the study programme. Different experts have to be consulted. The assessment has to be based upon criteria set by the NVAO regarding accreditation and assessments of study programmes. Finally, the NVAO takes a decision based upon the report provided by the review committee. A programme is accredited for a period of six years.

Since 2011, another way of providing accreditation is being used in the Netherlands. HEIs may request an institutional quality assessment. This way the institute is assessed and not the study programme. The idea is that the institute has to be capable of guaranteeing the quality of the offered programmes. All programmes still have to be accredited, but the procedures take less time per programme and are not as extensive.

As a national quality organisation, the NVAO is a member of the European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education (ENQA) (European Association for Quality Assurance in Higher Education 2018). In the role of promotor of quality assurance across Europe this association as was one of the founders of an official register of Quality Assurance Agencies (QAA) and provide guidelines for Quality assurance within EHEA (European Quality Assurance Register for Higher Education 2018). The NVAO is also a member of the European Consortium for Accreditation (ECA) (European Consortium for Accreditation in higher education 2018). This organisation has the ambition to be the driver regarding innovation in accreditation and quality assurance within EHEA.

The CROHO-register contains all programmes that are accredited in the Netherlands as already explained in section 2.2.5. This is the Central Register of Higher Education Study Programmes and can be accessed online. This list is important from a quality point of view because it lists all programmes that are executed by government-funded and approved HEIs.

If the programme is not registered in this database, quality assurance by the Dutch government does not apply. However, it could be that quality is assured by another country or another quality institute.

The main topic in the above described procedure is “quality” in higher education. Quality in the Netherlands is defined and assessed by the described method of accreditation. However, quality can be defined in multiple ways. The “Onderwijsraad”, the independent advisory board of the Dutch Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, recognises this. They have stated that the quality of higher education is ambiguous. There are multiple definitions and visions regarding quality in higher education, which have a legitimate base but may also conflict with each other. The differences depend on the chosen parts of education, the viewpoint of the one defining the vision, the methodology and the underlying norms and values (Onderwijsraad 2015, p. 14). They give the following definitions of quality or what they call “good education”:

1. Complying with the defined end-levels of the programme and reaching the described goals regarding learning. This definition focuses on reaching a certain level regarding knowledge and skills necessary to perform in a certain job. Within this definition there are multiple variations such as having a good knowledge in a certain field of expertise or being able to function in society in a good way or finally the aim to obtain knowledge as the more academic purpose of education.
2. The opposite of the first view is the focus on the development of the individual student. This perspective does not aim to reach a certain level, but aims to increase the knowledge and skills of the student and also to change the personality of the student. Within this view, education aims to maximise the personal development of each individual student.
3. The third view considers quality to be relative. Quality means excellence and being able to outperform. Higher education delivers quality if the students perform better in one programme compared with their sister-programmes.
4. A more social perspective is the view that education programmes exist to give as many students as possible an education and a certificate. This approach can be combined with the perspective to reach minimum standards regarding quality.
5. Another view is the measurement of satisfaction. This can be the satisfaction level of students, employers or alumni.
6. The last view is the one where efficiency plays a major role. Here the focus is on the process, and aims to deliver as many students to the required end-level as possible while minimising costs.

The advisory board states that many definitions can be a good sign as it indicates that there is a discussion regarding quality and the meaning of this concept in higher education. The risk they describe is that the stakeholders can have different views and that the vision on quality within the institute has to be consistent. Different views of quality can undermine alignment between the competencies developed in bachelor programmes and the competencies needed in practice.

The Minister for Education, Culture and Science of the Netherlands states in a strategic document that substantial investments are necessary to maintain and strengthen the position of Dutch higher education (Ministerie van Onderwijs 2015). She indicates that Dutch Higher Education is mainly focusing on knowledge transfer and qualification. It is her ambition to add two tasks in the year 2015: socialisation and personal development. The report concludes that there is no structural form of cooperation between HE and practice and concludes that more cooperation is needed. At the same time the statement is made that Higher Education is not only about what students want to learn, but also about what the HEI thinks students should want to learn. However, this disregards other stakeholders and seems to contradict with the statement regarding the need for more cooperation with practice.

The next section describes the results regarding the third sub question that deals with middle management.

2.3 Middle management

This section presents the results of the literature review regarding middle management. It is important to obtain a good working definition of this concept, because the aim of the BBA is to prepare students for middle management roles in various environments in the field of business administration. As described in section 2.2.7, the BBA programme defines three roles in the curriculum (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014):

1. Advice role
2. Leadership and result-oriented role
3. Research role

Once employed, possible roles with the BBA certificate are e.g. project manager, team leader or other management roles. These roles usually take a central position in any organisation: executing the strategy that comes from general management and leading employees in their day-to-day responsibilities. It is important to select a definition of middle manager and to understand its position in the organisation in order to be able to identify the necessary competencies.

Looking at management in an organisation, Henri Fayol can be considered as one of the founding fathers of management theory. He has described roles of management (Fayol 1917) and attributes five functions to a manager:

1. Looking ahead;
2. Organising;
3. Delegating;
4. Coordinating;
5. Checking and monitoring.

Although the functions almost completely comprise management roles, there are aspects missing. The five functions omit several important roles, which are: to manage relationships, creative problem solving and building a team. Furthermore, the five functions are based on Fayol's own experience. There has not been any empirical research. Finally, the external focus is missing. Customer needs are not taken into account. This results in the conclusion that organisations are structured to service the needs of that same organisation. A structure to service the needs of the customer is better, as this will support reaching the company goals.

Aucoin (1989) defines the middle manager as the link between senior management and the lower management levels of an organisation. As the link between operations and upper management, they can be regarded as the channel of communication. The middle manager can give valuable information and suggestions from the lower levels in the organisations and, vice versa, communicate major decisions, goals and strategic direction. As a result, the competencies of middle managers are therefore directly related to organisational success (King, AW, Fowler, S.W. and Zeithaml, C.P. 2001).

Middle managers take a central position in organisational hierarchies (Harding 2014). They must implement senior management plans by ensuring that junior staff fulfil their roles. Middle management can be divided into three task areas (Dance 2011): technical tasks, such as administration; people tasks, such as motivating; and strategic tasks, such as analysis and strategic communication. As a result, middle managers have to play many different roles and styles within an organisation. Talking with senior management requires a different style compared with talking to the subordinates and can lead to conflicts when used incorrectly. Conflicts and opposing forces in the organisation can be linked to this position. Harding (2014) states that the exploration of the identity of the middle manager offers contradictory insights. She suggests that middle managers are both controlled and controllers. They are also resisted and resisters. Rather than being slotted into organisational hierarchies, middle managers constitute those hierarchies. Middle managers can get stuck

between different stakeholders when, for instance, a change from top management conflicts with the views of his or her subordinates.

The role of middle management is clearly associated with both the operational and strategic levels of the organisation. Specific competencies are needed to fulfil this role. Anthony Dance (2011, p. 2) gives the following list of competencies that are needed for middle management positions:

- Strong commercial focus
- Self-development and learning
- Personal effectiveness
- Management team development
- Performance management
- A desire for continuous improvement
- Managing change

These competencies are described in a broad way, leaving room for different interpretations. The question regarding how these competencies should be measured is answered by Dance by stating that performance can only be measured by assessing the line managers in the team of the middle manager. This is context-driven, however, as not all middle managers will have line managers in the team.

Dance (2011) also lists key skills that any middle manager should have:

- Management by objectives: setting objectives and making sure targets are achieved;
- Training and coaching: coaching and training subordinates;
- Communicating assertively: being assertive in all forms of communication and towards all stakeholders;
- Poor performance management: how to turn-around poor performances;
- Talent management: the identification and further development of talent.

These skills are related to the position in the organisation. Team leadership is more important and challenging than strategic leadership according to Dance.

According to Henry Mintzberg, a manager practices 10 roles categorised in three types of activities (Mintzberg 1989):

1. Interpersonal activities: representation of the organisation to the outside world
 - a. Figurehead, leader and liaison
2. Communication activities: communicating both internally (to subordinates) and externally
 - a. Monitor, disseminator and spokesperson

3. Decision-making activities: converting information into planned actions:
 - a. Entrepreneur, disturbance handler, resource allocator and negotiator

Mintzberg defines middle management as connecting managers (Mintzberg 2015, p. 2). They stand between central management and operations and bring good ideas from operations to the management of the organisation. Mintzberg states that “top management” should be replaced by the title “central management”. Central management has a central position in the management structure and needs connecting management to transfer the strategy and strategic goals to the operational level. He argues that middle management should not be the first to be removed as a result from restructuring plans. Mintzberg has the opinion that middle managers are essential in realising constructive change. Good middle management sees the big picture and can also operationalise plans into the organisation.

In summary, the conclusion can be drawn that middle managers are situated in the middle between central management and their employees. This means that they have to rely on a set of competencies that support this position and role. In addition, the needed competencies can be defined based upon the context of the job at hand.

The next section describes the results regarding the fourth sub question that deals with the literature perspective on competencies.

2.4 Competencies

2.4.1 Introduction

In chapter one, the difference between competence and competency was described and the decision was made to use competency as the leading concept. In this section, the “competency” concept is investigated further, using different angles. First the researcher investigates the classification and categorisation of competencies which helps to understand which groups of competencies belong together and why. Then competencies are researched looking from the angles of HEIs, the developments in the international working environment and the European Union & the Netherlands. Last but not least, research is executed regarding the alignment of competencies within the context and scope of this research project and how to identify gaps by using literature.

2.4.2 Classification of competencies

The classical definition of competencies is the combination of skills, knowledge and attitudes, for example the definition of the European Commission as described in section 2.2.1.

The combination of these three should give any human being the ability to perform, to show behaviour leading to success. If one of these three is not present or not at the required level, the employee runs the risk of not meeting the expectations linked to his or her job (European Commission 2018c). When an employee does have the knowledge and the skills for a certain job but lacks the attitude, he or she “only” knows the process. If the skills are not present, the employee only knows the purpose; if the knowledge is missing, the commitment is present but not the ability. It is important to know which aspect is necessary to perform within a certain role. “Attitudes” deal with learning, self-reflection, the perception of the own abilities regarding performance and setting desired goals; it also involves personal motivation. Attitudes are often associated with experience and are thus more difficult to develop within the sometimes more theoretical environments in HEIs, which might lead to a lower performance of the employee. According to the European Commission, knowledge, skills and attitudes are overlapping and also strengthening each other. To be effective in any job, competencies have to be well-defined and in line with the role that needs to be fulfilled. Within organisations, job profiles are often connected to competencies; within HEIs, the curriculum defines the end-level competencies. HEIs use tools to translate competencies to modules within their programmes.

As described in Section 2.2.1, competencies are used in HEIs to define end-levels of education programmes such as bachelor and master programmes. To improve alignment of all modules in the design of a curriculum, a framework was developed in 1956 for classifying statements of what students should learn because of planned and executed educational activities: Bloom’s Taxonomy. He defined three domains regarding learning activities: cognitive, psychomotor and affective; also known as knowledge, skills and attitudes (Bloom 1956).

Benjamin Bloom chaired the committee of College and University examiners in the USA that developed this framework. The first Taxonomy regarding the cognitive domain had six cognitive categories that were all defined. The categories were: “Knowledge”, “Comprehension”, “Application”, “Analysis”, “Synthesis”, and “Evaluation”. All but “Application” had subcategories.

The cognitive and affective domains were assessed and developed, the psychomotor domain has however been omitted. The motivation behind this decision was a lack of experience in teaching manual skills. Users of the model have to know this when putting the model into practice.

Blooms taxonomy is more than a simple classification. The model attempts to transform the various thought processes into a hierarchical model. The hierarchy levels are linked and

depend on each other. For example, to be able to apply knowledge properly (Level 3), someone must have the correct information (Level 1) and someone must be able to understand that information (Level 2). Taxonomy refers to classification. Bloom's model was developed in lower levels and higher levels. The higher level is the level that the student should achieve. Complexity rises when going up the ladder and the student acquires a higher level of thinking. The other three levels "Knowledge", "Comprehension" and "Application" can be defined as the lower levels, while "Analysis", "Synthesis" and "Evaluation" are the higher levels. As a result, the model is hierarchical. Students that reached the highest level of the taxonomy have also managed to achieve the lower levels (Forehand 2005).

Since 1956 the framework was developed further. It was discussed for many years in the committee of College and University examiners. Additional research regarding Bloom's model led to more understanding and interpretations. In the 90's, the taxonomy was evaluated and updated. This revision was initiated by one of the original co-editors of the taxonomy together with a former Bloom student. During the 1990's, this former student of Bloom, Lorin Anderson, organised a new team with the aim of updating the taxonomy. The main goal was to create more relevance for students and teachers studying and teaching in the 21st century. The team consisted of cognitive psychologists, curriculum theorists and instructional researchers, and testing and assessment specialists (Anderson 2001; Kratwohl 2002). After six years, the results were published in 2001. The new version of Bloom's Taxonomy included changes made in three categories: terminology, structure, and emphasis. The changes in terminology between the old and the new version do seem obvious but can cause confusion. The six major categories were changed from noun to verb forms. In addition, "Knowledge" has become "Remembering". This is the lowest level in the model. Furthermore, "Comprehension" and "Synthesis" were renamed to "Understanding" and "Creating". The following comparison image explains the changes.

What follows is a description of each of Bloom's six levels of instructional objectives in the cognitive domain, each in terms of the essential question with which it is associated. Furthermore, each level includes several representative action verbs that can be associated with that key question.

The new taxonomy can be a useful tool for HEIs to structure the content of their assessment methods. The verbs make assessment easier and can be attached to any discipline. Benjamin Bloom's taxonomy is very good at providing "verbs" that can be used to organise assessments within HEIs (University of Wisconsin–Madison 2018).

Critical assessment of Bloom:

- The original intention of Bloom was to create a model that helps to assess students, not to teach them. This can provide conflicts with the new purpose of the model.
- In line with this point it is important to know that students have to learn the lower levels first to be able to master the upper levels. Assessing the ability of students to handle the higher levels does not automatically mean that they have mastered the lower levels too.
- The model focuses on knowledge and attitudes, leaving skills untouched. This is why the taxonomy might be considered incomplete when comparing it with the definition of a competency: a set of knowledge, skills and attitudes.
- The model works well when the topics are aligned with the different levels of the taxonomy. In fact, the taxonomy should not be considered as a hierarchy.
- The taxonomy does not take into account self-knowledge and reflection or moving from incompetent to competent.

The Bloom Revised Taxonomy is used by the European Commission to describe the desired learning outcomes of study programmes in higher education (European Commission 2016a). Here the distinction is made between knowledge, skills and competence. The latter is defined as the ability to apply knowledge and skills. The new taxonomy of Bloom is presented, without acknowledging the three learning domains. It is suggested that the top categories (analyse, evaluate and create) with the related active verbs can be linked well to skills that have to be developed in higher education. The lack of attention to skills in the Bloom model can thus be solved. HEIs in the Netherlands use Bloom to describe learning outcomes. The instructions regarding writing module descriptions for the Dutch Qualification Framework describe Bloom as the leading Taxonomy to structure descriptions regarding learning outcomes (Nationaal Coordinatiepunt NLQF 2017).

When looking at other ways to classify competencies, Miller (1990) identified several layers within competencies. Within his approach, the differences between competency and competence are clear. Miller argues that when a test is meant to measure job competencies, it is crucial to make the assessment authentic. He describes being competent for a job in four layers. The lowest layer forms the fundament for the upper layers.

The “Know” levels are the cognitive levels and look at the knowledge a person has and also how to use this knowledge. The two top levels are the behaviour levels. The first three levels might be defined as the learning stages that are managed by HEIs. The “Does” level is where the learning and development takes place at the workplace.

At the bottom of the pyramid at the “Know How” level, the student involved should know what is required to carry out certain tasks. This knowledge is required to be able to execute a certain job. Miller indicates that a good and wide knowledge basis is very important. Knowledge is important, but takes a different position and is used in a different way. However, just having the knowledge does not add much value. According to Miller these people are merely “idiot savants”. The student must have sufficient knowledge and have the judgment and skills to be competent enough to provide results in the form of an analysis or plan. This is what the author calls “Knows How” and calls this the competence level. The next step goes from the study environment to a simulated real-life situation. Here the student has to show that he has the “Know” and “Knows How”. This is the performance level where the student “Shows How”. A Law student should for example know how he has to use his or her knowledge when writing a plea. Here a learning product can be identified; in this example, it is the written plea. Only in this triangle the student should truly perform. The top-layer is the situation where the student should be able to apply the acquired knowledge, skills and attitude in a complex real-life situation. At the end of this phase the student should be ready for the job market. Here the student has to be assessed according to what Miller calls: “*performance assessment in vivo*” (Miller 1990). Depending on the goal of the assessment, fitting assessment criteria have to be defined. This final level is where the graduate may be acting on his own in the workplace. Here professional behaviour involves actions that are difficult to measure in an accurate and reliable way.

In the medical world, a special form of performance-based testing was developed that fits in the final layer of Miller’s model (Harden 1988). Objective Structured Clinical Examination (OSCE) is a method that measures the medical candidates’ clinical competency. The candidates are under observation and are evaluated while they perform a series of actions. For example, they interview, examine and treat standardised patients who have some type of medical problem. The test-environment that is created for OSCE testing is very similar to the real environment. The processes of the clinic or hospital are used as well, which is why OSCE is a good example of performance assessment in practice.

The OSCE is an approach to the assessment of clinical competence in which the components of competence are assessed in a planned or structured way with attention being paid to the objectivity of the examination.

Authentic assessment is a method to close the gap between things that are expected of students when working after their study and the way they are assessed during their study (Gulikers 2005; Mueller 2005; Wiggins 1989). This way of assessing should ideally close the gap between education and the working environment, which makes it interesting from an alignment perspective. Examples of authentic assessments are portfolio building, (group)

projects and experiments/ demonstrations (Mueller 2016; Wyatt-Smith 2014). Next to authentic assessment, HEIs can also opt to use authentic learning for their study programmes. As an example, the Miller Pyramid is being used in the Netherlands by the University of Twente as part of the tools that support learning (University of Twente 2017). Authentic learning and assessment is explored in section 2.4.4.

One critique of Miller's model is that, when using the topic of this research project as an example, HEIs might be focusing too much on the first three levels and not enough on the "Does" level. This is a risk that has to be managed when using the model. Another criticism towards the model also deals with the "Does" level. Literature suggests (Cruess 2016) that the assessment of professional behaviour, which is what this level is about, can be improved. They suggest adding a level on top of the "Does", namely the "Is". This is the level where the student has to demonstrate the required and expected attitudes, values, and behaviours. Here the student has to prove that he or she can think and act and feel like a professional.

The suggested improvements of Millers Pyramid deal with the deeper levels of personal behaviour. Attitudes, behaviour and acting are aspects that are described in the Iceberg model, which helps to understand the competency concept and can be related to Sigmund Freud's "Iceberg model of Consciousness" (Kreiman 2018).

Figure 2.1: The Iceberg model of competencies, depicted by researcher, adapted from NHS London Leadership Academy (NHS London Leadership Academy 2017)

Freud has divided the human mind in three awareness levels (Kreiman 2010). They are the conscious, subconscious or preconscious, and unconscious. He stated that the underlying motives of behaviour are not visible and are situated in our subconscious and unconscious mind. This fits with the Iceberg model where 10% is considered to be the visible part of everyone's behaviour. This part is known to others as it can be observed, the other 90% is unknown. Knowledge and skills are the visible aspects of the iceberg and are relatively easy to change. The aspects underneath the water level are relatively more difficult to change. The deeper we go into the model; the more difficult change will be. The water is the context, which is required for "acting". In this Iceberg metaphor, acting will lead to ripples in the water and thus affect that same context.

The Iceberg model consists of six parts (NHS London Leadership Academy 2017). The part on top can be observed and the other parts cannot. The observable parts above the sea are knowledge and skills, supported by experience. According to the model, the elements in the following table are all components of a competency.

No.	Level	Related questions
1.	Skills: ability to do something	Do I have the ability? Can I act effectively?
2.	Knowledge: available content, information in certain fields of work	Do I know enough to act? Am I missing information? Do I understand the situation?
3.	Social roles, values: beliefs or ideals	Do I know the role to play? Do I consider this to be appropriate? Am I doing the right thing?
4.	Self-image: how people see themselves, identity, i.e. as an expert	Do I see myself doing this?
5.	Traits: personal characteristics, i.e. a good listener	Do I have the characteristics needed to do this?
6.	Motives: personality aspects, beliefs, driving force	Do I enjoy this? Does it give me energy?

Table 2.4: Iceberg level description and related questions, depicted by researcher (NHS London Leadership Academy 2017)

The importance of the model not only lies in the identification of visible and non-visible aspects of competencies, but also in the underlying differences and relationship between all elements; acting depends on all of the levels. Knowledge and skills levels can be identified relatively easily and developed further through education, training and skill-building exercises. The parts underneath are, however, according to Spencer and Spencer (1993) more difficult to assess and also more difficult to develop. The parts below the surface

directly influence the usage of knowledge and skills. A sales manager with a good knowledge of products, customers and market dynamics and with excellent skills may not perform very well if, for whatever reason, he or she is not motivated. The only way to change behaviour is to work on all levels of the iceberg. The observed behaviour of the top of the iceberg is linked to what lies underneath. This is why we humans relate tone of voice, facial expression and body language with unobserved aspects of the iceberg that are under water. The observed behaviour is a reflection of what lies underneath. If possible, flipping the Iceberg, thus making the invisible visible, would be an interesting exercise to clarify what lies underneath.

The Iceberg Model mainly focuses on visible and non-visible aspects of competencies. The visual aspects are related to knowledge and skills. Values, self-image, traits and motives are linked with the deeper motives of a person. Korthagen (2008) has a different approach regarding analysing the deeper levels of behaviour. He has developed the Onion Model which combines competencies using a holistic vision. This model shows different layers and starts at the deeper core of personal motivation. He has developed this approach as a result of growing unease regarding the effect of the use of competency lists for teaching in the Netherlands. A pure focus on meeting competencies does not motivate employees, or in the example of Korthagen, teachers. The motivation of teachers was lowered based upon the usage of competency checklists which did not take into account the context and the potential and motivation of the teachers. Korthagen (2004) states that multiple levels are important when looking at personal development. He calls this Multi-level learning (MLL). The idea behind MLL is that it does not only start from the teachers' own experiences and concerns. The implicit potential of the model is that it aims to harmonise the six different layers. Development of competencies is just one of the layers in the model. This vision results in a more holistic approach, which not only encompasses competencies. This model has become known as the Onion Model.

The advantage of the model is that the pure competency-based approach to learning is replaced with a holistic view on the development of the relevant person. It combines the answers to questions such as "what inspires me" and "who am I" with the competencies that have to be developed. The outer layers influence the inner ones, but it also works the other way around. He states that there are often discrepancies between the levels; i.e. when someone has a certain ability, but the related behaviour is not important or someone has a personal mission but does not want to talk about this.

Korthagen also claims that this approach also results in a different view on how competencies can develop. This relates to the vision of Tickle (1999) reflected by the following quotation: *"The teacher as a person is the core by which education itself takes*

place". There are more aspects important to being successful in a certain job than just having a correct set of competencies. An important principle of the model is that all layers play a role in every learning process; sometimes people are aware and sometimes not. If the learning process stops at a certain level, it is important to consciously reflect on the layers below it. Core reflection according to Korthagen is when the deepest levels of the model also receive attention during reflection. The model takes what Korthagen calls the "implicit potential", which is embedded in the inner layers of the model and the person. Education should therefore take place based upon the connection between the components: practice, theory and person. The similarity with Millers Pyramid and the Iceberg model is the focus on thinking, acting and feeling of the student or professional, which goes beyond the assessment of knowledge and skills.

In summary, literature suggests focussing more on the "Does" and "Is" as described in Millers Pyramid, the social roles, self-image, traits and motives as described in the Iceberg model and looking at a non-hierarchical way of assessing the abilities of students by applying a holistic approach to all levels. This way, the validity and reliability of the performance of students can increase.

2.4.3 Categorisation of competencies

The competencies of the individual are important for organisations because these can help in reaching the goals set in the organisation. Boyatzis (1982) already explained this through the results of his research on a cluster of competencies:

A capacity that exists within a person that leads to behaviour that meets the job demands within parameters of organisational environment, and that, in turn brings about desired results.

There are different types of competencies. The first division that can be made is:

- Basic competencies
- Professional competencies

The basic competencies are existent in all individuals, but can differ in level.

Basic competencies encompass: intellectual, motivational, emotional and social competencies.

Professional competencies are job-related and are placed above basic competencies. They can be classified as:

- General competencies: these are core for the job.

- Technical competencies: these are functional, belonging to specific roles.
- Managerial competencies: these are focusing on steering and motivating other employees.

General competencies encompass those that are essential for all staff. Managerial competencies are important for staff with managerial or supervisory responsibilities. Finally, functional or technical competencies are important for jobs within a defined functional or technical area (Boyatzis 2007).

Another categorisation is the one between the organisation and the individual:

- Core competencies: the competencies are related to the organisation.
- Workplace competencies: here the competencies are related to the individual.

These two categories can and should be linked with each other; the personal competencies of the individual should help realise and develop competencies attached to the organisation, which then can provide access to specific markets (Prahalad 1990).

Competencies can be linked to performances on the job. Boyatzis (2007) and Sanghi (2016) divide them into two categories:

- Threshold competencies: everyone needs them, as they are required to be minimally effective in the job.
- Differentiating competencies: these establish the difference between being able to perform on a superior or an average level.

When HEI-faculties focus on developing global mind-sets, this is due to focusing on the “international competency”. This requires different resources and commitment of resources (Kedia, BL, Harveston, P.D., and Bhagat, R.S. 2001). When developing global competencies, students will learn that international business is more than just crossing borders. Students have to learn to be able to engage markets in different ways.

2.4.4 Competencies within HEIs

HEIs evaluate their students upon their last year’s performance and use competencies for this purpose. Abraham and Karns (2009) have shown that businesses and business schools agree on the competencies that attach success to managers and graduates. However, according to the authors, these competencies are not emphasised in the curricula of business schools (Abraham 2009).

Aggerwal states (2011) that business schools face a number of challenges when looking at the influences that demographics, sustainability and technology have on business. According to Aggerwal, these three are also the fundamental driving forces for globalisation. As a result, business schools must focus on the attitudes, skills and knowledge helpful for student career flexibility including leadership skills, a good work ethic and abilities to continue learning. A few years later, Aggerwal (2014) highlighted that business schools are still facing challenges when looking at the effects that demographics, sustainability and technology have on business. Global imbalances occur due to different demographic developments. Sustainability and climate change require new policies. Finally, technology increases business and work changes. He goes on to suggest that these are also the fundamental driving forces for globalisation. As a result, Aggerwal suggests business schools must focus on the attitudes, skills, and knowledge that will be helpful for student career flexibility including leadership skills, a good work ethic and abilities to continue learning. They must select and develop the competencies that are in demand in business environments.

Organisations are increasingly complaining that education does not prepare students well for their practice (CNV jongeren 2018; Universities UK 2015). These complaints are the result of the changes in society in recent years in which other requirements are imposed on employees. In order to function properly in practice, employees nowadays have to be able to think critically and be able to apply knowledge in new situations. Working in the current business environment requires the ability to deal with rapidly changing technologies and communication possibilities. In addition, the employee has to be able to work in teams and to keep on learning. Higher education must adapt to meet these new needs. Developing professional competencies has become key.

Competency-oriented higher education does not focus on gaining separate knowledge and skills. This kind of education aims to integrate knowledge, skills and attitudes. Furthermore, students have to apply these competencies in relevant professional environments as for example described in section 2.4.2 related to the OSCE-model. According to Segers, Dochy and Cascaller (2003), this requires a new way of assessing. Different types of tests and assessments have to be developed, all aiming at testing professional competencies. The main argument is that students are confronted with realistic situations where they have to apply their knowledge and skills to solve realistic and preferably real problems. The professional practice should be the context of the test. This is different from testing that most HEIs were used to. In other words: the assessment must become more authentic, as described in section 2.4.2. But, authentic in which setting?

Meg Ormiston (2011) links authentic learning to the practice environment:

Authentic learning mirrors the tasks and problem solving that are required in the reality outside of school.

The professional practice is the starting point. Gulikers, Bastiaens and Kirschner (2005) state that testing should take place in a professional setting and organised accordingly. Progress is also important, as it cannot be expected that a first-year student performs tasks of graduates or professionals in the field. Therefore, tests have to be adjusted to the level of the student combined with a fitting business environment. A starting point for authentic assessing is the performance of the student against a fixed set of predetermined criteria; for example, when the student performs his or her internship. This learning standard can be used to develop authentic tests. HEIs have to look into professional practice to be able to describe what relevant professional situations look like. From there, the competencies used in practice by the professional can be used as reference.

Disadvantages of authentic testing can be found in the field of costs. The development of new tests requires a lot of time, money and effort. Taking the example of the internship, although the student is placed in a professional setting, the HEI is still responsible for the tests and their execution. Furthermore, when the study programme is broad and has many possible job positions that are not always clearly defined, authentic testing is more difficult due to the ambiguity of the professional field. The future professional field of the business administration is a good example. However, relevant critical professional situations can be defined for every programme. Some programmes need more described situations and some less.

Spencer and Spencer (1993) argue that there are two reasons regarding the need for competency-based training. The first is the need to increase performance, i.e. to be able to outperform competition. The other aspect is the desire to reduce the learning curve time from job entry to full production. The assumption here is that new hire professionals take too long to reach a good level of productivity. The OECD defines "Productivity" as: "*a ratio of a volume measure of output to a volume measure of input use*" (OECD 2001b). They also state that although literature does agree with this general definition, that there are more definitions and that there does not seem to be a consensus or one definition which is used the most. In this context, the productivity of the graduate has to be compared to the employees that have similar tasks and do similar work. The context, tasks and responsibilities define how productivity should be defined and can be measured. To research the concept 'productivity' further in literature would be out of scope, which is why the OECD-definition of productivity is used in this research.

Figure 2.2: Productivity, depicted by researcher, adapted from *Competence at work* - Spencer & Spencer (Spencer 1993, p. 293)

Spencer & Spencer have visualised the development of productivity in a graph, the researcher adapted this model to visualise the dynamics (Figure 2.2). The graph assumes that it takes new hired graduates 12 months to be 100% productive. This 100% is defined as the average performance of an experienced employee. The average new employee will reach 50% after 6 months. The reduction of the learning curve results in a higher productivity within a shorter period of time. The model in the graph shows that with a better learning curve, 100% productivity may already be reached after half a year. This dynamic is shown by arrow "X", thus shortening the learning period by 50%. In addition, better selection and training can result in superior performance in a job due to a better fit between competencies and job responsibilities. Superior performers may exceed the 100% productivity border, shown by arrow "Y". Here the assumption was made that the required competencies regarding the job are clear, fit the responsibilities and lead to success. Productivity is a better factor to measure alignment than, for example, un-employment. It is a misconception to state that a low rate of unemployment in a group of university-educated workforce proves that alignment between HEIs and the employers of graduates is successful (Zlatkin-Troitschanskaia 2017). It is important to realise that employers can develop the missing (level of) competencies further in the first years of their employment to improve productivity. The focus should be more on the quality of alignment, which can be measured by using productivity.

When 100% productivity is the (average) level that employers want their employees to reach when developing them, the question rises at which level (which %) the HEIs deliver their graduates to the employers. What is the gap between the HEI curriculum and the desired competencies of employers? How can this be measured and how large is this gap? Spencer & Spencer do not answer this question. Furthermore, there seems to be room above the 100%, but it is not clear how much potential there is.

Another point of criticism towards the model is that it does not take HEIs into account. It is unclear at which level the students enter the market being a graduate and it is also unclear what the interaction between the two is or can be. The focus solely lies on what the organisation can do to improve the match between the competencies of the new employees versus the job requirements, for example by improving selection methods and training.

Spencer & Spencer have also developed a definition of a competency by splitting the concept into three parts: 1) personal characteristics 2) behaviour and 3) job performance. Motives, traits, values and self-image competencies result in a certain behaviour. Behaviour, in turn, results in a certain job performance. This approach has some similarities to the Iceberg model as described earlier. According to Spencer & Spencer, it is important to realise that competencies always come with a certain intent. This is the force that leads to action which leads to an outcome. If behaviour does not have an intent it should not be labelled as a competency and should not be used in competency profiles. By stating that a behaviour is incomplete when defined without intent, the authors Lyle M. Spencer and Signe M. Spencer (1993) indicate that there is a relationship between the competencies above the surface and those that lie beneath.

With this definition, the criterion is used that:

A characteristic is not a competency unless it predicts something meaningful in the real world.

If a characteristic does not have any effect or makes no difference in practice, the added value is zero and it should not be used for assessment purposes.

Summarising this section, the conclusion can be made that HEIs should ideally link their education processes and goals to the practice of the curriculum. Both HEIs and organisations have a responsibility and they have to find a way to work together. They also have to find a common denominator apart from competencies to measure results. Competencies are a means to an end, not a goal; it should lead to something meaningful. This is probably one of the major misconceptions in HEIs. Competencies can be described together and developed together. However, the fit with roles in business organisations,

measured by for example the productivity of the graduate, is ultimately the most important factor. Organisations want to have new employees that add value. Graduates do not have to perform at 100% when they start, but there is certainly room for improvement. The level of performance during the first year of working can be improved.

2.4.5 Competencies in an international working environment

It has already been made clear that internationalisation and globalisation are two concepts that are sometimes randomly used. The focus of the research project is on internationalisation, but due to the interchangeable usage of both concepts, globalisation will be assessed in this section as well.

When looking at the increased attention to internationalisation within higher education, one might assume that HEIs are steadily improving and adapting their programmes and related competencies regarding the demand in organisations. This assumption is undermined by de Wit, who identified several misconceptions regarding internationalisation of higher education. His list of nine misconceptions contains the following points (de Wit 2011b):

1. Internationalisation is education in the English language
2. Internationalisation is studying or staying abroad
3. Internationalisation equals an international subject
4. Internationalisation implies having many international students
5. Having a few international students in the classroom makes internationalisation into a success
6. There is no need to test intercultural and international competencies specifically
7. The more partnerships, the more international
8. Higher education is international by nature
9. Internationalisation is a goal in itself

De Wit states that the means have often become the goal. If HEIs think this way, internationalisation of higher education is not likely to be very successful.

As a result, one might also argue that the end-level of the programmes, largely defined by its competencies, will not meet the required levels in the labour market if HEIs do not know how internationalisation works in the future working environments of its students. A weak understanding of internationalisation leads to a weak alignment and thus weak education programmes for future employees.

As mentioned before, changes in the global economic world are increasing their tempo. Technology and other factors drive change. As a result, business methods are being

reinvented more quickly to be able to keep up with the changing demand. According to Kedia and Mukherji, management can no longer rely on the things they have learned in business schools some time ago. Kedia (1999) states that the world is a global marketplace where management should be able to act in the same pace of change. Complexity and increasing dynamics require people that understand the drivers and can continuously adapt to the ever-changing environment. To stay competitive as a manager one must become a global manager. But what is a global manager? Which competencies does he or she have to have? Becoming a true global manager seems unrealistic. It is impossible for any human being to know all relevant information about, for example, all cultures in this world. It can also not be expected that a manager or leader speaks all languages. As such, the global manager or leader does not and cannot exist. This is confirmed by Bartlett and Ghoshal (2003) and Baruch (2002); they argue that the universal global manager does not exist, and they suggest a different approach. They describe three groups of specialists that are currently acting in a global environment. First there is the business manager, second the country manager and third the functional managers. All these managers have different responsibilities, goals and roles. They work together under the supervision of corporate management. Top management should understand the strategic position and importance of each role. The three roles are considered to be specialists, which allows the possibility to focus on certain areas of expertise. This is a more realistic approach as it seems to limit the needed knowledge and skills for each role due to specialisation.

This approach does not take the cultural aspect into account. Much research was executed regarding the topic intercultural competencies in a global leadership context. One research effort concludes that interculturality consists of three dimensions: perception management, relationship management and self-management (Bird 2010). Deardorff (2006) executed research regarding the definition and fitting assessment methods of intercultural competences. This is the first study to document consensus on intercultural competence by two groups: administrators and intercultural scholars. The result of this research was that an agreement was found regarding the possibility to assess degrees of intercultural competences. A mix of quantitative and qualitative methods to assess intercultural competence would be best. This can include performing an interview, execution an observation, and personal judgment by other people. In total, 65% of both the administrators and intercultural scholars accepted the statement that measuring intercultural competence is specific to context, situation, and relation. The importance of analysing the situational, social, and historical contexts when assessing intercultural competence was defined as very important.

It is therefore important that HEIs use a clear and realistic definition of the international roles that are defined as goals for students when they graduate. The related competencies should be in line with these roles or positions and cultural aspects have to be integrated. The next challenge is that HEIs have to update their curriculum regularly as the environment keeps on changing and globalisation will be present on a permanent basis. Fundamental forces of globalisation are demographics, sustainability and technology according to Aggarwal (2011). Business schools have to be ready to work with changes in these areas and let their staff and their students work with it. Aggarwal stated that emerging economies like India and China, as well as technology, are changing the business environment and also the nature of working together in a business environment. As such, globalisation is here to stay. Higher education has to respond to these changes and dynamics. This continuous change is something that also has an effect on the way that HEIs operate. International Business students should consider the impact of demographics, sustainability, and technology in their study and work. In addition, Aggarwal states that business school curricula have to reflect the dynamics of the outside world. The students have to be prepared for this rapidly changing international business environment. HEIs do not always seem to understand what internationalisation entails. According to Knight (2011, p. 14) the concept is often used in a broad sense and loses therefore meaning. She describes five myths:

1. Foreign Students can be seen as Agents for internationalisation; here the assumption is that foreign students stimulate international culture and curriculum.
2. International activities boost quality; there is no proof that international activities are linked to quality.
3. International agreements in relation to prestige and attractiveness; research shows that many agreements are just difficult to manage and require major investments, which are not always present.
4. International accreditation; there is no proof that foreign quality assurance agencies are better than national agencies or that it shows a level of internationalisation.
5. Global branding; there is a difference between branding from a marketing point of view and academic internationalisation. This difference is often neglected.

These Myths show that HEIs have to understand what internationalisation is and how it can add value for their stakeholders before taking any steps forward. This is supported by de Wit, who states that the growing importance of internationalisation in combination with the variety regarding the ways HEIs approach this development calls for an assessment of the quality of internationalisation, and an approach on how to measure the progress and status of internationalisation within HEIs as well as in their education programmes (de Wit 2013). Coelen (2013) underpinnes this by stating that it is not really clear what graduates should

know and be able to do when they finish their studies. According to him, the concept “internationalisation” requires more consideration and discussion.

The internationalisation handbook that is in use in Belgium has identified four clusters regarding what they call “international competencies”: intercultural, language, the relationship between student and society, and personal growth. They have added a fifth group in 2017; international professional knowledge (Flanders Knowledge Area vzw. 2017). These five clusters are based upon a holistic approach around international competencies. The use of the term international competencies contradicts earlier literature findings regarding the definition of competencies versus international competencies. These five groups are a result of a project focussing on international competencies: “Internationale Competenties” (Associatie KU Leuven 2018), in English: International Competencies. The main aim of the project that has led to these five groups answers the following question: *“Which competencies are primarily sharpened by internationalization initiatives in higher education programmes?”* This approach supports HEIs and their education programmes courses to reflect on how to work with international competencies. This framework with five clusters identifies exclusive competencies regarding internationalisation, but also recognises that some competencies may be developed in a non-international way and that internationalisation may develop competencies that are not considered to be important in an international context.

2.4.6 Key developments: from the European Union to the Netherlands

In March 2016, the Council of Europe published a document containing a conceptual model of competences (Council of Europe 2016). In this document, the concept “competences” was preferred over “competencies”, as the focus lies on being competent. The aim of the Council is that learners can use this model and live in peace with others in culturally diverse societies. The focus is to teach students how to think and not what to think. The model should stimulate life-long learning as democratic citizens in Europe. The model was designed completely from scratch; no former model was used as a basis. A systematic analysis of existing schemes regarding democratic and intercultural competence was used to develop the model. In total, 101 schemes were found and analysed. The decomposition of all individual competences in the schemes formed the basis on which sets containing comparable competences were formed. Finally, 55 competences were identified that are used in the model. Using certain criteria, three groups of value, six attitudes, eight skills and three groups of knowledge and critical understanding were formed. Finally, the model was reviewed by i.e. experts, practitioners and policy makers.

There are some similarities when comparing this model with the Iceberg model, as described in the section with the classification of competencies. As in the Iceberg model, this conceptual model of the Council of Europe not only includes knowledge and skills. Values and attitudes are also part of the model. Values can be linked to “social roles, values: beliefs or ideals” in the Iceberg model. Attitudes in this model are more difficult to link, as they relate to “self-image”, as well as “traits” and “motives”. The Iceberg model has a more detailed description of the non-visible parts that influence human behaviour.

The four aspects of the conceptual model of the Council of Europe are considered to be essential for behaviour that is to be expected in democratic and intercultural situations. Behaviour is therefore on top, representing the final result of the four aspects in the model. Competences in practical situations are never or very rarely used individually. Usually a set of competences is used in real-life situations, depending on the situation at hand and the specific needs of the individual. The council states that competent behaviour requires the application of a set of competences. The model shows that in addition to knowledge and skills, attitudes are also important values and that behaviour is key.

Another European development in the field of competencies was initiated by the European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training (Cedefop). They have published results of a pilot regarding an employer survey on skill needs in Europe (European Centre for the Development of Vocational Training 2013). The main aim of this research was to investigate possible changes regarding needed skills within organisations. The countries selected for this pilot were: Germany, Hungary, Czech Republic, Ireland, Spain, France, Italy, Poland and Finland. The aim of the study was to identify trends regarding different jobs and patterns and development in general.

The following main results were found. The skills that experience the strongest increase are:

- advance learning, literacy, adaptability and persuasion;
- ICT-skills and green skills.

Other developments that were discovered are:

- foreign languages are increasing in importance. This depends however on the occupation and the type of professionals; the ICT sector and personal care workers show the highest growth;
- an increased flexibility and adaptability regarding new equipment or new material is required. This relates mostly to office clerks in construction and the health sector;
- Green skills are in demand in construction and the health sectors; demand for green skills varies across occupational groups;

- Tasks linked to reducing resources is of increasing importance. This can be raw material, energy or water, but also the reduction of polluting activities;
- Innovation is another aspect that is more required. Especially larger organisations experience an increase in demand. Innovation activities are skill intensive.

In general, it can be said that organisations that review the required skills of their work force are better prepared for improving generic skills. Furthermore, high-level jobs such as engineering professionals and IT-engineers are facing a more dynamic environment than average. Sectors that experience the most dynamics are finance, public administration, IT and health.

The focus on the importance of learning skills was developed further in Europe with the introduction of 21st Century Skills (Voogt 2010). The development of this set of skills started in the US and developed further to Canada, the United Kingdom and other countries. A large variety of academics, business leaders and governmental organisations such as the OECD have worked on its development (Pijpers 2015). 21st Century Skills flourishes as a result of a growing international movement. The focus is on skills that are considered necessary to be able to perform well in a rapidly changing digital society. The identified key personal and academic skills are supposed to match the requirements for the current as well as the next generation of students. In the Netherlands, 21st Century Skills was developed by Kennisnet, an organisation financed by the Dutch government that focuses on supporting educational institutes in the field of IT. This was done in cooperation with SLO, which stands for “Stichting Leerplanontwikkeling” and presents itself as the national institute for curriculum development in the Netherlands. These two organisations have developed a model (SLO/ Kennisnet 2016). The model has a total of 11 competences which reflect all 21st-century skills as shown in table 2.5. The 11 skills are not independent; all competences complement each other. When solving problems, you never use one skill, but always multiple skills together; i.e. working together and problem solving.

No.	Dutch	English
1.	Informatievaardigheden	Information literacy
2.	Mediawijsheid	Media literacy
3.	Computational thinking	Computational thinking
4.	Kritisch denken	Critical thinking (C)
5.	Probleem oplossen	Problem solving
6.	ICT-basisvaardigheden	ICT basic skills
7.	Samenwerken	Working together/ Collaboration (C)
8.	Sociale en culturele vaardigheden	Social and cultural skills

9.	Communicatie	Communication (C)
10.	Zelfregulatie	Self-regulation
11.	Creatief denken	Creative thinking/ Creativity (C)

Table 2.5: 21st century Skills, depicted by researcher (SLO/ Kennisnet 2016)

Criticism towards the model mainly focuses on the risk of overkill. A constant emphasis on generic skills can put the position of professional knowledge in education programmes at risk. This does not have a positive influence on the quality of education, argue Bergsen, Kirschner and Meester (2017). They state that the availability of knowledge, e.g. via the internet, is not the same as the possession of knowledge. Directors in higher education regularly wonder why they should train students for a job that may no longer exist once they have graduated. These doubts are usually combined with being insecure about doing the right thing. The exact meaning of 21st century skills is unclear; many institutions have defined their own versions. There are no unambiguous scientific definitions and definitions of the concept. Despite this, the concept is gaining popularity in national and international education sectors. Many governmental organisations seem to agree about the supposed importance of these generic skills. The OECD has stated in 2001 that education institutes should focus on skills like problem-solving, creativity and inventiveness (OECD 2001a). The Dutch Ministry of Education has set-up the Skills Platform where education and other specialists regarding skills join forces. In this platform, comparable advanced skills are the main topic. The government promotes the use of 21st-century skills also in other ways, i.e. via funding of practical research. Though a generic definition is lacking, 21st century skills can be placed in a context defined by the following three questions:

1. Which competencies are needed in the (near) future?
2. How should young people be trained for a rapidly changing society?
3. How quickly does knowledge age, and which knowledge is still relevant?

All 21st century skills rhetoric has the same structure: the world and the job market are changing. This is mainly due to social and technology developments. As a result, the focus should be on learning generic skills, instead of focusing on quickly aging knowledge, which is easily accessible via the internet anyway. There is criticism towards this approach. In its report "Towards a learning economy", the "Wetenschappelijke Raad voor het Regeringsbeleid" (Scientific Council for Government Policy, WRR) describes developments in the world that have an influence on higher education in the Netherlands (Wetenschappelijke Raad voor het Regeringsbeleid 2013). The main point refers to a less and less predictable world with greater societal challenges. The content of education has to

be reviewed. According to the council, the long tradition of freedom of education in the Netherlands has a downside; a social debate about topics that have to be transferred by education is severely lacking. The Netherlands lacks a “*national curriculum*”. The WRR also states that the discussion on how much attention 21st Century Skills should have in education is mainly held by individuals, not by involved stakeholder groups. Furthermore, the WRR has the opinion that the (too) far-reaching differentiation between education aimed at skills and education aimed at education needs a review. Too much attention on skills is not the correct way, neither is a one-sided cognitive approach towards education. Adaptability is crucial for being a professional in the future, according to the WRR.

The “ministerie van OCW” (Ministry of Education, Culture and Science, OCW) in the Netherlands has used the WRR recommendations and formulated the following strategic vision (Ministerie van Onderwijs 2015): “*Higher education must train for life and work in an increasingly unpredictable, complex and globalised world.*”

Following the direction set by the Ministry the “Vereniging van Hogescholen”, the Association of Universities of Applied Sciences wrote a strategic document in the same year which concerns the period 2015-2025 (Vereniging Hogescholen 2015). They have formulated the following aim for the Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands:

Universities of Applied Sciences have to train students to become agile and resilient professionals. Quality remains the guideline in higher professional education that trains high-quality professionals who have the latest knowledge and research ability.

It is unclear however how quality is defined; if it is a guideline, quality itself and what it entails should also be defined.

In line with the WRR, the main message is that future employees have to be prepared to function in a changing world. They have to work in an ever-changing environment, where they play an active role and steer the necessary changes. The association confirms that they believe that the cliché is true: the world will never be the same again. This is why adaptive power is becoming increasingly important.

Nienke Meijer, Chairman of the Executive Board of Fontys Hogescholen, one of the larger Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands, has written a strategic paper that discusses the directions above and ends with a “call for action” (Meijer 2017). She states that knowledge institutes play an important role in achieving the ambitions of the Netherlands in the upcoming years. Not only do they have the necessary knowledge regarding topics as digitalisation and technology, they also connect this knowledge to the business community and social institutions. More importantly, knowledge institutions have the responsibility to train and develop people who can make a difference later on. If the Universities of Applied Sciences manages to train a new type of employee in the coming years, the Netherlands will

be an innovative top country in 2050. The most important topics are innovative technology, entrepreneurship, creativity, agility and resilience.

Her “Call for action” involves a number of options for education programmes. No new and specific actions are required that involve organisations in the region of Fontys University of Applied Sciences. The future working environment of their graduates has not been acknowledged as the customer.

The conclusion can be drawn that governmental organisations in the EU and in the Netherlands, have recognised that the world is changing fast and that actions is needed in higher education. As a result, several models were developed. However, clear definitions regarding i.e. the definition of (international) competencies and quality are lacking. These definitions could provide a better guideline for HEIs and their curricula. In addition, a discussion is taking place in the Netherlands regarding the importance of skills versus knowledge. This discussion unfortunately does not include all levels in the Iceberg model, neither does in involve all stakeholders.

2.4.7 Alignment between higher education and organisations

In 2008, the European Parliament and the Council approved the Recommendation to adopt the European Qualifications Network (EQF). As described in Section 2.2.8, the main purpose of the EQF is to stimulate mobility in the EHEA-region. The EQF invites member states to link their national qualifications systems. Each country is invited to reference their national qualifications levels to the relevant EQF levels, and to develop a national qualification framework in line with national legislation and practice. The Netherlands defined their Dutch National Qualifications Framework (NLQF) in 2012 and Germany developed their German Qualifications Framework for Lifelong Learning (DQR) in 2013 (Bundesministerium für Bildung und Forschung 2012). However, it does not provide possibilities to measure quality, neither does it provide possibilities to align with the demand of organisations regarding competencies needed in an international environment.

Talent acquisition and access is important for organisations as indicated by a study from Deloitte regarding Global Human Capital Trends (2014). In this study respondents have put “Talent acquisition and access” on number four in the list with global trends, and 20-24% indicated that this topic is “urgent”. HEIs play an important by developing new employees to be ready for their future working environment. Aligning developed and required competencies is therefore important, and can be organised by developing Frameworks. They are used to organise competences for a specific purpose, for example to align higher education with the job market. This maybe done via a curriculum or by describing the

responsibilities in a job. Frameworks usually have a limited thematic focus. For example, the European Commission suggested in 2018 an update regarding “Key Competences for LifeLong Learning”, which are competences that each European citizen needs in their daily life (European Commission 2018c) as described in section 2.2.1. Member states are invited to work with these competences in education programmes. Within the EHEA-region, there are multiple international competence frameworks in use. The European Commission (2018c) has made an overview with the seven most known frameworks:

- ❖ *The OECD Global Competency*
- ❖ *The P21 framework*
- ❖ *The World Economic Forum framework*
- ❖ *The Council of Europe Competences for Democratic Culture*
- ❖ *The UNESCO Intercultural Competences Framework*
- ❖ *The UNESCO Global Framework of Learning Domains*

The frameworks above are organised around a certain topic; for example, the P21 framework is the same as the 21st century skills described in the previous section. A comparison made by a project group of the European Commission shows the similarities and differences between the different frameworks. All use the same definition of a competence: a set of knowledge, skills and attitudes. All refer to the ability to change and to handle complexity and digitalisation and technology. They also emphasise the importance of the further development of competences in line with the changes regarding demand. All frameworks put the emphasis on non-cognitive skills, attitudes or values. Neither of the above listed frameworks aims for a comprehensive basis for curriculum development or to align competencies with the job-market. All have a rather limited competence range. It can be concluded that there are different views regarding structuring the competence frameworks in Europe (European Commission 2018c) and that alignment with practice does not appear to have been sought.

The sub-conclusion is that the current bachelor-master structure in Europe and the used competence frameworks do not seem to address the alignment question. This assumption is supported by initiatives of sometimes private stakeholders who have worked on frameworks that cover this area and help to improve alignment. These initiatives aim to assure future needs in the job market by defining the required competences and thus give HEIs the possibility to use these in their curriculum. Two examples are of interest as these were developed based upon a large network of organisations.

The first example was developed by the European Logistics Association (ELA). This is a federation of 30 national organisations in Europe (European Logistics Association 2016). The network covers most countries in Central and Western Europe. One of the goals of the ELA is to recognise competences, validate logisticians' experience at different levels, and to certify them in a recognisable way across borders in Europe. The ELA Standards are mapped to the European Qualification Framework (EQF), an EU initiative for harmonising life-long learning, as described in section 2.2.8. The EQF is used as a translation method which makes logistics qualifications transferable. ELA has built a competence system that fits the ELA Certification. This approach reflects market needs by looking at workplace performance. These standards are developed with and agreed upon by organisations in this sector. For this reason, the European Certification Board for Logistics (ECBL) was established. The country members in this Board have agreed to share the Standards of Competence for Logistics. They manage and control the ELA Standards and update the ELA Standards when necessary. The Dutch member is VLM (Vereniging Logistiek Management) and represents over 1,700 Dutch business members in the logistics area.

Another example of an initiative in the market to meet future needs and that has received the full support of the European Commission and The Council of Ministers is the e-Competence Framework (EUROPEAN e-Competence Framework 2016) for Information & Communication Technology (ICT) job profiles. The initiative started in 2005; in 2016, it became the standard in Europe and was re-launched. Meanwhile it is supported by the European Commission and large ICT demand companies such as Airbus and Michelin. In addition, large social partners such as the German IG Metall and BITKOM are also involved. This framework provides a platform to meet the needs of businesses and other public and private organisations. The purpose of the e-Competence Framework (e-CF) is to serve as a European "umbrella structure". All regional and national frameworks should be able to link to it. This framework should provide a translation between different ICT frameworks. The e-CF should make the communication between different parties easier. The tool aims to support discussions between HEIs and employers, for example. Universities and Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands are starting to use this tool for their bachelor and master programmes. One example is Hogeschool Utrecht (University of Applied Sciences Utrecht) who uses e-CF as a foundation for their professional education. In this way, their Master of Informatics (Msc) was brought closer to the demand of future employers. In this profile, there are six families as well as the 23 European ICT profiles. In total, 40 competences were identified that were structured around the areas: Plan, Build, Run, Enable and Manage.

The two examples show the possibilities of aligning competencies between HEIs and business organisations in the European context. However, the field of expertise and the needed competencies are specific, and therefore have a clear scope, such as ICT. In addition, the possible roles and job descriptions within Logistics and ICT are limited when compared to the curriculum of business administration. This approach nevertheless proves that in this example, organisations working in the ICT-market are making efforts to bridge the gap between HEIs and business organisations. The competencies described in ICT job profiles can be used by HEIs for curriculum development.

Within the European Union, actions are being taken to identify future needs. One example is a Peer Learning Activity (PLA) which was held in Brussels in February 2016 (European Commission 2016a). PLA's are sessions that are organised with the aim of sharing experience and helping to work on topics within Europe. The topics of the PLAs are linked to the Working Group on the Modernisation of Higher Education (WG-MHE). In PLAs, representatives from ministries and HEIs representatives join forces to improve cooperation within Europe. The topic of this PLA was "developing future skills in higher education". The following are findings from this meeting:

1. Learning outcomes should include soft skills or 21st century skills or transferable skills. Within the Bologna process, attention was given to define concrete learning outcomes. Defining outcomes in the field of transferable skills in higher education programmes is part of this process.
2. The conclusion was made that there is an increased focus on the question to what extent HEIs prepare their students for jobs after graduation. Multiple research projects have proven that employers find transferable or soft or 21st century skills very important. In addition, graduates should have the knowledge and skills that prepare them for jobs in an increasingly dynamic economy and changing working environment.
3. HEIs need to do more than to make sure that graduates are employable. Socialisation and the development of a wide range of knowledge, skills, attitudes, attributes and other personal aspects are also part of the responsibility of the environment that has to be facilitated. Social, interpersonal and cultural skills are considered to be important whilst pursuing a professional career. Despite this, the conclusion can be made that learning outcomes in higher education programmes do not often contain social and civic competences.
4. There is a gap between rhetoric, plans and goals and the practice in the European classrooms. The conclusion can be made that the results are variable at best. Student centred learning is considered to be very important for skill development, but

this approach is not implemented on a large scale within European HEIs (European Students Union 2015).

5. The PLA wants to investigate how the development of skills and social and civic competences is promoted. The focus has to be on practice, as the effects have to be measurable and progress has to be realised in this field. Together with several organisations, representatives from eleven countries participated and answered questions regarding the following topics:
 1. The definition of skills and competences and how they should be understood;
 2. How the development of these skills and competences can be implemented in existing strategies, systems, etc.;
 3. How HEIs can promote the development of these skills and competences;
 4. How working together on a European level may add value.

The researcher concludes that there are different definitions and meanings when involved parties talk about “future skills”. As a result, it is not always clear what is meant when different stakeholders use the term “future skills”, despite the fact that there is, for example, a “European Framework for key competences for lifelong learning” (European Commission 2018c). It is encouraging to see their recommendation, that more focus should be given to all personal aspects, and not “just” knowledge and skills. Furthermore, there is an acknowledgment that the responsibility of HEIs is more complex than simply making graduates employable. Finally, it seems that the number of activities can be increased, which might lead to an increase in outcomes.

The PLA defined what they call “non-definitive” groups to classify skills (European Commission 2016a). These are the main groups of skills important for HEI students. The groups of skills were defined around the following three topics:

1. Cognition;
2. Methodology;
3. Social.

The skills related to these 3 groups were deemed important for civic and social competences and future working environments. In addition to this, the conclusion was made that this skill set relies more than average on personal attitudes, values, norms and ethical aspects of the individual student. Attitudes and values are invisible aspects of student behaviour and it was concluded that these are difficult to change in a HE-environment. More explanation or discussion regarding this topic was unfortunately not present.

Two other points of interest came from this PLA session. The first is the aim to work towards a clearer and shared definition of the skills that have to be promoted. To support HEIs, social and civil skills have to be defined on a European level. This will then support the definition of

this skills set in learning outcomes, which have to be comparable internationally, thus supporting academic recognition across borders. The second interesting point is the aim to build bridges between different stakeholders in higher education. This includes the focus on the cooperation and creation of links between HEIs and organisations where graduates go to work.

Ensuring that higher education graduates find a job is considered to be a high priority topic in higher education in Europe (European Commission 2014b). However, how the labour market demand or supply is managed differs per country. The most common way is by looking at the quality of delivery and targeting students as a whole, and not really zooming in on business requirements. The latter sometimes leads to frustration with employers when HEI-programmes do not meet their needs (Lowden 2011). By recognising that more cooperation is needed between relevant stakeholders, the conclusion can be drawn that there is a gap between the required competencies in business and the developed competencies by HEIs. Research shows that this gap may even be increasing. Milhauser investigated this topic by looking at curricula for IB programmes (Milhauser 2010). He concludes that the needs of industry regarding knowledge, skills and abilities do not match the competencies of graduates. This means that alignment is not executed in a good way. A predecessor of Milhauser executed a research study in 2005. The participants in this study, who were active in a global business environment, indicated that they expect that higher education would struggle to keep pace with industrial organisations. One of the reasons for this statement was that HEIs mainly have a content focus (Knowles 2011).

The PLA members have recognised that major changes in all aspects of society will occur on a continuous basis. The economic, political and cultural environment of employees is changing and change is here to stay. Globalisation is accelerating, and its consequences are not yet completely understood. How this may affect future working environments is not clear. It is expected that by 2023, due to continuous shifting of political and economic powers worldwide, change may be more common than continuity. The PLA discussion resulted in the conclusion that when organisations want to remain competitive in an ever-increasing trend of globalisation, the focus should be on leadership. Global and international teams have to have the skills and competencies that support the roles and tasks needed to get things done. Higher education has a critical role. HEIs have to make sure that students have the skills that are necessary to be productive in this changing global and international setting. The best way to do this according to the PLA members is to partner with industry. Working together with organisations in the field towards a sustainable focus on required knowledge, skills and abilities may be the only way for HEIs to remain relevant. The statement was made that this could be the only way to regain value. The most important customers of HEIs are not their

students but is the global marketplace. The conclusion was made that no such partnerships were found, which does not mean that they do not exist. The two examples given earlier are the initiatives of organisations, not of HEIs. Further research is needed.

Failing to be in line with the requirements of international business and to follow the changes will result in problems for both the HEI and for organisations. If the faculties are not aware of the required knowledge, skills and other required aspects regarding global and international business and/ or do not adjust their curricula, organisations have to take action and close the gap after hiring. The European Commission issued a warning in this direction in their document: "The future of Work". They state that "Work" cannot be regarded as static anymore, it should be seen as portfolio of roles that have to be managed in different manners and different settings (European Commission 2016b). They advise to develop tailor-made, customised interventions that do not only manage the required competencies, but also how they are used in practice. The graduates have to be trained and have to gain experience to be effective in international business. The differences between national and international business are diminishing. HEIs run the risk of becoming obsolete if they do not reflect international business requirements regarding competencies. Managers working in this environment have to be able to function effectively across cultures. Therefore, internationalisation of business education remains a major requirement of HEIs (Kedia, BL, Harveston, P.D., and Bhagat, R.S. 2001). In addition to the importance of meeting the demands of organisations active in international business, timing is also important. No graduate wants to enter the job market with the wrong set of competencies. Kedia concluded in 2011 that the pace of internationalisation of business is outperforming the pace of globalisation of curricula, students and faculties. There is a disconnection between international reality and the ability and speed of HEIs to deliver global managers. In addition, the definition of what a global manager is remains unclear according to Kedia (2011b). He states that higher education institutes are only gradually increasing their awareness regarding globalisation and the impact on curricula and students. Azevedo supports these findings by stating that it remains unclear how well HEIs prepare their students for the constantly evolving work place. The degree of mismatch between skills acquired and skills needed is a major cause of the perceived lack of employability (Azevedo 2012).

In a curriculum that aligns teaching with employability, it is important to consider the information provided to students and their parents, because ratings and rankings can be of key importance to them (QS Quacquarelli Symonds 2017). Commercial ratings seem to prevail over reliable and accurate data regarding programme outcomes. Rubin (2009) has executed research in this field by looking at business administration curricula on the Master level. Masters of Business Administration (MBA) programmes are receiving more and more

criticism by their stakeholders. The criticism goes in the direction that the MBA is not in line with the “real world” and is even irrelevant to managers. Based upon this criticism, Rubin has initiated research to investigate the relevancy of MBAs and their competencies in relation to the requirements in organisations. In total, 8.633 managers, 52 occupations and 1 empirical competency model were used for this purpose. The results show that the most critical competencies are least represented in the MBA curricula. In addition, media rankings and other factors regarding the institute have no effect on alignment of the programmes (Rubin 2009). University rankings are however used to attract new students, who are then developing the “wrong” competencies. The expectation is that university rankings are here to stay; the number of rankings will rise, but they will probably will become more specific (European University Association 2011).

Research executed in Denmark (Martensen 2009) shows that HEIs are facing a growing international education market. This can be a major opportunity to attract other groups of students and increase worldwide presence and turnover. The corresponding challenge, according to Martensen, is that the national institutions have the aim of making their institute and programmes unique in such a way that students and researchers are willing to travel to their location. To investigate this topic, Danish employers were asked in a survey to assess the competencies of MSc graduates of Copenhagen Business School. Furthermore, they were also asked to indicate the importance of each competency. Results indicated that industry values social and personal competencies, such as cooperation, motivation and adaptability. In addition, delivering results, communication and general business knowledge are also considered to be very important. Delivering these competencies may result in delivering quality, as these are the requirements of the market. Job requirements and graduate competencies were analysed by Teichler and Schomburg (2013). Teichler states that measuring competencies is considered to be the best method to verify the quality of HEIs. However, there are some potential negative points. Higher education institutes have to execute research to identify job requirements in addition to the competencies of their students. This means that students, academics and employers have to be asked for their opinion. Teichler addresses areas regarding realising improvement such as the development of new concepts that help realise improvements in the match-finding process. Next to this, methods have to be developed that overcome misconceptions between needed competencies by organisations and those within HEIs. As a result, it can be concluded that methods have to be developed that are accepted by all stakeholders.

Waleson is director of “Fontys Hogeschool HRM en Psychologie” (Fontys University of Applied Sciences HRM and Psychology) and states that not one organisation was satisfied

regarding the end-level competencies of graduates within the last 25 years. His advice is to convince politicians and organisations that the “higher education column” should not and does not only exist of HEIs. The organisations where the graduates go to work are also responsible, not only for the benefit of society, but also for their own benefit (Waleson 2017). Based upon this statement, organisations should provide HEIs and students with actual and current knowledge. This has resulted in an interesting internal discussion within Fontys Hogeschool. Van de Camp is a teacher of Finance and Marketing at Fontys and does not agree with Waleson. He states that HEIs should focus more on knowledge (van de Camp 2017). Knowledge was disregarded too long. He is afraid that too much focus on 21st Century Skills, for example, is a risk for the HEI role as a knowledge institute. If knowledge is no longer a spearhead, how will students then be prepared for their working career? Even if knowledge in a HEI is not up to date, students will still learn a lot as new knowledge is usually built upon existing knowledge. He states that the working field is asking for more and more knowledge. According to Camp, teachers have become more coaches instead of important bearers and bringers of knowledge. This can be changed by working together more with local organisations and networks. This will take time, but is crucial for alignment and the reduction of the gap between what was learned and what is needed in practice.

In addition to HEIs, business organisations have a responsibility regarding the improvement of alignment. Continuous economic and technological development affects working conditions and the environment of employees and results in changing competencies. Rudman (2016) suggests that the definitions of competencies used by employers in different business sectors are not aligned. The study focused on new hires, hiring processes and discrepancies between employer definitions of competencies. Employers focus very much on task-based aspects of roles in an organisation and behavioural aspects, or more specifically: getting things done. Important aspects were e.g. drive, versatility, adaptability and cultural fit; all factors of the levels underneath the water of the Iceberg model. Meeting the competencies in the eyes of employers means that the new employee has to fit into the culture of the organisation, can work in a team, is productive from the first day of working, and is flexible and motivated. At the start of their career, it is not clear how productive new employees in general can be in the short- and longer-term, which means that it is also not clear which level of productivity is and can be achieved by graduates. Additional questions in the study revealed that although certain candidates in the hiring process met the job criteria, other aspects were missing. The candidates were either not able to demonstrate the knowledge and skills as described in their resumes or they lacked interpersonal skills. Furthermore, the fit with the organisation’s culture is an important factor in the decision-making process. Even if the candidate had the skills, the question remains if they were a

good fit for the organisation or had the drive to excel in a certain job. Hires that are considered to be unsuccessful were related to a hiring process that aimed to fill a vacant position and not to find the right candidate who meets all criteria. The criteria used in hiring a new employee should be based upon their drive to succeed and to help the organisation to succeed.

In 2003, The Hay Group published in a review document with an analysis regarding the interaction between the Iceberg model and the hiring process. They advised that new employees be recruited based upon the levels below water of the Iceberg model (Hay Group 2003). The levels above the surface are easier to train and develop. The levels below water are more difficult and take more time to develop. Planning careers, job changes and coaching can realise the development of the required characteristics that are needed in more senior roles in the organisation. This raises the question what the roles of HEIs are when organisations train and develop graduates and, therefore, partly take on tasks that are usually the role of HEIs. This study also concluded that the best performance is supported by the levels below water of the iceberg. More complex roles in organisations require employees that have qualities in these levels below water. Hiring processes that only focus on knowledge and skills will not be able to hire the best performers. In addition, only focusing on behaviour can be a pitfall. Behaviour has to be linked with intent; only intentional behaviour delivers the required performance. Organisations need to organise themselves well and have a clear focus on the job and the necessary competencies at all level of the iceberg. The Hay Group drew the conclusion that is important not to limit the hiring process to knowledge and skills. Deeply rooted competencies determine high potentials. Social role, self-image, traits and motives have to be combined with the required knowledge and skills of the relevant position. There has to be a fit or a clear path that develops the required competencies further in the organisation. This way mismatches, low morale and recruiting costs are avoided. More importantly, the chance that high performers will join the organisation may increase.

The assumption is made that delivering the desired competencies will result in actual results in the workplace. However, Packard (2014) stated that there is just little evidence that links the used competencies in HEIs to actual results in the workplace. According to him there is little proof of actions that bring this added value. He raised the question: how do the competencies of students and later employees impact the performance of the organisation? This is a limitation in knowledge and provides an area where further research is needed (Packard 2014). This does not mean that competency has to be abandoned as the common denominator when HEIs and organisations are working together to improve graduate

contributions in the workplace. It does imply, however that the concept of alignment is multi-dimensional. There are more aspects that influence quality; there are more aspects that influence the productivity of alumni when they start working.

Constructive alignment is a systems approach developed by Biggs (2013) in which all elements of the curriculum should align. The learning outcomes of students are defined before teaching and assessment methods and teaching are combined in such a way that the intended results at the intended level can be achieved. The starting point of the Biggs model are the learning outcomes of a module, which can be linked to a taxonomy, such as that of Bloom. The next step would be that the HEI develops the teaching strategy and can determine the type of test, the content of the test, the assessment criteria and how to standardise the test. A critical point towards the model is that although Biggs acknowledges the importance of external drivers, the focus is on the process of alignment regarding teaching within the HEI organisation and does not really take into account the alignment with the relevant external stakeholders; it does not include answering the question what has to be learned and why. Alignment can only be realised by involving all stakeholders with the right focus and an active attitude and by constant monitoring the relevant environment. This regular monitoring by HEIs of the changes in the business environment of the organisations where the alumni try to obtain jobs, should be followed by changes in the curriculum and the way students are prepared for their future work. This implies that an organisation-wide approach is crucial, academics and other professionals should be involved and recognise the importance of institutional support and champions for programmatic innovation.

As discussed in section 2.4.2 the teacher has an important role in competency development. He or she has to work with changes in the requirements regarding knowledge, skills and attitudes, has to integrate these changes as innovation in education programmes and is relying on other HEI-professionals for support. The success of alignment is therefore depending on the adaptability of teachers and all other involved HEI-employees. Once the required changes regarding competencies and programmatic innovation are clear and evaluated against the curriculum, also the changes in teaching and the role and responsibilities of the teacher and other relevant HEI-professionals should be identified. This does not mean that academic freedom should change; the aim is to make sure that competencies are developed that are required by business organisations by matching the pace of changes in business. Theoretically, it is just a matter of learning how to do this. However, although this sounds plausible, the reality might be different. Academics and other HEI-professionals might not believe in proposed changes and/ or might not be willing to cooperate. Fullan (1998) confirms this risk by stating that change is difficult to manage. Any co-worker or employee has a natural resistance to change, some more than others. Any

organisation with human beings wants to remain in balance and continue to do things as they have done before. When confronted with change people tend to fight this threat, flee their environment or try not to be influenced.

When the teacher is accepting the required change the next challenge is how to deal with the changes regarding knowledge, skills and attitudes. Innovation in knowledge is relatively easier to integrate than innovations in skills and attitudes. The last two might require that the teacher has to work more intensively on his or her own competencies. Hamachek (1999, p. 209) points at a probably well-known risk in this area. A teacher has to work on his or her competencies. However, working hard on your competencies as a teacher does not guarantee success. The personal qualities define the way you are teaching: *“Consciously, we teach what we know; unconsciously, we teach who we are”*. This relates to the iceberg structure as discussed in section 2.4.2. The levels below water are not in the picture. Tickle (1999) drew the conclusion that due to an analytical perspective on people in education the deeper levels of the iceberg are neglected. Instead of judging HEI-teachers, the focus should be on supporting them to manage the changes and to support professional development, including the personal challenges they encounter as a result of the changes due to alignment. This is what teachers and all other involved HEI-employees, as a discipline, already do. However, the pace has to be increased, which means that the pressure on these stakeholders will increase to. This goes beyond the classical competency-oriented development methodology and goes more into the direction of a process with a holistic approach.

When looking at alignment the conclusion can be drawn that it is complex. There are multiple aspects to consider and a detailed analysis is necessary before any alignment activities are initiated. Alignment relates to quality, it has the aim to deliver alumni with the required combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes. The graduate should at a minimum be able to find a job, and at best find the job that is in line with all developed competencies and be one of the leaders and innovators of the future. When done right, all the layers of the Iceberg model should be used for alignment purposes; how to do this requires more research.

The conclusion can be drawn that alignment should be regarded as a process, which fits the opinion of Yemini (2014). This process will be continuously improved by using a fitting set of performance criteria combined with the right success factors. For this reason, the next sections will look at possible models that can be of value for the alignment process.

2.4.8 Identification of gaps

This study focuses on the possible gap between demand and offer in the field of international higher education. The researcher addresses this topic from a quality perspective. Delivering competencies that are required by business organisations may result in delivering quality, as discussed in section 2.4.7. For this reason, the final analysis will be done using a model that makes the identification of gaps in service delivery possible. There are two major models that compete for being the best: SERVPERF Versus SERVQUAL. These two will be described and compared, and a decision will then be made to use one of both for analysis purposes. The reason why these models were chosen for this study is that it analyses different sorts of gaps, supports the development of an alignment model and helps to improve alignment.

The Service Quality Model (SERVQUAL) was developed by Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Berry (1985). The aim of the model is to measure the service quality that is perceived by customers. Communication is an important vehicle for delivering quality. Organisations, including HEIs, have to know the expectations of their customers. Only by knowing the demand of customers can expectations be matched. The SERVQUAL model can identify gaps regarding the difference between the needs of the customer and the offered services.

Figure 2.3: SERVQUAL - Gaps model of service quality, depicted by researcher, adapted from Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Berry (1985)

The focal point of the model is the expected quality of the offered service. This gap deals with the difference between what customers expect and what they perceive and actually experience. The main aim of the SERVQUAL model is to identify factors that play a major role when looking at the expectations. Knowing these factors provides organisations the

opportunity to improve their services and proactively work with the expectations of their customers.

The researcher adapted the SERVQUAL model by adding HEIs and organisations, thus specifying the context of the gaps that can be identified.

The SERVQUAL model identifies five sorts of gaps:

1. Knowledge Gap
2. Policy Gap
3. Delivery Gap
4. Communication Gap
5. Customer Gap

To understand each gap and how they are combined, the researcher describes each gap in the following section.

1) The Knowledge Gap indicates how much knowledge there is regarding the expectations of the customers. Any organisation runs risks when they do not have enough knowledge about the expectations of their customers. A large knowledge gap indicates that managers are either not aware of the expectations or they have interpreted the expectations in a wrong way when they define and/ or develop the services of the organisation. This may result in aiming to address customer needs that are wrong or do not exist. Comprehensive market research is needed to close this gap.

2) Having wrong or insufficient rules and policies compared to the desired service delivery may lead to problems. When customer expectations are translated incorrectly to employee rules and guidelines, the desired service may not be delivered. This incorrect translation may be due to translation problems or not enough standardisation, for example. Customers may choose to go to another organisation based upon the delivered performance.

3) The Service Performance Gap means that the organisation is not delivering according to its service designs and standards. This gap focuses on the performance of the employees in the organisation. This gap exists when the employees do not receive well formulated instructions, are not well trained, and/ or do not have good processes and guidelines for support. This results in bad equipped personnel; the employees do not have the means to perform in line with the expectations of the customers.

4) The outward-bound communication of organisations may contain promises that can interest customers or even increase the expectations of customers. When these messages

are not matched by the real service, a communication gap may develop. This gap can cause disappointment with customers, and push them away from the organisation.

5) The fourth gap is the most important gap: the difference between expectations and actual delivery of services. The experienced difference is measured based upon the perceptions of customers. This external analysis focuses on customer needs in relation to the quality of the experienced service. The focus is always on customer needs and not the perception of the organisation towards customer demand. The most important gap that can be identified using the SERVQUAL model is between the expectations of customers versus the actual experienced services by customers. This is the main gap in the model: the "Customer Gap".

The SERVQUAL model was originally based upon studies within a telecommunication company, a bank and a maintenance organisation. The customers of these organisations were asked for their perceptions of the experiences quality of service. These surveys resulted in approximately 100 aspects. Finally, the researchers decided to keep 25. The responding customers have found that these items were important when looking at customer service. These 25 were then condensed into 10 dimensions by the authors (1985):

1. Reliability
2. Responsiveness
3. Competence
4. Access
5. Courtesy
6. Communication
7. Credibility
8. Security
9. Knowing the customer
10. Tangibles

The original SERVQUAL model is more than 30 years old and was frequently criticised. SERVQUAL is complex, subjective and sometimes not reliable. However, the five dimensions can be used for qualitative research purposes. Buttle (1996) has assessed the model and has three main points of criticism. The perception and experience are very subjective and therefore not really measurable. He also states that there is not really a connection between service and the experience of quality. Finally, the aspects that are measured do not have to relate to service quality in particular, but to customer satisfaction in general. An important factor is the definition of quality. Quality related to SERVQUAL is defined as the performance for its stakeholders. Most of the time, customers are the most

important stakeholder. However, suppliers, employees, and other groups are also stakeholders. To be able to deliver quality, the stakeholders first must be identified, and second, their needs must be understood in order to be able to meet or even exceed these needs.

When looking at the results of literature research, HEIs consider their students to be the most important stakeholder. Therefore, assuming that organisations know more about the required competencies than students, real alignment is not possible because organisations are not structurally asked for their opinion. Students are not likely to have that knowledge, they already have difficulties choosing the higher education programme that fits their wishes. The number of students that stop with their study or switch to another study in the first year is around 20% (Vereniging Hogescholen 2016). A study in 2018 indicates that one of the main reasons is that many students do not orientate themselves in a good way before choosing a study programme (Meens 2018).

Looking at the SERVQUAL model, this means that Gap 1 (Knowledge Gap) and 5 (Customer Gap) are not measurable at the moment by HEIs. Alignment therefore cannot be improved this way. First the customer has to be acknowledged and their satisfaction has to be measured. Furthermore, HEIs define quality based upon NVAO assessments and the satisfaction of their own students. The statement can be therefore made that Gap 2 (Policy Gap) and 3 (Delivery Gap) are based upon this definition and therefore do not use input from organisations in the field. The Communication Gap (Gap 4) is out of scope as it focuses on communication, which is not the main topic of this research. In addition, the customer needs to be identified and communication methods have to be developed. Gaps 1 and 5 are crucial for this research project and are in scope. The main purpose of the model is to identify possible gaps and to increase the quality of delivered services by reducing these gaps, which may improve alignment.

As described earlier, there has also been criticism in science regarding the SERVQUAL model. The main criticisms are that the model is complex, subjective and statistically unreliable. In response, Cronin and Taylor (1993) developed the SERVPERF model. This model uses only one dimension, namely service quality. In addition, only the total performance is measured and the approach in SERVQUAL to use “perception minus expected approach” was abandoned. The latter was motivated by Cronin and Taylor by stating that the evaluation process of people does not show any clear differences regarding expectations that exist before experiencing the service and after. As with the SERVQUAL model, a questionnaire can be used as a research instrument. When executed, it will provide

insight regarding the service quality. The outcomes can give direction to further improvements regarding the provided services and their service quality.

When comparing both models, the conclusion can be drawn that SERVQUAL is the preferred model. It is used often in research regarding service quality. All dimensions of service quality in the SERVQUAL model tend to be contingent with offered services in various industries according to Ladhari. He executed research and investigated the gap of service quality in each dimension (Ladhari 2009). The model is not only regularly used as a subject for academic papers, but the model is also used in practice. According to Asubonteng, the SERVQUAL model is often applied in industry (Asubonteng 1996).

The SERVQUAL instrument is used in various contexts and many different cultural settings. After many years and despite academic criticism, the model still is leading the way to measure service quality. For this reason, this model will be used to analyse data obtained from research executed in this project. It will provide a structure for analysing the obtained data from filed research and will thus help understanding the gaps between higher education and practice.

2.5 Conclusions literature analysis

As stated in chapter one, working in international environments has become more common, and continues to show an upward trend. Looking at Higher Education, the conclusion was made that though internationalisation is recognised by HEIs as an important trend, taking real steps to be able to prepare students for their future working environments is slowing down the internationalisation of business environments. The executed literature research will help define the gaps in literature and will provide the theoretical framework that will be used in the next phases of this research. The researcher has researched the concepts until 2018. From this literature research, the following main conclusions are drawn.

The BBA-programme that is the subject for this study is based upon Dublin descriptors that form the basis for all Bachelors in the EHEA-region; competencies are used in this region to measure study progress. The competencies in the BBA are described in a broad way and cover many job profiles. These profiles all aim at positions in middle management. The role of middle management in an organisation is associated with both the operational and strategic levels of the organisation.

Literature research shows that a competence can be described as “being competent to do a certain job”, while competency refers more to the behaviour lying behind a competent performing individual. There is confusion in literature on what competencies are when

looking beyond the first “simple” definition of the concept, which is a set of knowledge, skills and attitudes. In general, two directions can be identified. The first one refers to the output and results and goals of e.g. training; the other direction refers to the input, or requirements i.e. being competent to do a certain job.

Literature does not provide one definition of “international competencies”. Different authors use multiple combinations of the words “internationalisation”, “competencies”, “competences” and “globalisation”, and do not always clearly explaining their meaning. Literature provides suggestions for competencies necessary in an international environment. These are often also called “global competencies”, thus adding to the confusion regarding the differences between “international” and “global”.

Competencies can be divided in different groups. The focus of this research will be on professional competencies that are job-related, as the focal point of HEIs is to deliver graduates that are productive in a working environment. There are multiple methods to classify competencies. The Iceberg model is the model which fits the best in this research as it not only identifies visible and non-visible aspects of competencies, but it also addresses the underlying differences and relationship between all elements. The only way to change behaviour is to work on all levels of the iceberg. The Iceberg model works well in combination with the Onion model of Korthagen, as the latter adds value by applying a holistic view on the development of the relevant person. The Onion model takes the what Korthagen (2004) calls “implicit potential” which is embedded in the inner layers of the model and the person. According to these models Higher Education should therefore take place based upon the connection between the components: practice, theory and the person, the student. This way alignment can be sought and optimised.

Alignment should be a process that is improved upon on a continuous basis. This approach would be in line with internationalisation, which is also considered to be a process. This alignment process should follow trends in the future working environment of the student. Here major changes take place, e.g. technology increases business and work changes that are the fundamental driving forces for globalisation. This way business schools could focus on the attitudes, skills, and knowledge that will be helpful for student career flexibility including leadership skills, a good work ethic, and abilities to continue learning. Internationalisation means that more business organisations develop their business in other countries and have to deal with multiple cultures. Deardorff (2006) suggests that measuring intercultural competence is specific to context, situation, and relation. The importance of analysing the situational, social, and historical contexts when assessing intercultural competence was defined as very important. HEIs should select and develop the

competencies that are in demand within business environments. Management can no longer rely on the things they have learned in business schools some time ago. The world is a global marketplace where management should be able to act in the same pace of change, and literature research shows that HEIs do not seem to be able to keep the same pace.

The EHEA region is trying to keep up with these changes through new initiatives. Several new models were developed to match the developments in international business, such as the European Qualifications Network (EQF) and 21st Century. However, so far “private” initiatives such as the e-CF and the ELA have proven to be more practice-oriented and more successful when it comes to alignment. In general, the conclusion can be made that besides skills, knowledge and attitudes, there is somewhat more attention within the EHEA for the lower parts of the iceberg such as “values”. It unfortunately does not seem to be enough. The EHEA models do not, for example, cover all aspects of the iceberg.

The challenge for HEIs to keep up with changes in business environments is not much different in the Netherlands. The long tradition of freedom of education in the Netherlands has a downside; a social debate about topics that have to be transferred by education is not really present. The Netherlands seems to lack a “national curriculum” based upon for example a national debate. The conclusion can be drawn that governmental organisations in the EU and in the Netherlands, have recognised that the world is changing fast and that action is needed in higher education. Several models were developed, but they mostly only address a part of the iceberg layers. An example is the discussion in the Netherlands regarding the importance of skills versus knowledge, which does not include all levels of the Iceberg model. Clear definitions of key-concepts, such as internationalisation, are lacking. These definitions could provide a better guideline for HEIs and their curricula. The conclusion can be drawn that the used competencies in Dutch HEIs relate on a high level to the international EHEA standard and that enough input seems to be obtained by representatives of peer universities; the alignment with the job environment of the graduates, however, does not get much attention. Developing a bachelor programme in line with the national quality standard seems to be more important.

Another conclusion is that there are different definitions and meanings when involved parties within the EHEA talk about “future skills”. As a result, it is not always clear what is meant when different stakeholders use the term “future skills”, even though there is, for example, an “European Framework for key competences for lifelong learning”. On a more positive note, literature results show that more focus should be given to all personal aspects, and not “just” knowledge and skills. Finally, reports within the EHEA state that developments are relatively

slow compared to the business environment; the number of activities can be increased, which might lead to an increase in outcomes. The conclusion can therefore be made that higher education and (international) business do not operate at the same pace.

Research shows that to be successful with alignment, it is very important to focus on the cooperation and creation of links between HEIs and the organisations where graduates go to work. However, multiple sources in literature also show that HEIs are not very successful regarding alignment. Failing to be in line with the requirements of international business and to follow the changes will result in problems for both the HEI and for organisations. From the perspective of the organisations that recruit graduates, the best performance of a new employee is realised by looking at the levels below water of the iceberg. It is therefore important not to limit the hiring process to knowledge and skills but to assess all levels. There are two reasons regarding the need for competency-based training. The first is the need to increase performance, i.e. to be able to outperform competition. The other aspect is the desire to reduce the learning curve time from job entry to full production. Spencer & Spencer have visualised this approach in a graph that fits very well to the topic of this research, as it focuses on how to improve the productivity of a new employee. This new employee could be the graduate from a HEI.

Summarising the above described conclusions, the researcher identifies the following gaps in literature:

1. Literature shows that there is confusion on what competencies are when looking beyond the first “simple” definition of the concept;
2. Literature does not provide a definition of international competencies;
3. Literature research has proven that alignment is a challenge for HEIs;
4. Research confirms that HEIs have problems keeping up with the changes in business environments;
5. There are no models available in literature that focus on alignment based upon what is being done by HEIs and what is being asked by organisations.

In addition to the conclusions described in this paragraph, the first two gaps will be used as input for the interviews with HEI experts. The next section describes the theoretical framework and the input for research design.

2.6 Theoretical framework and input for research design

The findings from literature analysis were used to develop the field research methodology that explored the views of HEI experts and representatives of business organisations. This

section describes the models, key-concepts and gaps in literature that were used as topics for discussions in the interviews with HEI-specialists; e.g. literature does not provide a definition of “international competencies”, what is the perspective of HEIs? Together with the results of the interviews, this section also provided input for Phase three where representatives of business organisations were asked to give their opinion regarding the existing and required competencies.

The internationalisation handbook that is in use in Belgium has identified four clusters regarding international competencies, as described in Section 2.4.5. These clusters were discussed with HEI-participants. A fifth cluster was added after executing the interviews with the HEI-specialists: international professional knowledge. This last cluster has therefore not been discussed during field research.

The 14 competencies in the BBA were used for the interviews with HEI-specialists and the questionnaire for business organisations.

Furthermore, the following topics were used in the interviews as well as in the survey:

- The definition of (international) competencies.
- The perspective regarding competencies in an international environment.
- Requirements of middle management.
- How competencies are aligned.

The SERVQUAL model was used by the researcher to analyse the gaps regarding alignment based upon the results of the survey for business organisations.

The model of Bloom was not used in this research. The reasoning behind this is that the model has several limitations as described in section 2.4.2 and the model has its value for assessment of students, but less for the classification of competencies.

The Iceberg model was chosen over the Miller Pyramid because it has a more detailed approach towards personal behaviour. The suggested improvements of Millers Pyramid as described in section 2.4.2, deal with the deeper levels of personal behaviour and are aspects that are described in the Iceberg model. The Iceberg model was used to help identifying and measuring gaps in alignment and combined with the model developed by the authors Lyle M. Spencer and Signe M. Spencer. By synthesising all literature and field research results and using the holistic view of Korthagen regarding personal development, a new model and process is presented in section 6.5 that can help identifying gaps regarding alignment and

may help to improve alignment. This new model and process includes the suggestion to not only think about what needs to be learned, but also how it should be learned, as described by Dewey.

3.0 Research methodology

3.1 Research structure and research philosophy

This section describes the overall research philosophy and describes how the research project is structured. The research is executed in phases with the research approach for each phase depending on the results of the preceding phase(s). Consequently, the research methods for each phase were not designed in detail until prior research was complete. The detailed research approach for each phase is presented in Sections 3.2, 3.3 and 3.4. Literature research is executed until the end of the field research. Figure 3.1 provides the overview of this structure, the interdependence of the different phases, and the executed learning and improvement loops that helped strengthen the research conclusions.

Figure 3.1: Research process steps, depicted by researcher.

Research structure

1. Phase one provides the theoretical backbone. Using descriptive research, the definitions regarding “competencies”, “middle management”, “higher education” and “BBA” were explored within the literature to determine whether there is consensus. This part of the study is descriptive with the aim to provide a definition of the concepts above and to identify gaps in literature regarding competencies. The results of this phase provided input for the design

and execution of the expert interviews executed in Phase two. The Gap overview in figure 3.2 shows all gaps that were investigated during the research.

Figure 3.2: Gap analysis overview, depicted by researcher.

The focus of the research is to identify the gaps, as identified in Figure 3.2. The major aim of this study is to investigate the gap between competencies offered within HEIs in the Netherlands and the required competencies when working in an international environment, when looking at middle management in the Netherlands (Gap four).

Gap one deals with gaps to be found in literature regarding the definition of (international) competencies. The literature review identified gaps that influenced the shaping of the research. The aim was not only to identify and characterise gaps in literature, but also to obtain a good view on which definitions are in use and which definitions can be used when asking HEI specialists about their curriculum and Dutch organisations about required competencies. This analysis formed the basis for the following steps in this research as described in figure 3.1.

This part of the research project was revisited based upon the acquired input coming from interviews with HEI experts in Phase two and the survey results in Phase three.

2. The focus in Phase two was to identify which competencies are used in one Dutch BBA programme and why, as well as which ones are considered internationally important by HEIs and why. Experts within universities were interviewed regarding competencies and internationalisation. The findings from the literature research in Phase one provided input for

the questions asked during the expert interviews. The general aim of this part of the research was to identify the gap between theory and practice in HEIs when looking at competencies (gap one). The two aims of this phase were:

- 1) to identify the vision regarding internationalisation and the definition of competencies used in higher education in The Netherlands;
- 2) to investigate what competencies are considered internationally important by HEIs when looking at their BBA programmes, and for what reason.

One might assume that the views of the HEI experts are translated towards the curriculum of their BBA-programme. However, the competencies in the BBA might be different from the opinion of experts, due to factors that were not known at the start of this study. These factors may influence the fourth gap: the gap between desired competencies by organisations and those in the BBA curriculum. This gap is the main goal of this study. It could be that certain competencies are not put in the curriculum due to factors that are beyond the control of the HEI specialists. Research will show the gap and which factors cause gap two.

3. The aim of Phase three was to identify what competencies are required of middle managers in an international environment by asking Dutch organisations. This Phase aims to investigate the demand regarding middle management competencies when looking at the Dutch German business environment. This field research was designed to provide the answer regarding the demand in practice. Representatives of Dutch organisations were asked via a survey to give their view on this subject. Input for the research design in this phase came from the results of the literature study and the findings from HEI expert interviews.

Gap three in figure 3.2 deals with the differences between competencies considered internationally important by HEI experts versus the opinion of representatives of organisations that are active in international business. Theoretically speaking, this gap might be different from Gap four; as stated earlier, it could be that competencies are not put in the curriculum due to factors that are beyond the control of the HEI specialists. Moreover, HEI experts might have a different opinion regarding the importance of certain competencies in an international environment than representatives in the field. Gap three will describe the possible differences and what causes them.

4. In Phase four, similarities and discrepancies between demand and offer were identified. In this phase, the gaps as depicted in Figure 3.2 were defined. Summarising the gaps; gap one considers the possible differences between theory and practice in HEIs when looking at the

definition of competencies. Gap two aims to identify the differences between the competencies in the BBA curriculum versus the views of HEI specialists. Gap three looks at the possible differences between the competencies found important by specialists within HEIs and those found important in the business field. Finally, Gap four focuses on the major topic of this study: the alignment between competencies in the BBA and the competencies found important in the business field.

Finally, answers were given to the defined sub questions. The researcher aims to develop a model for alignment which can be used to identify and reduce the gaps identified in Figure 3.2 thus answering the third sub question.

Saunders, Lewis and Thornhill (2012) introduce the concept of the research onion in their book "Research Methods for Business Students" which analyses different research layers or layers of the onion. Using this model, a structured approach is designed for this research project.

The research approach for this research project was described following the layers in the research onion of Saunders. For this reason, the philosophy, approach, methodology, strategy, time horizon and data collection & analysis were defined. The time horizon approach of the whole research project is cross-sectional, as the researcher studied the concepts at a certain moment in time and not over a period of time. The execution of the field research methods, the interviews and the surveys, were only carried out once.

The research design aims to use findings of one research method as input for the next, which increases the quality of the research. The four phases and how they are linked with each other were described and combined with the possible gap(s) that were identified as described earlier. For example: Phase one is the literature analysis and aims to define the gap(s) in literature regarding the competencies in an international environment. Figure 3.1 provides an overview of the research steps and how they are related. The field research methodology design requires input from literature research. Literature research results were used in the research design of the interviews with HEI specialists. The order of the research is sequential, each step requires input from the previous step. The same approach was used for the survey by using the results of the literature analysis and the interviews with HEI specialists for the research design of the survey for Dutch organisations.

3.2 Research methodology literature

This phase consists of descriptive research during which the concepts, competencies, middle management, higher education and BBA are defined by analysing literature. In addition, a more in-depth research was executed regarding competencies and the international

perspective of competencies. This part of the research is descriptive as it is the aim to establish definitions.

Summarising, the literature analysis had three aims:

1. Identify working definitions of: “middle management”, “higher education in the Netherlands” and “BBA”.
2. Describe and analyse what is known in literature about competencies.
3. Identify gaps in knowledge regarding competencies and thus contribute to the overall knowledge.

There are multiple methods to analyse literature (Saunders 2012b): narrative, evaluative, exploratory, instrumental and systematic. The narrative literature review provides criticism towards literature and results in a summary of the actual existing body of knowledge regarding the researched topic. This approach usually does not include a description of the methodology used, which gives the disadvantage that data cannot be easily reproduced. When applying this approach, the research question has to have a clear focus. This method can give a comprehensive overview of the subject and will help to identify gaps in literature. This review fits this research project as the aim is to present the existing status in literature regarding competencies and competencies in an international environment.

Another approach is the evaluative review, which focuses on providing a discussion regarding literature and their coverage and contribution to knowledge. This approach does not fit this research as literature will be used to explore practice; the results of the literature analysis must support the research activities in practice. The third type is the exploratory review, which has the aim to find out what exists in academic literature regarding research methods, empirical evidence and theories. This approach does fit as this method will be used to identify and improve the literature research findings by identifying new search areas during the research project. For instance, results from the interviews with specialists in higher education may result in new and undisclosed research areas. The fourth method is the instrumental review of literature. This approach does not identify the current available knowledge but aims to specify the best way to execute research. This approach provides no added value to this research project, because the researcher wants to use current available knowledge to identify working definitions of: “middle management”, “higher education in the Netherlands” and “BBA”. Finally, the fifth approach is the systematic review, which puts the focus on critically analysing work of other authors. This approach offers less flexibility, which is needed to be sure that all areas are covered.

The chosen research approach for the literature analysis is therefore a combination of the narrative and the exploratory review. The main aim was to describe the existing body of

knowledge (narrative approach) and to continue to explore literature after analysing the interviews with HEI-specialists in chapter four and the survey for Dutch organisations in chapter five.

The search engines Beluga and Google Scholar and libraries were used to find literature for all topics. Regarding the two topics “Higher Education in the Netherlands” (Field Sub-Question one) and the “BBA” (Field Sub-Question two), mostly Dutch state and European Union sources were used as this is the scope of the research. No overview in tables were made for these two sub questions since the search was limited to state documents of the European Union and the Dutch government which provided input regarding the actual situation.

With regards to “middle management” (sub-question three), limited literature research was executed, as the main goal here was to select a definition that fits the research topic the best. This research does not have the aim to explore the definitions regarding “middle management”. The focal point of the research was on the Netherlands since the HEIs are located there and the BBA is offered in the Dutch market. For this reason, the search was done in two languages: Dutch and English, the latter being the international language being used by most authors. The geographical area regarding literature was not limited to any region.

The search included grey literature, which are documents such as annual reports, white papers and governmental documents (Lawrence 2014). Grey literature is produced by non-traditional organisations regarding academic research such as non-governmental organisations (NGO's), government departments and agencies, private companies and consultants. The researcher paid special attention to the quality level of grey sources by limiting the source to governmental bodies, such as the European Commission.

To obtain recent sources, the time frame for middle management was between 2005 and 2018. The search was done online and offline, using Beluga and Google Scholar as search engines, and the UWS Library in Paisley, the Helmut Schmidt University Library in Hamburg and the library of the Hamburg Hochschule für angewandte Wissenschaften (HAW) as physical sources of the academic and grey literature. Older sources were added when there was an added value according to the researcher. The used keywords were described in the tables; they were used as single words or combined with other relevant topics. Table 3.1 provides an overview of the search approach of Sub-Question three.

Sub Question 3. Middle management			
<u>Study boundaries:</u>	<u>Inclusion criteria</u>	<u>Exclusion criteria</u>	<u>Remarks</u>
1. Type of data	Variety of studies; also, grey literature	Review papers, except for their references	Grey literature; for example, working papers, annual reports, government documents
2. Language	English and Dutch	Other languages	
3. Time frame	Publication years: 2005 - 2018		Period of time to obtain actual data
4. Search engines	Beluga Google Scholar		- UWS Library - Helmut Schmidt University Library - HAW Library
5. Keywords	middle management; midden-management		Combined with English keywords: definition, business, the Netherlands, Holland, Germany. Dutch keywords: definitie, business, Nederland, Duitsland.

Table 3.1: Research approach “middle management”, depicted by researcher.

The major part of the literature analysis was carried out on the concept of “competency” and “competencies” (sub-question four). The definitions that are found in literature were compared with the views of the HEI representatives and representatives from Dutch organisations. An extensive literature analysis was necessary to be sure that the definitions are current and reliable and to secure a good narrative regarding the topic.

The approach regarding the search for sources for competency and competencies was largely the same as with middle management. However, to be able to explore all sources on the topic and to be able to follow-up on new insights based upon the results of field research, the publication years covered a larger timeframe. The first important source regarding “competency” is the article of Mc. Clelland in 1973 (as discussed in Section 1.1.3), which defines the starting moment of the search for academic sources and grey literature. The analysis of the survey was finalised in 2018, consequently indicating the final year of the literature research analysis. Table 3.2 provides an overview of the search approach of Sub-Question four.

Sub Question 4. Competency and competencies.			
<u>Study boundaries:</u>	<u>Inclusion criteria</u>	<u>Exclusion criteria</u>	<u>Remarks</u>
1. Type of data	Variety of studies; also, grey literature	Review papers, except for their references	Grey literature; for example, working papers, annual reports, government documents
2. Language	English and Dutch	Other languages	
3. Time frame	Publication years: 1973 - 2018		Starting year is the publication year of the first article of Mc. Clelland
4. Search engines	Beluga; Google Scholar		- UWS Library - Helmut Schmidt University Library - HAW Library
5. Keywords	competency; competencies.		Combined with English keywords: definition, international. Dutch keywords: Nederland, internationaal.

Table 3.2: Research approach "competency, competencies", depicted by researcher.

In chapter one, the choice was made to work with "competency" instead of "competence", which is why this word is used in the search. The keywords that were used are both single and plural.

The search was organised by looking for relevance, as the research had a fairly narrow scope (competency and international) and used criteria regarding inclusion and exclusion as indicated in the tables. To stay in scope, the following checklist was used (Saunders 2012b):

A. Relevance

1. What is the date of publication?
2. Is it likely that there is a newer version?
3. Does the subject of the source fit with the research topic of this research (inclusion)?
4. Does the context match the exclusion criteria?
5. Are there any references that are useful?
6. Does the item bring anything new, e.g. a contradiction or support of results so far?

B. Value

1. Does the item contain a bias? i.e. illogical or emotional statements

2. Are there any omissions when looking at the methodology?
3. How precise are the described results?
4. Does the item provide any possible topics for future research?

Sources in literature were found using these criteria. The sources are described in the list at the end of this research report.

3.3 Research methodology HEIs

3.3.1 Research aim

Phase two consists of field research within universities of applied sciences in the Netherlands. A group of 14 universities of applied sciences use one BBA programme and curriculum, which is the main topic of this field research. Experts at HEIs were interviewed regarding competencies. The findings from the literature research provided input for these interviews. By using semi-structured interviews, the interviewees were asked for their opinion regarding competencies and the results of the literature study on competencies were shared and discussed. The main aim of this part of the research was to compare the discourse in the literature with the higher education practice differences (Gap one in Figure 3.2) and to highlight the commonalities between the competencies in the BBA curriculum versus the views of HEI specialists (Gap two in Figure 3.2). To realise this aim, sub-goals were defined. The two sub-goals of this phase were:

- 1) to identify the definition of competencies used by specialists in higher education in the Netherlands;
- 2) to investigate what competencies are considered internationally important by HEIs and why when looking at their BBA programmes.

To reach this aim and the two sub-goals, the researcher defined a structured research approach as described in the following section.

3.3.2 Research approach interviews HEI specialists

Peeling the onion of Saunders (2012b), the researcher chose the interpretive philosophy as the research philosophy for the interviews. Looking at the research topic, the researcher wanted to find out what the opinion is of specialists in the field of higher education, and therefore must focus on subjective meanings. In this phase, the question was answered how specialists within HEIs look at internationalisation and competencies in their BBA curriculum. The axiology of this philosophy implied that the researcher takes part in the discussion, taking a neutral, objective position. This was necessary to guide the interviewee through the interview using the findings of the literature research, among other things. In addition, data

collection in this research philosophy often takes place via small samples, in this case semi-structured interviews.

The chosen research paradigm is interpretive. Saunders (2012b) developed four paradigms, using radical change, objectivist, regulation and subjectivist as the four sides of a quadrant. The objectivist side of this quadrant implies a rational perspective, which does not fit with the research subject and aim. The subjectivist paradigm fits better with the interpretive research philosophy because the researcher was looking for opinions.

Looking at the dynamics in Europe regarding higher education, the radical change that can be identified was the start of the Bologna process in 1999. In this year, the current bachelor-master structure (BaMa) was introduced. Since then, the proposed changes to this BaMa structure have not been radical; an example is the introduction of new programmes such as the ERASMUS programme (European Commission 2014a, 2018b) that was initiated in 1987 or new countries that have joined the Bologna approach. ERASMUS is short for “European Community Action Scheme for the Mobility of University Students” and aims to increase the mobility of students in the EHEA-region. The assumption is that the situation in EHEA also reflects the situation at HEIs in the Netherlands. The nature of the research topic tends therefore to be more about regulation, instead of radical change. This means that the paradigm is situated in the left-bottom corner of the quadrant, which is the interpretive quadrant.

The chosen research approach is inductive. In this phase specialists were interviewed regarding competencies with the aim of obtaining more data regarding the nature of the topic. The acquired data was analysed and provided insight into the practice and usage of competencies at Dutch HEIs (Saunders 2012b). The concept was thus further explored.

The chosen research design method and strategy for the complete research project is the mixed method. A mixed method approach combines quantitative and qualitative research in a research design (Bernard 2013; Mayring 2014; Saunders 2012b). By using a sequential order, a qualitative method was used to receive input from HEIs, followed by a quantitative method in chapter five to obtain input from organisations. This exploratory sequential research design uses an interactive level of interaction. (Creswell 2010). The qualitative results from the interviews helped making decisions about quantitative research questions, sampling, and data collection for the survey for organisations (Silverman 2013).

Qualitative research is associated with interpretive philosophy (Denzin 2011; Mayring 2014). This is because the research involves working with subjective and socially constructed views regarding competencies. The way competencies are used and how they are translated from the Dublin descriptors towards the products of HEIs is different for each HEI. There are no formal rules in this area, the researcher expected different views from the consulted experts. The researcher expected also that the participants provide partly objective and subjective answers, based upon rules that might differ in each HEI and their personal experiences.

Research strategy is a plan of action. The methodological link between the philosophy and the chosen methods for collecting data (Saunders 2012a), in this case interviewing HEI-specialists, provided contextual background and gave extra information regarding the research topic. The time horizon approach was cross-sectional. The research studies the concepts at a certain moment in time. The execution of the planned methods, the interviews and the surveys, were only done once. This was done to be able to compare multiple variables at the same time, and due to the time limitation as the next step was to research the views of organisations and to compare both perspectives.

Participating HEIs

The Netherlands has 37 state-financed universities of applied sciences (Vereniging Hogescholen 2017). Some of these universities cooperate by sharing their curriculum so as to try to reduce costs when executing the programmes. Business Administration programmes are not limited to universities of applied sciences. However, another shared curriculum does not exist in the Netherlands, which is why the research in Phase 2 was carried out at universities of applied sciences that have produced, and make use of, one Dutch national education profile. This curriculum is managed by a National Curriculum Commission (Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde 2014):

Opleidingsprofiel van de Bacheloropleiding Bedrijfskunde MER; Competentieprofiel van de HBO-Bacheloropleiding CROHO 34139;

Opleiding voor Bedrijfskunde MER.

Translated into English: Education profile of the Bachelor's degree in Business Administration - Management Economy and Law; Competency profile of the HBO Bachelor's degree programme with CROHO number 34139. Education Programme for Business Administration. This document was made public in March 2014.

The BBA programme and curriculum that is in use with all 14 universities of applied sciences is based upon nine generic competencies and five task competencies. This profile discussed five so-called "task" competencies. These competencies relate to specific business

administration actions: problem analysis, diagnosing, increase effectiveness through process optimisation, change management and evaluations of actions.

In addition, the curriculum also describes nine “generic” competencies: cooperate/networking, communication, the ability to connect, act professionally, innovation, work methodically, ICT knowledge and skills, advice, and act responsibly. The five task competencies are based upon a problem-solving approach that does not limit itself to business administration and is used in various disciplines. Therefore, the primary focus during the interviews will be on the nine generic competencies, which have a clearer focus on the specific domain. The learning outcomes in this programme were out of scope in this research project as they are used on a lower level in the curriculum.

The 14 universities of applied sciences (in Dutch: “Hogeschool”) are:

1. Avans Hogeschool
2. Christelijke Hogeschool Ede
3. De Haagse Hogeschool
4. Fontys Hogeschool
5. Hanze Hogeschool Groningen
6. Hogeschool Inholland
7. Hogeschool Rotterdam
8. Hogeschool Utrecht
9. Hogeschool Windesheim
10. HZ University of Applied Sciences
11. Hogeschool van Amsterdam
12. Hogeschool van Arnhem en Nijmegen
13. Noordelijke Hogeschool Leeuwarden
14. Saxion Hogeschool Enschede

These Universities of Applied Sciences offer a variety of bachelor programmes for potential students. Most programmes focus on the Dutch market, but some programmes also want to attract foreign students. The programmes are executed at the locations of each HEI and offer different delivery possibilities such as full-time, part-time and/ or the dual study option.

Sampling

The sampling strategy was to contact all 14 HEIs. Before doing this the researcher had to obtain the approval to contact all 14 HEIs. This was obtained by contacting the chairman of the National Curriculum Commission in January 2016 and formally submitting a request to approach the persons responsible for the bachelor's degree programme with CROHO

number 34139. Although the job titles differ per HEI, most respondents of the 14 HEIs have the title “Opleidingsmanager”, in English: manager education. All respondents were responsible for the BBA-programme and sometimes also other bachelor programmes.

The chairman discussed this request in the board, and the board gave their approval on March 14, 2016 with the restriction note that all members were free to decide on an individual basis whether they want to participate in this study. The chairman provided the researcher with a list with every specialist per HEI, making it possible to identify every person responsible for the curriculum of the Bachelor programme(s) with CROHO number 34139.

In order to determine the number of interviews, the concept of saturation of knowledge was applied (Bertaux 1981; Mason 2010; Verhoeven 2012). There are two general methods regarding saturation. The first method is based upon the grounded theory and uses theoretical saturation as its principle; this means that when saturation was reached, newly obtained data no longer adds anything new to the research results. This approach continuously modifies data collection methods after each interview. The second saturation approach does not change the data collection instrument. The researcher chose this saturation method to ensure that the questions asked remain the same during the field research period. The research instrument has therefore not changed during the execution of the interviews and the researcher has stopped with planning and executing interviews when noticing that no new themes were discussed, indicating that no new data was obtained. Not reaching saturation can be a risk regarding the quality of the research and the validity of the content. There is discussion in literature regarding the possibility to calculate the probability of reaching saturation using statistics and a qualitative research approach (Fusch 2015). Galvin (2015) has made recommendations regarding the saturation number of semi-structured interviews, based on a number of criteria that impact on the reliability of findings. Although the model has some limitations, it gives an indication regarding reliability. Using the table that was generated by Galvin, given that the population consists of 14 HEIs (1 participant per HEI) and that the sample is 6 (which is 42,9% of the total population), an estimate was made regarding the probability that a certain topic is present in the indicated sample of interviewees, which indicates a certain reliability. The assumption with the used table was that the sample is random, which was difficult to determine as the researcher depends on the willingness of the 14 potential participants to participate. Assuming this is a random sample, the table of Galvin indicates that the probability that all topics are covered in the indicated sample of interviewees is between 95,33 % and 95,23%. The reliability seems therefore to be high. The execution of the saturation approach is done by comparing the

answers to the questions asked after each interview, using the same list of questions and verifying if the results are comparable.

Research methods and instruments

There are many ways to execute an interview. Saunders identifies standardised versus non-standardised interviews (Saunders 2012b). The standardised form uses interviewer-administered questionnaires while the non-standardised forms can be split in “*one to one*” and “*one to many*”. The standardised form doesn’t offer enough flexibility; the researcher wants to explore the topic with the specialists and expects surprises and new insights. Therefore, an interview method is required that provides the possibility to explore the topic based upon the answers of the participant. As the target group consists of individual specialists, the one to one direction is chosen. Here Saunders identifies three possibilities: 1) *face-to-face interviews* 2) *telephone interviews* and 3) *internet and intranet-mediated (electronic) interviews*. Concerning the aim of the research, it is important to have the time to explore different topics. Input comes from the previous phase, where relevant concepts were explored in literature that are used in the questionnaire for the HEI experts. The disadvantage of the electronic self-completion questionnaire and the telephone interviews is that the researcher did not have the flexibility nor the time to address the desired topics and combine this with an explorative approach which would lead to an in-depth interview. The best option is therefore the face-to-face interview. Verhoeven (2012) identifies a risk attached to this approach. Compared to the other two methods, the face-to-face method has a higher risk of influencing the participant. According to Verhoeven (2012), there are four options for face-to-face interviews: 1) unstructured interviews 2) open interviews 3) semi-structured interviews and 4) structured interviews. The unstructured approach usually uses one question, although the main theme stays the same and each interview can lead into different directions. When the researcher uses the open interview methodology, a topic list is used, but participants still have the flexibility to address the points they find important. The semi-structured interviews are based upon a pre-defined list of questions or themes; the structured interviews are more quantitative, as mostly pre-coded answers are used and the freedom of the participant is limited compared to the other methods. The advantage of the latter method is that it has a higher validity compared with the other methods, and the approach is also called “quantitative research interviews” (Saunders 2012b). The validity is the lowest with the open interviews and increases in the direction of structured interviews. The chosen method was therefore semi-structured interviews (Verhoeven 2012). This research method offers more added value than the other methods due to the fact that:

- 1) the researcher has defined topics from literature research that have to be used, and,

2) the open response of the interviewees on these topics gives the researcher the possibility to explore unexpected directions.

Depth could be therefore added to the response of the interviewees by asking for clarification, additional information and/ or examples, and the researcher has the possibility to identify new topics and address different angles. In addition, it is important to confront the participant with views from literature and to discuss important topics of the research project.

The interviews were held with experts with the relevant HEIs. There are many definitions and explanations of people who are called “experts”. For this research, an expert is defined as an HEI employee who is responsible for and works on the BBA-curriculum and its competencies. The selected employees have this responsibility and were asked to describe the current situation within the HEI and their vision regarding internationalisation and the BBA-competencies. They are able to offer the specific required knowledge and vision that would otherwise not be available. In addition, the assumption was made that objective data can be obtained from these experts. Semi-structured face-to-face interviews fit well with expert interviews and it could be expected that experts in a higher education environment are aware of how this research method works.

It is important to be systematic during the data collection (Verhoeven 2012). Systematic means in this situation to have a standardised approach towards the execution of the interviews. The benefit is that, when repeated, the interviews will lead to the same results. This improves the reliability of the research method and results. The interviews were therefore executed using the same questionnaire and using the same order regarding the questions in the questionnaire. It is important to organise a fitting and quiet environment where the interview can take place. For each interview, the researcher asked for a separate and quite room within the relevant HEI building. Furthermore, it is important to be unobtrusive (Baarda 2009). The researcher acknowledges his personal critical view on HEIs and their actions regarding internationalisation, which is based upon his personal experience in the field of work and upon the research in the previous chapter. The researcher has taken action to prevent subjective influencing the participants.

The “Hawthorne effect” (Mayo 1933) is an example of the influence that a researcher might have on the participant during research. To avoid influencing the participant, the researcher formulated the questions in such a way that further explanation was not needed and asked the questions of the topic list in the correct order and refrained from subjective wording or sounds. Furthermore, the focus was on asking questions like “why”, “when” and “where” to obtain depth during the interview.

A topic list and some main questions were used to structure the interview (see Appendix 5). During the interviews, the researcher tried to refrain from influencing the participant by, for instance, giving his own opinion. In addition, the research placed on an important focus on what the participant had to say. By repeating the answers of the participant, the researcher tried to stimulate response. A very important success factor is LSP (Verhoeven 2012); listening, summarising and probing. This requires an active attitude from the researcher.

All contacts on the list were contacted and interviews were scheduled at seven universities with seven different participants. More interviews were planned when needed, based upon the saturation approach. The participating HEIs represent 83% of all students studying at Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands, as can be seen in Table 3.3. In this table data from 2014 are used, as this was the most recent data (HBO-raad 2015) at the moment of executing this research.

University of Applied Sciences The Netherlands Name	Total No. UoA Students 2014
Avans Hogeschool	28.485
Christelijke Hogeschool Ede	4124
De Haagse Hogeschool	25324
Fontys Hogeschool	44310
Hanze Hogeschool Groningen	26566
Hogeschool Inholland	28555
Hogeschool Rotterdam	33944
Hogeschool Utrecht	36447
Hogeschool Windesheim	19908
HZ University of Applied Sciences	4823
Hogeschool van Amsterdam	48110
Hogeschool van Arnhem en Nijmegen	32394
Noordelijke Hogeschool Leeuwarden	12090
Saxion Hogeschool Enschede	25360
Total of 14 Universities:	370.440
percentage of total number of UoA students	83%
Total number of UoA Students in 2014	446492

Table 3.3: Comparison of total number of students in the Netherlands with all students of 14 HEIs, depicted by researcher.

The next step was to recruit the participants for the interviews. This approach is described in the next section.

Recruitment

The recruitment strategy consists of five steps:

1. The HEIs on the list were ranked according to the number of BBA students. All 14 HEIs on the list were contacted by email;

2. In total, seven participants reacted in a positive way. These interviewees were contacted by telephone to explain the purpose of the interview and to formally ask for their consent. All potential interviewees were given time to reflect on the offer of participation;
3. All seven gave their consent via email. A date and location for the interview was chosen and confirmed via a personal letter. All interviews took place in a quiet room at the working environment of the interviewee;
4. All participants received a participant information sheet (Appendix 3) and a participant consent form (Appendix 4). The consent form was returned before the execution of the interview;
5. After the interview, all participants received a transcript of the interview and were asked to make corrections or additions when necessary, and to give their approval regarding the report.

The models, key-concepts and gaps in literature described in the theoretical framework in section 2.6 were used for the field research methodology of phase 2 and phase 3. The following literature review aspects were used as input for the expert interviews in the form of questions for the semi-structured interviews:

- What is your definition of (international) competencies?
- What is your view regarding competencies in an international environment?
- Which competencies of the BBA curriculum are internationally important?
- What is middle management?
- How would you describe the target group of your BBA programme?
- How does your HEI organise alignment?
- How do you measure the success in practice (alignment) of the used competencies?

To increase the validity of the interview, before starting the interviews the topics of the interviews were discussed with the chairman of the BBA curriculum commission (LOO Bedrijfskunde MER). The topics of the interviews were assessed to confirm that they are current and relevant, as well as to verify that the targeted participants are working and responsible in the fields that were to be addressed. The result of the discussion with the chairman was that the goal and context of the research in general must be explained in more detail. The researcher therefore added a more comprehensive introduction for the interviews. Furthermore, the decision was made to focus in the interviews on the nine generic competencies. In the curriculum, the five task competencies are related to a business administrative research cycle, and were thus considered to be less attractive for a discussion regarding “internationally important” or not.

3.3.3 Data analysis interviews HEI specialists

The analysis of the data in Phase 2 had a bottom-up approach, starting with the data acquired from the interviews. The motivation for this approach was that the research is mostly exploratory, and not, for example, theory-testing (Myers 2013). A constructionist approach was used when looking at the questions that indicate the motivation regarding the usage of competencies in the Bachelor programmes. The interviewees have their subjective view on how the competencies are and must be used. The reality was built based upon the views and reactions of specialists in the universities of applied sciences.

The researcher has worked with large amounts of textual information, which were systematically analysed, thus identifying important structures. A systematic procedure of analysis is important because it must be fitted to suit the research topic. The procedure was therefore developed looking closely at the context of the topic. For analysis purposes, data gathered from the interviews were put into a software tool called MAXQDA™ (MAXQDA 2016). The choice for this tool was made based on proven flexibility and availability. This tool was used to analyse the collected data.

The following approach regarding analysis was developed by combining the step by step approach of Löfgren (2013) and the approach described by Verhoeven (2012). As a result, the steps used for the qualitative analysis were:

1. All interview transcripts are read.
2. Notes are made regarding first impressions, thus unravelling the texts in relevant parts.
3. The transcripts are reread carefully, line by line. New notes are made.
4. Relevant pieces are read and coded according to the following:
 - 4.1. Repetition
 - 4.2. Surprises
 - 4.3. Statement of interviewee
 - 4.4. Scientific links, i.e. with article
 - 4.5. Links with theories or concepts
5. The next step involves categorising. Categories are made, all results are sorted.
6. Categories are labelled. Names are given to the categories.
7. Categories are connected. Relationships between the different categories are defined.
8. A hierarchy is made. A structure is developed based upon identified relationships and ranking.
9. Results are visualised.
10. Discussion: results are interpreted and compared.
 - 10.1. Results from literature

10.2. Theories or concepts from the field

10.3. Other relevant aspects

The attitude of the researcher during analysis of the field research results should be unbiased, creative and open-minded.

Regarding repetition (Point 4.1) of the approach described above, the following analysis was undertaken:

1. To investigate which competencies first come to mind, a lexical search was executed for:
 - the nine generic competencies that form the basis of the BBA
 - the five task competencies
2. A search was executed for specific concepts that are discussed during the interviews:
 - a. “cultuur” or “culturele”: culture or cultural
 - b. “internationale competenties”: international competencies
 - c. “competenties”: competencies
 - d. “kennis”: knowledge, being part of the definition of competency
 - e. “vaardigheden”: skills, being part of the definition of competency
 - f. “attitude”: attitudes, being part of the definition of competency

An example of the search regarding the specific concepts (point 2) can be found in appendix 6.

The described approach includes coding of categories. This coding brings order into the obtained data from all interviews. The researcher organised the coding using three methods: open coding, axial coding and selective coding. Coding the fragments that were selected in the first, second and third steps is called open coding and is done first. Thereafter, the coded fragments were compared and grouped. Based upon identified relationships, a hierarchy was created, as described in the fifth step of the described approach. Finally, conclusions were drawn by analysing the coded fragments and groups in more detail. The whole process was done in the native language (Dutch), the conclusions were translated to English.

3.4 Research methodology business organisations

3.4.1 Research aim

This field research involved a survey which was sent to Dutch business organisations. The following sections describe the research approach and research results.

The main aim of this part of the research was to identify the views regarding competencies in the BBA and regarding alignment. This view would make it possible to identify gaps, in this

case Gap three and four in Figure 3.2. Gap three identifies possible differences between the competencies found important by specialists within HEIs and those found important in the business field. Gap four focuses on the competencies in the BBA and the competencies found important in the business field.

Literature research and the field research with HEI specialists resulted in the conclusion that there is not one clear and usable definition of “internationally important” competencies. Due to this, no distinction can be made between competencies, which is why the researcher did not change the focus: all competencies in the BBA-curriculum were assessed in this research.

To realise the defined aim, sub-goals were defined. The two sub-goals of this phase are:

- 1) to investigate which competencies are considered important by Dutch organisations;
- 2) to analyse the status of alignment between HEIs and Dutch organisations.

To reach this aim and the two sub-goals, the researcher defined a structured research approach as described in the following section.

3.4.2 Research approach survey business organisations

The overall research approach and the relevant concepts for this research project were described in chapter one. The theoretical framework defined in section 2.6 provides input for the research design of the interviews with HEI experts. The described results of these interviews provided input for the research methodology of Phase three. This approach is illustrated and described in Figure 3.1 and Section 3.1.

The chosen research philosophy for this Phase is realism philosophy. Although the researcher wanted to obtain data from a large group of participants, it is important to be able to obtain and analyse data in an ever-changing world; thus, taking the critical realist position and not the direct realists position, which assumes that the world is relatively unchanging. This means that the researcher aims to obtain quantitative data as well as qualitative data. The researcher wanted to find out what the opinion is regarding defined competencies in one curriculum against this changing environment. The results can be quantified and analysed. This is an important difference compared to, for example, the positivism philosophy, where the researcher ultimately wants to make “law-like generalisations” (Saunders 2012b). In this research, it was also important to obtain qualitative data; for example, regarding missing competencies, the reasons why they are missing and why they are important. This is qualitative data and crucial for input regarding a proposal to improve alignment. In this phase, the views of representatives in the field such as CEO’s and sales managers regarding

competencies were collected. The axiology of this philosophy implies that the researcher is objective and does not take part in the research. In addition, data collection in this research philosophy often takes place via large samples, in this case a survey. In Phase three, the subjective views of representatives of Dutch organisations were asked regarding the competencies of their middle management. These participants have given their opinion and their motivation regarding required competencies, and which competencies are considered important for their middle management working in an international environment.

The chosen research paradigm is interpretive. Saunders (2012b) developed four paradigms, using radical change, objectivist, regulation and subjectivist as the four sides of the quadrant. The objectivist side of this quadrant implies a rational perspective, which does not fit with the research subject and aim. The subjectivist paradigm fits better with the interpretive research philosophy.

The chosen research approach is inductive. In this phase, Dutch organisations were asked about their views regarding the competencies of their middle management. The acquired data provided insight regarding which competencies are important and valued and which competencies are lower rated and why. The results led to conclusions; thus, data collection was used to explore the views of representatives in Dutch companies. In this phase, the researcher investigated the demand and the underlying motivation regarding competencies for middle managers in an international arena. This research led to empirical generalisations.

The chosen design method and strategy is the mixed method. A mixed method approach combines quantitative and qualitative research in a research design (Saunders 2012b). By using a sequential order, a quantitative method was used in this phase. This exploratory sequential research design uses an interactive level of interaction. (Creswell 2010). The qualitative results from the literature research and theoretical framework and the HEI interviews results helped to make decisions about quantitative and qualitative research questions, sampling, and data collection. The approach was done concurrently, one phase informed the other, quantitative influenced qualitative approach, as described in section 3.1 and illustrated in Figure 3.1.

Although the research in Phase 3 was conducted quantitatively, the survey that was sent to Dutch organisations fits partly in the interpretivist philosophy. The motivation for this is that the data gathered had qualitative aspects, as it related to the attributes of people and because open questions were part of the survey. The survey focused on the opinions of senior management regarding the required competencies for middle managers working in

international settings. The expectation was that this target group is not aware of the several definitions regarding competencies, and will complete the survey partly subjectively.

Research strategy is a plan of action. The methodological link between the philosophy and the chosen methods for collecting data (Saunders 2012a), provided contextual background and gives extra information regarding the research topic.

The time horizon approach was cross-sectional. The research studied the concepts at a certain moment in time. The execution of the planned methods, the interviews and the surveys were only done once.

This phase comprises of an exploratory study with the aim of investigating the demand regarding middle management competencies within Dutch organisations. This field research provided the data pertaining to the demand in practice. Representatives of Dutch organisations were asked via a survey to give their view on this subject.

Participating organisations

The research plan required establishing a cooperation with the DNHK, the German-Dutch Chamber of Commerce (“Duits Nederlandse Handelskamer”) (DNHK 2017), because all Dutch DNHK members do business with Germany. For this reason, contact was sought with the marketing department of the DNHK in September 2016 which led to a meeting in December that same year. After several meetings, an agreement was made that the DNHK database could be used for this research.

The calculations regarding the survey are based upon one calculation for a large population and one for the DNHK-population. The number of Dutch and German organisations doing business in both countries cannot be calculated, as the Dutch Chamber of Commerce does not register if an organisation has trade relations with one specific country, in this case the Netherlands and Germany. For this reason, the researcher made a calculation with a population of 20.000, representing all Dutch companies that possibly do business in Germany and compared this with the calculation made for the DNHK population. By using a population of 20.000 organisations, the maximum sample size could be calculated as calculations made above 20.000 do not really change the sample size. This approach was chosen because the researcher wanted to compare options and wanted to have a back-up plan when things do not work out with the DNHK. By comparing these two calculations, a decision was made regarding the desired response.

Summarising, the first population is the number of organisations in the Netherlands that do business in Germany. The second population consists of all members of the “Duits

Nederlandse Handelskamer”, the DNHK (2017). Here the assumption was made that the DNHK has a representative number of Dutch organisations doing business in Germany.

Therefore, two calculations were made:

1. Using a population of 20.000 organisations.
2. Using a population of 1.300 organisations.

For this calculation, the following formula was used (Cochran 2007):

$$Sample\ Size = \frac{\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2}}{1 + \left(\frac{z^2 \times p(1-p)}{e^2 N}\right)}$$

In this formula, the following variables were used:

N = population size

e = margin of error

z = z-score, the z-score with a confidence interval of 95% is 1,96.

p = standard deviation

Using this formula, the following results were used for the survey for Dutch organisations.

Sample size Phase 3: survey Dutch organisations				
Population	Confidence interval	Confidence level	Distribution	Sample size
20.000	95%	5%	50%	377
20.000	90%	5%	50%	267
1.300	95%	5%	50%	297
1.300	90%	5%	50%	225

Table 3.4: Sample size survey organisations, depicted by researcher.

The sample has to be large enough to be able to say something about the population, this is why the maximum sample size is 377 when looking at the population of 20,000. This figure changes a little bit when calculating with a larger population such as 50,000 or 80,000 and finally has a maximum sample size of 383. The calculations in the table show that the sample size differs when looking at the two populations.

The DNHK population consisted of 1,300 members and was the sampling frame (Verhoeven 2012). The aim was to obtain a response of 22.8% or 297 usable returns. This was based upon a confidence interval of 95% and a confidence level of 5%.

Sampling methodology

The majority of the DNHK members are SMEs (Small and Mid-Sized Entrepreneurs). The targeted roles within the SMEs were within top tier of management. The assumption was that they have a good view on the required competencies of their middle management. The invitation was therefore addressed to the CEO of the DNHK-member organisation. It was not possible to ascertain whether the member organisation has employees, which is why one of the questions in the survey covers this aspect by asking for the number of employees thus making possible to identify if the participating organisation has employees. Therefore, the researcher has analysed the data for differences between freelancers and organisations with employees.

The chosen sampling approach was the simple random sample (SRS) method (Saunders 2012b, pp. 261-73). This method was chosen because generalisation is important; the aim is to be able to say something about the total population. Probability sampling was used; all addressed representatives in the database were given an equal probability of selection (Creswell 2010; Saunders 2012b; Verhoeven 2012). No subdivision was made in the population of DNHK-members. Every organisation (DNHK-member) had the same chance of participation which minimises bias and simplifies analysis of results.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire was developed based upon literature research results, the research with HEI specialists and based on the research approach as described in Section 3.2 and 3.3.

The questionnaire consists of 44 questions, of which six are open-ended and 38 are closed-ended questions. The survey is divided into three parts and each part is guided by a short introduction. The first part (questions 1 to 12) focuses on the data related to the participant, such as sector, size of organisation, role in organisation and contacts with HEIs. This part consists of open and closed questions. The questions regarding the role of the participant and sector where the organisation of the participant is active were used to improve the external validity of the survey. The results of the sector question were compared to national figures to see if there were differences. If the divide in sectors is comparable, the external validation will be higher. The positions play an important role, as the aim was to obtain data regarding middle management positions. Therefore, participants with positions above the level of the middle manager were of interest. The assumption was that they have a good view on the required competencies. The obtained results were also compared with the results of Part two and three of the questionnaire.

The second part focuses on the importance of the 14 competencies and consists mainly of closed questions for each competency. Here the participant was asked to give his or her opinion for each competency. By using all 14 competencies of the BBA-curriculum, the content validity was improved. All relevant competencies were covered and reviewed by the questionnaire. Likert scales with five options for answering were used to obtain a detailed response (Field 2018). The disadvantage of a 5-point scale is that participants can take a neutral stance. The advantage is that participants can give a strong statement by choosing either the “very bad” or “very good” answering option. Open questions were added at the end of this part to obtain qualitative data regarding the motivation of choices that were made.

The third and last part consists mainly of closed questions and asks for the satisfaction level per competency. A similar approach was chosen regarding the answering options by using the 5-points Likert scale. As in part two, open questions were added at the end of this part to obtain qualitative data regarding the motivation of choices that were made.

Validity and reliability

The questionnaire was designed to avoid random mistakes that can occur during completion, thus enhancing the reliability of the survey. Possible random errors that can occur are:

- a) The participant does not know the answer and gives a random answer;
- b) The participant accidentally highlights the wrong answer;
- c) The participant is not interested in all questions and thus adds scores in the middle, i.e. not good or bad;
- d) The participant has a different understanding of one or more keywords in the questionnaire.

These risks were managed by analysing how the survey was used. The time needed to complete the questionnaire and the usage of the scale with closed questions was analysed. A low dispersion of answers and/ or a relatively short average time for completing the questionnaire can indicate that participants have answered the questions in a fast way. This can be caused by the fact that questions that are too easy, that the participants are not really interested in the topic, and/or that they do not have an opinion. To overcome the risk of misunderstanding, each phase starts with an introduction on what is required and each competency is explained. In addition to verifying the closed questions as described earlier, the researcher checked the answers of each participant in the open-ended questions. This was done by checking if the answers that were given by each participant relate to the questions that were asked.

Some risks can unfortunately not be managed. The disadvantage of the set-up of this survey is that it has to be completed in an uncontrolled environment. The researcher cannot be present during the completion of each individual survey. This can, for instance, lead to the risk that the participant is distracted during completion or does not take enough time. The researcher planned and executed steps as described later in this paragraph that helped reducing all risks that can be managed and increase the reliability of the research results. Another risk was data management; SPSS™ was used to analyse the obtained data from the survey. The transfer of data from the online environment, to Excel and again to SPSS™ could lead to mistakes. For this reason, all data were checked after each transfer by looking at the number of records, random checks per record and the qualitative data given with open questions. This increased the reliability of the data.

The researcher tested the questionnaire to ensure that that is measured what needs to be measured (Verhoeven 2012) and used the feedback to improve the questionnaire. The testing focused on the logical order of the questions, possible mistakes, clarity of the questions and the duration of completing the questionnaire. This has improved the validity of the survey. In total, three tests with three participants were executed. After each test, the questionnaire was improved and sent to the next participant for another test. The names regarding the external persons involved in the tests are not used in this report due to privacy reasons. The aims of the tests were to:

- verify if the questions are clear;
- check the logical structure of the survey;
- verify if the questions cover all relevant areas regarding the research topic;
- check the time needed for completion.

The first test was done by the researcher, thus checking the logic and content of the survey. It resulted in changing some numbers of questions and the logical order. The second test was done with a potential participant, the Director European Key Accounts in the field of trade. Based upon his responses, the explanations per phase in the survey were adapted and some mistakes were corrected. The third test was executed with a Professor at a Dutch University of Applied Sciences. Based upon his responses and feedback, two corrective actions were identified. The BBA has several variations regarding focus, names and execution in the Netherlands; for example, the International Business and Languages study (IBL) is a BBA-variant. By adding these names, the recognition by the potential participant was improved. Furthermore, the used sectors for segmentation of the participating organisations were aligned with the existing European structure.

To be able to measure the reliability of the scale, the researcher used Cronbach's alpha. The reliability coefficient of Cronbach is a method that was used to analyse the of the internal consistency (Field 2018). To be able to get reliable results, the coding of the results must be consistent. This is why, for example, the two questions (importance and satisfaction) per competency in the questionnaire are coded in the same way. The maximum score of Cronbach's Alpha is 1,0 and there is, theoretically speaking, no minimum. When analysing the results after using the Cronbach's alpha method, high values (more than 0,80) indicate that the reliability and the internal consistency are high. When the values are low (less than 0.50) the reliability is considered to be too low. The aim is to have a minimal value of 0.70, which indicates a reliable result. Scores 0.70 or higher indicate that the analyses done with this variable result in statistically significant results.

The questionnaire can be found in Appendix 7.

Recruitment

The planned approach of DNHK members was to be coordinated in cooperation with the person responsible for the communication with, and marketing for DNHK members.

The recruitment strategy had five steps:

1. All DNHK members have to be informed about the upcoming survey via the DNHK website and "FACT", the digital DNHK newsletter;
2. Two weeks later the selected organisations receive a letter to explain the purpose of the survey;
3. This letter also contains a link to a website where the online questionnaire can be completed;
4. The participants have two weeks to complete the questionnaire. A reminder will be sent after one week;
5. After completion, all participants are given the chance to receive the results in twofold: in a report and during a presentation / workshop. An invitation will be sent to those who have indicated to be interested.

The first step had to start mid-January 2017, and the other steps follow as indicated in the five steps. Adding some weeks for extra actions to increase the response, the total throughput time was set for two months. At the end of March 2017, all data had to be gathered. Section 5.2.1. describes how the plan was executed.

3.4.3 Data analysis survey business organisations

The aim of this phase was to investigate the demand regarding middle management competencies when looking at the Dutch-German business environment. The researcher started with analysing the reliability via Cronbach's alpha. The analysis showed the competencies that are most required in an international environment; ranking the results by comparing variables made this clear. Furthermore, by using simple and multiple regression analysis, possible patterns were investigated, e.g. the relationship between dependent and independent variables.

The analysis was based upon quantitative and qualitative data which was coded by using first cycle and second cycle coding (Saldana 2016). In the first cycle, both descriptive and pattern coding were used to develop categories of answers. The answers were coded towards a descriptive category. In addition, the patterns were analysed looking at similarity and frequency. In the second cycle, both focused coding and axial coding were used. The aim of focused coding is to find similarities in themes and concepts. This was done by a clustering strategy of handing categories and re-categorising earlier made codes and code schemes. The aim of axial coding is to find relations between a category's properties and dimensions.

The following concepts were used for analysis (Verhoeven 2012):

1. The distribution of a certain variable; this concept provides a frequency distribution that gives an overview of the counts per answer.
2. The central tendency is a set of tools that provide different data presentations:
 - a. The mean is the average of all counts;
 - b. The mode is the most frequent occurring variable;
 - c. The median is middle value of a ranked distribution of the observed variable.
3. The range indicates the distance separating the highest from the lowest value of the variable.
4. The variance describes the variability of the distribution of all data. It describes how much the research results differ from each other; a high variability indicates a high spread of data.
5. The standard deviation is the measure that indicates the variability in a set of data compared to the mean. When the score regarding the deviation is higher, the data are more dispersed when lower the data are more concentrated.

An example of used coding regarding the open question regarding the motivation regarding awareness of HEIs can be found in Appendix 8.

The researcher used several methods to analyse the obtained data from the survey. Using a univariate analysis, one single variable was displayed in a pie or another graph. This simple linear regression uses one dependent variable and one independent variable for analysis and provides a simple but very accessible view on the results (Verhoeven 2012). Pie charts were used when the number of categories is not very high. The researcher also used the multivariate analysis method, which uses one dependent and two or more independent variables. This method uses two or more variables for analysis purposes. The chosen multivariate analysis method is the regression analysis, which was used to identify possible relationships between i.e. the answers given regarding the importance of competencies and the level of satisfaction per competency. The regression explains the relation between one dependent variable and one or more independent variables and has the aim to either determine the level of prediction, to forecast certain relevant effects and/ or to provide a trend for a forecast. Regression analysis consists of several types that can be used by the researcher (Field 2018). All these methods primarily aim to explain and determine relationships between variables.

3.5 Ethics

3.5.1 Ethics interviews HEIs

The study was conducted in line with the by UWS approved protocol which is described in this section. Due to the sequential order of this research project, ethical approval was sought twice; first for the interviews as described in this section, and a second ethical approval was sought for the survey, described in section 3.5.2. Both approaches were approved.

All persons that were contacted and asked for their participation received a participant information form. When the approval was given, the interviewee received a letter of consent. To ensure confidentiality, each participant had a code. This code was registered on the letter of consent. From this moment on, the interviewees were anonymous during the research period.

All information gathered from the participant is linked only to the participant identification number (PIN). All data was reported in aggregate format without using the PIN numbers or real names. The participant remains anonymous in any reports or publications arising from this study. Their identities are completely concealed and will always be protected.

There was a potential risk to the universities taking part in the study in terms of being singled out as not meeting the business competencies. This has the potential to damage the

reputation of the organisation. The risk was relatively low because the universities have joined efforts in this matter. During the process of development, feedback was retrieved from different business fields. The risk was handled by providing feedback to all participants, and in addition to the chairman of the “Landelijk Opleidingsoverleg Bedrijfskunde (LOO) Bedrijfskunde MER”. This way the feedback and information was also organised “umbrella-wise” for all participating universities. This reduced the risk for the individual university.

The research was executed according to “De Nederlandse Gedragscode Wetenschapsbeoefening” developed by the “Vereniging van Universiteiten” (VSNU). This code of conduct regarding science and research was developed in 2012 and updated in 2014. The association of universities (VSNU) focuses on education and research at Dutch Universities.

All information will be destroyed after five years of the study being completed.

3.5.2 Ethics survey business organisations

After the execution of the interviews as described earlier the second ethical approval was sought for the survey. This approval can be found in Appendix 1.

By completing the online survey, it is understood that the participant has consented to participate in the study. From this moment, all data gathered remained anonymous during the research period.

All data was reported in aggregate format. The participant will remain anonymous in any reports or publications arising from this study. The identities of the participants are anonymous before, during and after the survey is completed and all obtained data will always be protected.

All information will be destroyed after five years of the study being completed.

3.6 Data security

The data that were obtained during research are kept safe and secure. Therefore, the following aspects were worked out in a plan:

1. How the data is stored, including back-up;
2. Who has access to the data, and;
3. How the data can be accessed.

The focus lies on planning for the unexpected.

All research data is stored on a back-up device that has no direct connection with the internet. All data is solely accessible by the researcher. Only he and when required his supervisors have access to all data on the stand-alone back-up password protected device. All printed material is kept in one place, in a locked cupboard, and only accessible by the researcher.

Data storage and security is executed according to “De Nederlandse Gedragscode Wetenschapsbeoefening” developed by the “Vereniging van Universiteiten” (VSNU). This code of conduct regarding science and research was developed in 2012 and updated in 2014 (VSNU). The association of universities (VSNU) focuses on education and research at Dutch Universities.

All research data will be destroyed five years after obtaining the data.

4.0 Competencies in Higher Education Institutes

4.1 Introduction

The overall research approach and the relevant concepts for this research project are described in the previous chapter. Having analysed the literature perspective on competencies and related concepts in chapter two, the next step is to research the situation in practice. The results of the literature research in chapter two led to the defined theoretical framework that was used for the research methodology described in the previous chapter. This theoretical framework helped structure the research approach and helped realise an in-depth study regarding the vision on and usage of competencies in HEIs in the Netherlands and the view of HEI-specialists regarding alignment with business organisations in the Netherlands. The focus of this research is to examine the alignment of practices between HEIs and business organisations. This chapter contains the results of the interviews with HEI-specialists, while the results of research involving business organisations will be presented in chapter five.

4.2 Presentation of research results and analysis

4.2.1 Research execution versus planning

All 14 universities of applied sciences were contacted via e-mail and telephone. The universities that were interviewed are shown in table 4.1; the names and figures in bold are the universities of applied sciences that were consulted.

University of Applied Sciences The Netherlands Name	Total No. UoA Students 2014
Avans Hogeschool	28.485
Christelijke Hogeschool Ede	4124
De Haagse Hogeschool	25324
Fontys Hogeschool	44310
Hanze Hogeschool Groningen	26566
Hogeschool Inholland	28555
Hogeschool Rotterdam	33944
Hogeschool Utrecht	36447
Hogeschool Windesheim	19908
HZ University of Applied Sciences	4823
Hogeschool van Amsterdam	48110
Hogeschool van Arnhem en Nijmegen	32394
Noordelijke Hogeschool Leeuwarden	12090
Saxion Hogeschool Enschede	25360
Total of 14 Universities:	370.440
percentage of total number of UoA students	83%
Students at UoA where interviews executed	207.578
percentage of population (14 UoA)	56%
percentage of total number of UoA students	46%
Total number of UoA Students in 2014	446492

Table 4.1: Coverage of consulted Universities of Applied Sciences, depicted by researcher.

A lack of time was the main motivation within the target group not to participate. The respondents represent seven universities of applied sciences, by which more than half of the student population was reached. In total 56% of the population was covered, which is 46% of all university of applied sciences students in the Netherlands in 2014.

The interviews were based upon the concept of saturation of knowledge as described in the sampling strategy. The population consisted of 14 universities of applied sciences. In total, seven interviews were completed. Due to the chosen saturation approach, the interviewer stopped interviewing once patterns became apparent; no new topics were addressed and more interviewees confirmed the already existing information. These patterns became apparent after six interviews. The last interview (number seven) was also completed because it was already planned and to confirm that saturation was really happening and to make sure that the already existing information could be confirmed.

The results of each interview were made anonymous and sent to each participant to for approval. Out of all seven reports that were sent, one participant did not respond to the request for approval regarding the transcript. The reason for this is unknown as the participant has not reacted to any of the contact efforts. Therefore, the results of six interviews form the basis for analysis, these six transcripts are coded by using numbers: "HEI1" until "HEI6". The research was executed precisely as intended and described in chapter three. The analysis of the research findings was done according to plan, as described earlier. For this, MAXQDA™ was used and the steps described in Section 3.3 were executed. Categories were labelled, names were given to the categories and categories were connected. Relationships between the different categories were defined; e.g. internationalisation was connected with other different concepts such as competencies and orientation. A hierarchy was made, thus creating a structure based upon identified relationships and ranking.

The following categories were created:

- A. The 14 competencies; nine generic and five task competencies. The motivation for this decision is that these are the competencies of the curriculum. The focal point is on the nine generic competencies.
- B. The definition of competency identifies three elements: knowledge, skills and attitudes. The motivation for this decision is that this is the definition of "competency" used by the 14 HEIs in the Netherlands.
- C. Internationalisation, in combination with other concepts such as HEI and levels. This category was chosen because competencies in an international arena is the focus of this research.

In the following discussion, the terms “most” and “some” are used to describe the results of the qualitative data from the six interviews “Most” means more than half of the participants (>3), “some” means 1, 2 or 3.

Section 4.2.2 presents the main topics found based upon the analysis of the transcripts. In section 4.3 the researcher describes the conclusions based upon the analysis of the results.

4.2.2 Research results of HEI interviews

This section describes the results of the interviews and the performed analysis.

Discussed topics by analysing the repetition of words

The frequency of words/ concepts was analysed. For this, a search was executed and initially the following words were used (in “Dutch” and in the English language):

- a. “cultuur” or “culturele”: culture or cultural
- b. “internationale competenties”: international competencies
- c. “competenties”: competencies
- d. “kennis”: knowledge, being part of the definition of competency
- e. “vaardigheden”: skills, being part of the definition of competency
- f. “attitude”: attitudes, being part of the definition of competency

Based upon the results, other words were added to the search. All words of all transcripts were analysed to see which words were used the most.

Codes HEI-Interviews and frequencies			
No.	Nederlands	English	Frequency
1	"Internationale competenties"	"International competencies"	272
2	Competenties	Competencies	239
3	Kennis	Knowledge	50
4	Gedrag	Behaviour	46
5	Management	Management	39
6	Vaardigheden	Skills	39
7	Context	Context	38
8	Cultuur of culturele	Culture or cultural	33
9	Samenwerken	Cooperation	26
10	Houding	Attitude	16
11	Probleem, problemen herkennen	Problem, problem recognition	16
12	Handelen	To act	12
13	Communiceren	Communication	11

Table 4.2: Codes HEI-interviews and frequencies, depicted by researcher.

Words such as “HEI” and “student” were excluded in the search as they do not provide an added value to this analysis. Apart from the fact that the words “competencies” and “internationalisation” had the highest scores, some remarkable results came out of this analysis. The following section describes the main results of this Word-count.

When looking at the frequency of words and concepts used during the interviews, the following are worth mentioning. The words “competencies” and “internationale”, “internationalisering” were most frequently used. In English, these words are translated as: competencies, international and internationalisation. This is no surprise because they directly relate to the topic of the research and the questions asked during the interviews. The participants were first questioned regarding the definition of competencies. This resulted in a relative high frequency of knowledge (50) and skills (39). However, the word frequency for attitude (16) is relatively low compared to knowledge and skills. The set of these three are mentioned by most participants as their definition of competency.

The definition regarding competency is related to the view of the HEI-specialists regarding competencies needed as a middle manager, which is the targeted position of the BBA-student after graduation. Middle management is defined by most participants as the management in the middle, between managers that operate on a strategic and an operational level. Middle managers operate on tactical level and ideally should communicate strategic changes to employees with operational responsibilities and communicate the wishes of operations towards the managers in the top of the organisation. Many participants see a trend that the number of layers in the organisations is reduced, which has its implications for middle management. It sometimes results in roles that have responsibilities on all levels of the organisation or that the position is eliminated; i.e. by introducing project management and project management roles. This definition is in line with the results from literature research.

Analysing the word-frequency further, more concepts were found that were used relatively often. The word “context” and/ or its Dutch counterpart “omgeving” was used 38 times when discussing the future working environments of the bachelor alumni. The word “context” is also used in the Netherlands, which is why these two words are combined in this count. The participants placed their alumni often in an international working environment. Context defines, according to some of the participants, the necessary competencies. For example, a decision-making process in China or Japan requires a different approach compared to one in Germany or the Netherlands.

Another concept often used in the interviews is “cultuur”, “culturele” and other related words; in English, this is called culture and cultural and was mentioned 33 times and can only be found in the top of the list by combining all used variations. This concept is linked with internationalisation, learning to deal with different cultures in the study programme. Thus, preparing to be able to work in an international arena.

Learning about different cultures can take place when the student is studying and maybe even living in one of these cultures. This why many HEIs offer their students the possibility to study one or more semesters with a partner university (of applied sciences) in another country. Or, as one participant said:

*We are also looking for changing partner universities and that also internationally...”.
(HEI2)*

This indicates that some HEIs are continuously looking for new international partners.

The third important topic based upon word-count is “international” and all related words that were found in the transcripts, such as the Dutch words “internationaal”, “internationale” and “internationalisation”. All participants indicated that their HEI has a good international network enabling their students to study abroad for a semester or maybe longer. The countries vary. Some HEIs at the border with Germany have good relationships with this neighbour, while other focus more on the UK, Spain or on countries outside Europe. The decision-making process regarding the choices made regarding the search for partner HEIs abroad is not very transparent. According to the participants, there are more methods available for HEIs to let their students learn aspects of internationalisation, as it is important to realise that not all students have the possibility to go abroad and study. Most students in the Netherlands remain there. For these students, the concept “internationalisation at home” was developed (Nuffic 2016). This is used as shown in the following quote:

This is also possible through internationalisation at home. And you don't necessarily have to send all students abroad, you can also immerse yourself here in the Netherlands, in how minorities live, how are the refugees doing and so on. (HEI6)

The idea behind this concept is that the student should not have to go abroad to learn and experience internationalisation; examples are the internationalisation of the curriculum, the international classroom and online internationalisation. This concept was mentioned several times by the participants and often led to a discussion regarding the question where students can and should learn to work in international environments and where they should work on their competencies. “Internationalisation at home” is not only important for those who do not have the chance to study in another country. One might ask whether the students who have the chance to study a semester in different cultural setting learn more than students who cannot but use learning methods. This has not been investigated further.

One participant emphasised that he thinks there are “*multiple levels of internationalisation*” (HE11). Learning to really deal with cultural differences is something that HEIs do not address. This kind of specialisation needs other curricula and learning methods. According to this participant, the current model or approach regarding internationalisation is rather generic.

Another participant stated that certain programmes do have specific national requirements. HRM and, in more detail, the related laws regarding how to manage employees are mostly country specific. The same applies for the bachelors Law and Accountancy. Every country has accountants, but the laws are different in every country. Compared to these bachelor programmes, the BBA is a rather generic programme and has less country specific elements. Comparing several BBA's that are offered in different countries will probably lead to the conclusion that there are many comparable elements in the programmes and that BBA alumni can work in many countries. The competencies are so generic that they can be applied in an international context.

All other words and related frequencies do not provide additional insight or have to be put in the context of how the participant has replied to the questions asked during the interview. The next paragraphs will address the encountered surprises.

Surprises

Surprises in the discourses are described based upon remarks and suggestions that are defined by the researcher as unexpected. For example, when asked for their definition of competency, most specialists described a set knowledge and skills, sometimes adding attitudes. The surprise was the relatively low word-frequency of attitude (16) and to act (12). Instead, participants referred to behaviour more frequently (46) when discussing competencies:

Ehm, I think, how do we work with that, on the one hand it is skills but also a certain behaviour or whatever you want to call it. That the student in addition to the knowledge they need ultimately will be able to function as a business administrator.
(HE14)

The participants did not use the term attitude often nor discussed the concepts “to act”, “attitude” and “behaviour” regarding their differences and similarities and their relationship to knowledge and skills, whereas knowledge and skills were discussed regularly during all interviews. This was not expected because attitude does belong to the definition of competencies that is being used by HEIs. Other aspects, such as the non-visible parts of the iceberg such as values, were only mentioned occasionally during the interviews.

All participants indicated that they are actively working with internationalisation in their curriculum. The surprise is that the way this is done differs per HEI. The geographical location and attached regional factors play an important role. All HEIs have indicated that they try to work with regional organisations and provide access for students who live in a circle around and the direct neighbourhood of the specific university of applied sciences. Because some regions are, for example, close to the German border, one might expect that these HEIs focus on a region that includes both sides of the border, i.e. a region that covers the Netherlands as well as Germany. However, one HEI close to the German border indicated that despite their geographical position, they were unable to develop modules dedicated to doing business with Germany. They have acknowledged the importance of the trade between the two countries. They did develop ideas to add this possibility in the BBA-curriculum but have not been able to realise it. Reasons for this include a lack of money, a bureaucratic organisation and the absence of a political willingness to invest. In this situation, quality control by the NVAO (NVAO; Accreditations Organisation of the Netherlands) plays a role. HEIs are “ruled” by quality aspects which are being checked on a regular basis by the NVAO in the Netherlands. Without the NVAO quality approval, no bachelor or master programme can be offered; no students can start with this study programme and the HEIs do not get any money from the government. It was stated several times by participants that bureaucratic and budgeting issues are a barrier for innovation and alignment with job-market needs.

All HEIs are working with internationalisation in different ways. The definition of internationalisation is also different per HEI. The researcher obtained different answers to the question what internationalisation means when targeting geographic areas. No clear answers were given to the question: “are you preparing students to be ready to work in an international environment, for example the Dutch-German business or as a global middle manager of something in between?”. Most participants struggled with this question. This shows that no real thoughts were given to what internationalisation means for the curriculum and what the targeted international positions are for their graduates.

Although some HEI-specialists state that they have a clear view on internationalisation and competencies, sometimes contradictory actions are planned. One specialist states that his HEI is very internationally oriented and has the view that all competencies are international when placed in such an environment. The international focus of the HEI is supported by stated facts, such as having contact with over 100 HEIs and universities in many other countries and being able to offer many apprenticeships abroad. Nevertheless, this HEI is thinking about adding one extra competency; “international sensitivity” to give more attention to internationalisation. This is a contradiction; if all competencies are international when

working in an international environment, there is no need to add an extra competency covering aspects of internationalisation to the curriculum.

Statements

All HEIs work with competency-matrices for their bachelor programmes. The main purpose is to have a uniform way of working within the programme. All participants indicate that the BBA builds a broad and rather general knowledge basis, without a specific specialisation.

Although there is one curriculum for all 14 HEIs regarding the BBA, the universities have enough possibilities to add their own philosophies and vision in the curriculum regarding for example internationalisation. This relative freedom results in different ways of operationalising internationalisation. Some HEIs use the concept “Internationalisation at home” while others offer the possibility to study a semester abroad. Many state that the attention towards internationalisation has to be improved; the following quote provides the motivation of one participant:

Well, in essence, you can still obtain your bachelor title and master thesis competencies without having crossed borders. And without having done anything regarding learning about other cultures, etc. So, in that sense, the international orientation fails, which is why something must be added. (HEI2)

What has to be added according to this respondent was not made clear and needs to be further investigated.

Many participants stated that internationalisation is very important and described what their HEI is doing to address this in their bachelor programme. This does not mean that everyone is happy with the way this is handled. One participant concluded with the following statement: “*The way internationalisation is being created now cannot be accredited*” (HEI3). The participant motivated this remark with the following three points:

1. The concept is not 100% clear to everyone, there is no common definition and/ or understanding of what internationalisation is and what it means;
2. Everyone translates this concept into different views and activities, as there is no common definition. The way internationalisation is used in higher education differs per HEI and sometimes even per faculty;
3. The execution (operationalisation) is treated differently in each HEI; the approach differs very much per university of applied sciences.

From an accreditation point of view, this statement is rather dangerous. It means that the bachelor programme cannot be accredited and that the programme cannot be offered. It might also lead to the situation that students will learn different things in one and the same curriculum depending on the HEI and the study.

The accreditation procedure is by far the most important quality aspect according to the participants. It defines processes and procedures within the university. Within the defined processes, competencies play an important role as they define the desired end-level of the study programme. Although it is unclear how important alignment is, the statement can be made that alignment with the job market and internationalisation is ranked lower than accreditation on HEI priority lists.

Alignment

The way the universities of applied sciences try to succeed regarding alignment and the effectiveness of the defined competencies is the same in every HEI. The following methods are used:

1. Measuring student satisfaction via surveys.
2. Surveys for alumni; always within 1 or 2 years after graduation, but not done regularly and not by every university of applied sciences
3. “Werkveldcommissie” or advisory board: this is a commission with field representatives; the members are asked to provide input regarding the content of the bachelor programme. Usually three or four business representatives participate in each commission.

The only differences between the different HEI representatives deal with the frequency of the surveys and the size of the targeted population. Some HEIs send surveys each year or even more often, while other have a lower frequency.

This description of how success is measured indicates that these HEIs consider their students to be their customers. Their satisfaction level is measured by most HEIs. These surveys focus on the satisfaction of the students regarding the programme and its execution, not on the connection with the working environment for which they are being prepared. The question is if the students know which competencies are required in their future working environment. The organisations where the students might end up working may have a better view regarding the required competencies. However, they are not asked for their opinion or asked to evaluate. Some HEIs also ask their alumni for their opinion, but it is not clear what is being done with the results of these surveys.

HEIs do involve representatives such as managers and specialists from practice. Apart from using guest lecturers who share their practical experience with students, they also form advisory boards for the development of each study programme. This is a commission with field representatives, usually people working in the field related to the programme. These

members are asked to provide input regarding the content of the bachelor programme. The required expertise of these business representatives depends on the study programme. For example, a law study programme requires experts with a law background. One might question whether usage of the “Advisory Board” addresses the requirements of organisations regarding competencies in a representative way. Though they are representatives from practice, their number is really small.

The aim of the bachelor programme and the underlying curriculum is that students are offered the chance to develop themselves and obtain a bachelor title. How alignment is organised with their future job market remains however unclear. Organisations are not asked by the universities of applied sciences for their opinion regarding the competencies used in the relevant bachelor programme in a structured way and on a regular basis. Neither are they asked about the alignment of study and work. Therefore, the question if the HEIs deliver the workforce that have the competencies that are needed in their future working environment cannot be answered. However, the assumption can be made that it is difficult - if not impossible - to deliver quality in the eyes of the future employer of the students without alignment. It remains unclear how success is measured by HEIs regarding alignment with practice of the developed competencies. When asked, some participants replied that it is recommendable to search for alignment by regularly asking organisations for their opinion regarding required competencies in the market. Most participants talk about employability as the proof of good alignment:

I notice at graduation ceremonies, if I ask right and left, that I am always surprised how many students already have a job which sounds like they are all at the intended level of a starting professional. (HEI6)

However, one might question this idea; a low employment rate influences the speed regarding finding a job but does not say anything about the quality of alignment.

The conclusion can be made that organisations are involved in product development within HEIs. However, there are no processes in place that define the needs regarding competencies and that evaluate the outcome of the learning processes within HEIs against these needs in a continuous and structured way. It is very critical when HEIs do not execute any research regarding the wishes of their end-customers, and when they do not try to obtain the (future) demand regarding competencies needed in the organisations where their alumni will be working following their bachelor study. The alignment between developed and demanded competencies may remain a big gamble. The graduates do not know if their competencies fit the requirements and the organisations do not know if their new hires match or even exceed their demand regarding competencies and will bring real added value.

Competencies and internationalisation

Each interview started with a short introduction by the researcher concerning the aim and scope of the study, as well as the importance of the interview. One of the first questions focused on the definition of the concept competency: what are competencies according to the view of the participant? Many participants indicated that this was a difficult question and started to describe the concept by talking about knowledge and skills. Some also indicated that behaviour is also part of the definition, followed by a discussion about behaviour. The overall definition of behaviour was the ability to perform a certain task in a certain environment.

The internationalisation handbook that is in use in Belgium has identified five clusters regarding international competencies (Flanders Knowledge Area vzw. 2017). However, during the execution of the interviews, the handbook described only four clusters; the fifth cluster “international professional knowledge” was therefore not discussed. The following clusters were discussed with all participants:

1. Intercultural;
2. Languages;
3. Relation student and society;
4. Personal development.

The clusters “intercultural” and “languages” are recognised by all participants; all are the opinion that these two are important when looking at internationalisation and competencies. Cluster three, the relation between student and society, was identified as the environment where learning and development in an international environment takes place. Global awareness is an example of a competency belonging to this cluster. According to some participants, the focus of the study programme regarding internationalisation can also be limited to, for instance, two countries instead of a region or all countries in the world. This indicates that internationalisation has different dimensions and requires a clear definition for each education programme. Personal development is regarded as being a standard cluster, the participants did not address this cluster in much detail.

The results of the interviews show that there are different opinions regarding which competencies are important internationally and which are not. There are two main approaches regarding this assessment. Some participants look at each competency separately, and evaluate per competency if it is internationally relevant. The importance from an international perspective depends on the competency. Another discussion resulted in the view that all competencies are internationally important because they should all be viewed from a context perspective. When working in an international environment, all competencies

are relevant to the performance of the middle manager. Depending on the context of the job and work to be done, the relevance and importance of each competency may vary. This context is relevant:

Well, business administration students very often work in an international context, so, they have something to do with internationalisation or with export or with different cultures (...) that you really train for international positions. Well, we do not train for international positions, but we do train them for an international environment. (HEI1)

The first perspective, which is called by the researcher the “competency-based approach”, defines each competency as the starting point. This perspective results in different views regarding the importance of each of the nine competencies. All participants gave their view regarding the importance of each competency, independent from their preferences regarding the competency or the context approach. The competencies “cooperate/ networking”, “communication” and “the ability to connect” are considered internationally important by almost all participants. Different views exist regarding the competencies “act professionally” and “innovation”. Some participants consider them to be important when working in an international environment. Other participants do not share this opinion. The motivation was not always very clear or fact-based. The yes and no votes were in balance. Internationally less important are “working methodically”, “ICT knowledge and skills”, “advice”, and “act responsibly”. The motivation of most participants here was that these competencies do not play an important role when working abroad or in an international environment when compared with a local or national working environment. These competencies are not directly related to or influenced by for example culture or languages. The motivation given by the participants is largely subjective. No fact-based proof or sources from literature were given by the participants that might support these views.

One HEI is thinking about adding an extra competency to the existing nine: “cultural sensitivity”. Their view is that this competency is a requirement for international working environments. Although all HEIs use the same curriculum, this change seems to be possible without having consent of the other universities.

Figure 4.1 visualises the results looking at the views by competency. The competency “cultural sensitivity” is added to the figure, but was not included in the original 14 competencies of the BBA.

Figure 4.1: Competency-based approach, depicted by researcher.

The second perspective, which is called by the researcher the “context-based approach”, states that the context of the working environment is the starting point. The importance of each competency is context-driven. Here all competencies are internationally important, but the environment defines the level of importance. Figure 4.2 visualises the results of this context approach.

Figure 4.2: Context-based approach, depicted by researcher.

In the context-based approach there is no need to add “cultural sensitivity” as an extra competency. In this approach, all aspects that are important for the working environment must be included in the relevant competencies.

One participant explained his vision regarding the relation between the BBA curriculum and internationalisation. BBA students may often work in positions with an international context, either via export activities, buying from another country or having customers abroad. The BBA curriculum could have three levels regarding internationalisation. Level one has the aim to get acquainted with the concept of internationalisation. Here students have to learn, for example, which definitions are present and what the different views are in literature. In Level two, students have to learn to work in an international context; here theory meets practice. Finally, Level three has the aim to educate students for an international position; the student will zoom in on certain business environments and attached roles. In this level, specific learning programmes have to be attached to the specific and actual context in practice. Although the researched BBA programme does not educate students specifically for a Level three international position, the graduates that work in an international environment may be lacking certain required and specific context-related competencies. Considering this fact and the given three levels, it would be very strange to add specific competencies with the aim of developing internationalisation in the curriculum. Every competency can be put in an international context.

Most interviewees indeed feel that defining a context for competencies is important. Developed competencies have to lead to performance, in this case performance on the job and added value for the organisation. Some participants indicate that competencies can be used everywhere and are not specific, i.e. they can be used in a hospital and in a trade organisation. Other participants counter this statement by stating that they want their students to be able to learn the competencies in specific business working environments and thus focus more on specific roles in specific environments. Suggestions for further research were made:

It would be interesting to put that against a number of international or foreign business administration courses to see if that is the same set. My idea in this regard is that many foreign study programmes focus more on the knowledge components. We also very clearly focus on that behavioural and attitude component. (HEI2)

Learning outcomes were mentioned as the extra method or maybe even alternative for competencies. In the current situation, students may have the same end-level competencies but have different bachelor end-level profiles.

4.3 Conclusions research competencies in HEIs

A constructionist approach was used when looking at the questions that indicate the motivation regarding the usage of competencies in the Bachelor programmes. As indicated in the research approach, the aim was to construct a view on which competencies in an international environment are considered to be important and how alignment regarding the requirements of competencies in the business arena is managed by HEIs.

Looking back at the aim and the two sub goals regarding Phase two of this research project, it can be concluded that they were reached. The results of the field research show how the HEIs deal with competencies and which competencies are considered internationally important by HEIs when looking at their BBA programmes. The interviews with HEI specialists result in the following conclusions.

HEIs use competencies and all specialists could give a rough definition during the interviews. However, when discussing the concept in more detail complexity arose and the concept became unclear. The development of behaviour was described by some of the participants as an important goal of the BBA-programme, which is confirmed by a relatively high usage of the word behaviour when discussing competencies. However, the topics attitude and to act were relatively less discussed in a conversation about competencies. No common definitions of competencies needed in an international environment were found. Neither is there any method to assess which competencies are internationally important and why.

All participants indicated that they are actively working with internationalisation in their curriculum. The definition of internationalisation is different per HEI. The researched universities of applied sciences have different views on how internationalisation of working environments should be integrated into their BBA programme. This freedom that HEIs have regarding the execution of the curriculum results in different ways of operationalising internationalisation. Some HEIs use the concept "Internationalisation at home" while others offer the possibility to study a semester abroad. This shows that no real thoughts were given to what internationalisation means for the curriculum and what the targeted international positions are for their graduates. This situation is reflected by a citation of one specialist, who concluded: "*The way internationalisation is being created now cannot be accredited*" (HEI3). There is no common way of dealing with this concept, which means that it cannot be measured as it lacks quality references.

The concept that there are multiple levels of internationalisation as emphasised by one participant can be of interest regarding the alignment of competencies. Learning to really deal with cultural differences based upon a developed vision on how to deal with internationalisation is something that HEIs currently do not seem to address. This kind of specialisation needs another curriculum and learning methods and/ or a different scope. This concept indicates that the current model or approach regarding internationalisation is rather generic on the one hand and individual on the other hand. Depth is missing and it seems that every HEI has its own perspective on internationalisation. According to some participants, the focus of the study can also be limited to for example two countries instead of a region or all countries in the world. This would reduce the scope and make alignment with business organisations easier, as the focus is, for example, narrowed to cultural differences between Germany and the Netherlands.

Although it is unclear how important alignment exactly is at the researched HEIs, the statement can be made that alignment with the job-market and internationalisation is ranked lower than accreditation on HEI priority lists. Alignment of the required and offered competencies is difficult for universities of applied sciences. The existing ways of finding the needs in the market such as advisory boards and surveys for students and alumni can be considered insufficient. Although there are other ways to find information regarding business developments and the necessary competencies, direct contact with the future employers of their graduates is to be preferred. Alignment from the perspective of HEIs is not sought by asking organisations for their opinion regarding required competencies in a structured way. HEIs have difficulties matching the requirements in the field due to a lack of knowledge of the desired competencies, but also due to more internal issues such as a lack of money, a bureaucratic organisation, and the absence of a political willingness to invest. It was stated several times by participants that bureaucratic and budgeting issues are a barrier for innovation and alignment with market needs.

The HEI specialists have different views regarding which competencies are internationally important. As a result, the research could identify two perspectives: the first perspective, which is called by the researcher the “competency-based approach”, and the second perspective, which is called by the researcher the “context-based approach”.

The conclusions from this research, including the two perspectives, were used as input for the survey for organisations.

4.4 Input for survey competencies Dutch organisations

Findings from the interviews with HEI specialists were combined with the results of the literature research to provide input for Phase three, where representatives of organisations were asked for their opinions on the required competencies for middle management.

The following aspects were used to design the questionnaire and for the development of questions:

- Having experience with doing business internationally; in this case with Germany;
- Experience with BBA-graduates as employee(s);
- Qualitative and quantitative aspects regarding contact with HEIs in the Netherlands;
- Awareness within HEIs regarding desired competencies of middle management by organisations;
- Importance and satisfaction level per curriculum competency (14 in total).

In addition, questions were included about which aspects are missing when looking at the competencies in the BBA-curriculum. The results of research involving business organisations will be presented in the next chapter, which explores the views of business organisations as to whether their requirements of new employee competencies align with the curricula of HEIs.

5.0 Competencies in Dutch organisations

5.1 Introduction

It is important to understand what business organisations require and what HEIs offer in order to judge the extent of their alignment. To obtain this information, the field research regarding the competencies in HEIs is therefore followed by research aimed at obtaining the perspective of Dutch business organisations regarding competencies. This research is Phase three and was executed using input from the theoretical framework and input from the results of the interviews with HEI representatives. This helped structuring the research approach, developing the questionnaire for the survey and realising an in-depth study regarding the required competencies in Dutch organisations and their view regarding alignment with HEIs in the Netherlands.

5.2 Presentation of research results and analysis

5.2.1 Research execution versus planning

This section describes why the target group of the survey has changed. The differences between the plan and how the survey was executed was placed in this part of the thesis to explain the changes and to be able to link it with the response and the coding. The plan was to send the survey to all DNHK-members as described in section 3.4.2. The slight deviation was caused by a sudden lack of support for this research within the DNHK organisation. The DNHK initiated a plan to develop and send their own survey. As a result, they concluded that this research could interfere with the expected response rate of their own survey. This is why priority was given to the own survey and the support to this research was limited. The planned letter to the DNHK-members to inform them about the research project was not sent. The other planned steps, as described in section 3.4.2, did not take place either. Due to these discussions between the researcher and the DNHK, the planning was delayed. The first step regarding the promotion of the survey had to start mid-January 2017. The researcher had to plan a survey start (Go Live) after the summer holiday period of 2017. Due to the new situation, the survey was made available at the 12th of September 2017. The DNHK-members were made aware of the survey in the newsletter "FACT" on the 5th of October 2017. This newsletter was sent to all DNHK-members. In this newsletter, another survey was promoted too, possibly resulting in less attention for this research project. The appeal to repeat the request to participate in the research in another FACT-newsletter was not granted. The other actions to promote the survey as described in section 3.4.2 were not executed as planned by the DNHK and no other activities were allowed. The promotion activities regarding the survey resulted in a response of 72. Two of them were incomplete, which leaves 70 usable questionnaires by the end of October 2017. The aim to

obtain a response of 22,8% or 297 usable returns was not reached within the planned response period.

The researcher therefore had to find other ways to increase the response. The best way to increase response was to involve a panel from an external market research organisation, which meant that all Dutch organisations would be in scope of this research. Although the original intention was different, getting away from Dutch-German business environment is a strength. The negative point of not being able to focus on Dutch organisations doing business with Germany was more than compensated by putting all Dutch organisations in focus. Approval for this action was sought and received in October 2017 from the University of the West of Scotland. The conditions for approval were that the researcher is the designer of the questionnaire and is also the decision maker and scholar behind the planning of the administration of the survey. The change of the sampling frame from all members of the DNHK (Dutch German Chamber of Commerce) to all business organisations in the Netherlands made the research even more robust. This new population increases the chance to improve external validity or generalisability. The findings are more likely to be applicable to all business organisations in the Netherlands. The requirements regarding the new population, such as the focus on senior management, are the same as the initial cooperation with the DNHK.

After this approval by UWS, a cooperation was setup with Survey Sampling International (SSI), a global provider of data solutions and technology for consumer and business to business research. SSI reaches participants in more than 90 countries via internet, telephone, wireless and mixed-access offerings and has staff in 20 countries. Services offered include sampling, data collection and computer-assisted telephone interviewing (CATI) (Survey Sampling International 2017). Contact was made with SSI in the Netherlands, they have a Business-to-Business (B2B) database available that can be used for gaining response (Survey Sampling International LLC 2018). Based upon the aim of the study and the existing questionnaire the researcher gave the following instructions to SSI:

1. Select participants in organisations from 2 until more than 100,000 employees in the Netherlands. The aim of the questionnaire is to obtain the view of Higher Management regarding the required competencies of their middle management. As a result, the targeted organisations have to have employees, preferably with middle management positions.
2. Select the following roles in organisations:
 - a. Owner/ partner/ CEO/ CFO/ COO/ CIO
 - b. HR Director/ HR Manager

- c. Finance Director/ Senior Finance Manager
- d. Sales Director/ Sales Manager
- e. IT Director/ Senior IT Manager
- f. Marketing Director/ Marketing Manager

Limitation: a maximum of 1 participant per organisation has to be set.

3. Make no selection based upon sector: all sorts of organisations may do business in Germany.

The advantage of setting up this cooperation was that response could be realised in a relatively short period of time. The moment the survey was made available to the panel, surveys were completed and the aim to obtain a minimum of 383 usable surveys could be reached, as described in section 3.4.2. From an ethical point of view, there were no major changes; by completing the online survey, it was understood that the participant had consented to participate in the study. From this moment, all data gathered were anonymous during the research period.

5.2.2 Research response

The survey was made available to the members of the SSI-panel on the 13th of November 2017. In a period of three days 328 responses were gathered. The researcher already obtained 72 surveys before this cooperation, which brings the total response of the survey on 400, of which 8 were rejected due to being incomplete. Finally, 392 responses were defined as being complete and usable.

The aim was to obtain a response of 297 usable returns from the DNHK population. This was based upon a confidence interval of 95% and a confidence level of 5%. The population has changed from the DNHK-members to all organisations in the Netherlands. With this new population, it was not possible to select organisations that are doing business and/ or have done business in Germany, which was the original aim. This problem was covered by adding a question to the questionnaire where the participant was asked to provide an answer to the question if his organisation does or has done business with Germany. Despite the plan to select only organisations with two or more employees, 6% of the responses came from organisations with one employee. After checking the profiles of the participants, the researcher decided to keep the data for analysis. The reason was that some of the participants work in the education sector and others have for example a consultancy role, and therefore might have a good perspective on the research topic. Most of them gave answers to the open-ended questions.

The total number of organisations in the Netherlands (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek 2017), was 1,581,740, in 2016. The number of freelancers, who are not included in the population for this research, was 1,000,815 in 2016. Deducting Freelancers from the total number of organisations in the Netherlands provides a population of 580,925 organisations. Using a confidence interval of 95% and a confidence level of 5%, the sample size results in 384. This result is in line with the sample size calculation as described in section 3.4.2. The obtained response of 392 is above the required 384. Based upon an unknown population of 20.000 and a confidence interval of 95% the confidence level is 4,90%. In section 5.2.4 the researcher verified how many participants are doing business and/ or have done business with Germany and how this affected the reliability when looking at the business between the two countries.

The main focus of the research project was on the competencies in the BBA-curriculum; all competencies are compared with each other. For this reason, the researcher used Cronbach's Alpha to measure the reliability of the survey and the split-half method (Field 2018) to analyse the internal consistency of questions related to the 14 competences in the survey. Cronbach's Alpha is mostly used when multiple questions such as Likert-scales are applied in the survey. This method helped indicating if the scores were reliable by measuring the different variables. The split-half method helped measuring internal consistency by correlating one half of the data-set with the other half, again using Cronbach's Alpha. This analysis was done by focusing on the 14 competencies and the questions asked regarding the importance of each competency and the satisfaction level per competency. The respondents were asked to rate the importance and the satisfaction per competency, using a Likert-scale. SPSS™ was used for both methods.

The results show that the data are reliable, the Cronbach's Alpha calculations can be found in Appendix 9. The score regarding the importance of the 14 competencies is 0.898 and the score regarding the satisfaction regarding the 14 competencies is 0.911. The question is if this reliability stays on this level when diving deeper in the results. For this reason, the researcher used the split-half method, which also provides an indication regarding reliability by looking at internal consistency by splitting the total set of variables in two groups. The split-half method is used by dividing the 14 questions in two groups of seven questions and thus analysed the Cronbach's Alpha. This was done for the 14 questions regarding importance as well as the 14 questions regarding satisfaction. The Cronbach's Alpha for the split-half regarding importance are 0.853 for part one and 0.817 for part two. These scores indicate that both parts are reliable. Cronbach's Alpha for the split-half regarding satisfaction

are 0.851 for Part one and 0.840 for Part two. These scores also indicate that the results remain reliable when using the split-half method.

5.2.3 Coding research data

Participants quotes that were used in the following section were coded by using the “B” for business organisations and using the sequential order of the SPSS database; e.g. “B1” represents the answers of the first participant and B392 represents the answers of the last participant.

The 38 closed-ended questions were coded in line with the answer options. The 6 open-ended questions were coded according to the following methods.

Question five and six: job title and other responsibilities

The participants were asked in question five to provide their job title and to add other possible responsibilities in their daily work via question six. Both questions are open-ended questions. First, all responses to question five were identified and grouped in another column with comparable titles, such as “sales manager”. In the next column, these results were put in function groups within an organisation, such as “sales management”. The next step involved the input from question six, which had the aim to receive input regarding the areas of responsibility of the participant. The main aim of this question was to check the role of the participant. By combining the answers given to questions five and six, the correct role in the organisation was identified.

The defined groups in the organisation are based upon management responsibilities and functional roles. The following groups were made:

1. Top Management: existing of job titles such as CEO, COO and CFO
2. Sales Management: with job titles such as Key Account Manager and Sales Manager
3. Financial Management: with job titles such as Manager Finance and Control.
4. HRM: with job titles such as Manager HRM
5. ICT Management: with job titles such as Manager IT
6. Marketing Management: with job titles such as Manager Public Relations and Marketing Manager
7. Programme and Project Management: with job titles such as Project Manager
8. Procurement and Purchasing Management: with job titles such as Procurement Manager
9. Logistics Management: with job titles such as Logistics Manager

10. Facility and Support Management: with job titles such as programme Manager or Project Manager
11. Rest: i.e. quality management, consultancy and undefined job titles

Some job titles given to question five are very specific, such as “adviseur bedrijven” (company advisor). These responses were coded using the answers to question six regarding responsibilities. If the participant for example answered “sales” as the area of responsibility, the role was coded as “sales management”. This approach was successful for many participants. Due to insufficient data, the job titles of 50 participants could not be identified and were put in the group “Rest”.

Question 12: motivation regarding answer awareness required competencies

This question contains the motivation of the participant for the answer given in question 11, where they were asked for their opinion regarding the question in what way the HEIs are aware of the required competencies in an international business environment.

The results regarding question 12 were coded and analysed in two ways. First, the motivation for the given answer was coded in three groups: positive, neutral and negative. This was done to be able to perform a more detailed analysis of the views of the participants and the motivation they have given. The results of this coding were visualised in a pie-diagram.

Second, all answers that gave a usable qualitative motivation were set aside from the answers that could not be identified as a usable motivation for the answer given to question 11. Thereafter, all usable answers were read and the comparable answers were grouped in topics such as “customer orientation” and “communication”. These topics were grouped by using the SERVQUAL Model as described in Section 2.4.8 and used in the report. An overview of all groups can be found in the next section.

Question 27: missing knowledge, skills, attitudes and/or behavioural aspects

Here the participants were to provide competencies or specific areas that, according to their opinion, are not covered by the 14 earlier assessed importance of the competencies belonging to the BBA curriculum.

First, all responses were classified in usable and non-usable answers and written in another column. Then usable and comparable answers were grouped in topics. Usable answers are answers that contain content, such as “resilience” and “motivation” while not usable answers are for example “not” and “not applicable”. The topics ranged from “none” which can be related to responses that indicated that the 14 competencies are sufficient, to personality

aspects such as “self-analysis and self-reflection”. The second round of coding was done using the six levels of the Iceberg model as described in Section 2.4.2.

Question 43: motivation regarding answer focus on knowledge or skills

This question contains the motivation for the answer given in question 42, where the participants were asked for their opinion regarding the question where the HEIs should put their focus on in the upcoming years: knowledge or skills development. First, all responses were classified in usable and non-usable answers and transferred to another column. Then usable and comparable answers were grouped in topics based upon the preference knowledge or skills. Finally, two more groups were added; one group covering the responses that state that both are important and another group which covers general remarks.

Question 44: suggestions or recommendations

This was the last question of the survey. Here the participants had the possibility to give suggestions and/ or recommendations. First, all responses were classified in usable and non-usable answers and written in another column. Then usable and comparable answers were grouped in topics based upon similarity and frequency; for example, practice is a recurrent theme in the responses due to the fact that many participants stressed the importance of practice experience for students.

5.2.4 Research results and data analysis survey

The survey setup was divided into two parts. In the first part, general questions had to be answered, such as the role of the participant in the organisation and more specific questions regarding contact with and their view regarding HEIs. The second part consists of the questions regarding the 14 competencies in the BBA curriculum and related questions referring to competencies.

One of the questions in Part one of the survey deals with the size of the organisations of the participant. This question is important because the researcher wanted to obtain data on which competencies are important for middle managers. This is why organisations with many employees are important, as they are expected to have middle management positions and it also explains the decision to define organisations without employees initially as out of scope. Furthermore, it is important to be able to generalise the results of the study towards the population: all Dutch business organisations. The survey sample must therefore be representative. Results of the survey in the first part are compared with national data. This was done regarding the size of the organisation and the sectors where the organisations are active.

Figure 5.1: Univariate analysis of the organisation sizes of the participants, depicted by researcher (n=392).

The participants represent different sizes of organisations when looking at the number of employees. Compared with the figures provided by CBS, the Dutch abbreviation for Bureau for Statistics in the Netherlands (Centraal Bureau voor de Statistiek 2017) the following comparison can be made regarding registered organisations in the Netherlands segmented by the number of employees.

Data survey vs. national CBS data (retrieved 2017)	Frequency survey	Percent survey	Netherlands 2016
One employee	25	6%	78%
2 to 10 employees	71	18%	18%
10 to 50 employees	88	22%	3%
50 to 250 employees	102	26%	1%
250 or more employees	106	27%	0%
Total	392	100%	100%

Table 5.1: Comparison of national data employees per organisation versus survey data, depicted by researcher.

The representation of two to ten employees within the survey results is similar to the national percentage, which is also 18% when considering the overall division. All other segments in the survey differ from the national Dutch statistics. Using the CBS segmentation of organisations as a reference, there are more participants from larger organisations in the survey compared with the national data. Assuming that higher management in larger organisations have a better perspective regarding the requirements of middle managers, the reliability of the research is thus enhanced.

In addition to the size of the organisation, it is also important to have a look at the different sectors of the participants. To what extent can the survey results regarding sectors be compared to the national division and what does this say about reliability. The following pie chart provides an overview of the participants per sector.

Figure 5.2: Univariate analysis of the response per sector (n=392)

The participants of the survey cover a lot of different sectors. Consultancy & Research, Information & Communication and Finance form the largest groups of survey participants. The external validity of the survey results is compared to the targeted population so that conclusions can be drawn that say something about the total population. The comparison entails the results of the survey versus the weight of sectors in the Netherlands: the overall division of all sectors in the Dutch economy. Table 5.2 underneath shows this comparison.

Sector comparison response vs. National				the Netherlands, CBS Statline
				Data per 31.12.2016
				1581740
Sectors	National	Survey	Delta	Analysis
A Agriculture	4,7%	2,8%	-40%	Relatively equal (difference <200%)
B Mineral resources	0,0%	0,8%	> 1000%	Low numbers
C Industry	3,8%	9,4%	144%	More organisationswith >50 employees
D Production and distribution of energy	0,1%	3,1%	> 1000%	Low numbers
E Water treatment and distribution	0,1%	0,8%	693%	Low numbers
F Building and construction	9,9%	3,8%	-61%	No explanation
G Wholesale	14,2%	7,9%	-45%	More organisationswith >50 employees
H Transport	2,5%	3,6%	47%	Relatively equal (difference <200%)
I Hotel and other lodging	3,4%	3,1%	-8%	Relatively equal (difference <100%)
J Information and communication	5,3%	10,2%	92%	No explanation
K Finance	5,4%	9,7%	80%	Relatively equal (difference <200%)
L Real estate	1,6%	0,5%	-68%	Low numbers
M Consultancy and research	19,7%	10,2%	-48%	More organisationswith >50 employees
N Rental of goods	4,1%	1,3%	-69%	More organisationswith >50 employees
O Public administration	0,0%	2,3%	> 1000%	Low numbers
P Education	4,5%	7,9%	76%	Relatively equal (difference <200%)
Q Health	8,6%	4,6%	-47%	Relatively equal (difference <100%)
R Culture and sports	6,1%	5,4%	-11%	Relatively equal (difference <100%)
S Other services	6,1%	10,2%	68%	No explanation
T Households as employer	0,0%	1,3%	> 1000%	No explanation
U Extraterritorial	0,0%	1,3%	> 1000%	More organisationswith >50 employees

Table 5.2: Response sector comparison, depicted by researcher.

The division of the response of the survey per sector is relatively in par with national data. Some sectors have a very low representation in both the national figures as in the survey, such as the sector “Mineral Resources”. The relatively higher number of organisations from the industry can be explained by the low number of organisations with 1 employee in the survey and the high number in the national figures, and strengthens the validity of the research results. The wholesale, consultancy and research and rental of goods sectors have a relatively low representation in the response. It is assumed that this is probably due to the same reason.

Figure 5.3: Univariate analysis of the response per role in organisation, depicted by researcher (n=392)

Some other differences, such as the “information and communication” sector cannot be explained without further investigation. In general, this means that the survey results can be generalised to the population.

The answers given by participants regarding their role were coded and clustered in groups. The largest group that was defined (27%) is “Top Management”. This group consists of participants with roles like CEO, CFO or CIO. The largest group in the graph is the group “Other”, which contains all roles that have a percentage lower than 5%. Examples are roles in marketing management, program and project management, procurement and purchasing management and logistics management. This group also contains the freelancers and participants who did not explain their role and therefore cannot be placed in a specific group. Assuming that top management and other senior positions have experience with middle management, the analysis shows that the participants are likely to have a good perspective on the topic. Most participants have a (senior) management role and consequently it is probable that they have experience with middle management roles as earlier described.

Due to the change in the sample-frame, one question was added to the survey. The question of whether the participant has done business with Germany was asked in order to identify participants with and without experience in doing business with this country and to analyse if there are differences between the two groups regarding their perspectives on competencies. Attached to this question, further clarification was given in the survey by indicating that “doing business” concerns responsibility areas like purchasing, sales, or other forms of cooperation. The kind of business was not asked.

Figure 5.4: Univariate analysis of doing business with Germany, depicted by researcher (n=392)

More than half (55%) of the participants, answered positively when asked whether they have done or are doing business with Germany. Due to the change in population, as described in Section 4.3.1, there are now also participants that are not active in this country. The number of organisations that do business with Germany and participated in the survey is analysed. When looking at the response, the number of companies that have done or are doing business with Germany is 55%. The reliability is high when looking at the total sample with $n=392$, and less reliable when looking at the participants that have indicated doing business with Germany based upon $n=215$. If the researcher decided to use the latter, the confidence level would increase to 6,65%. This is based upon an unknown population of 20,000 and a confidence interval of 95%. The extent to which the sample mean can fluctuate with this sample size due to random sampling is therefore higher than the planned 5%. Combining this figure with the fact that many participants have high positions in their organisations, the researcher assumes that the participants are able to provide valuable input regarding the needed competencies of their middle managers.

To verify this in another way, the researcher compared the size of the organisations doing business with Germany to those not doing business with Germany. As described earlier, analysing the participants regarding the size of their organisations proved to add value to the reliability. Figure number 5.5 shows the division between large and smaller companies looking at the number of employees versus doing business with Germany.

Figure 5.5: Bi-variate analysis number of employees versus doing business in Germany, depicted by researcher ($n=392$)

The group of organisations with 50 to 250 employees has the largest percentage of companies that do business with Germany: 18% out of 26%. This means that almost 70% of these medium-sized companies is active in Germany. In comparison, the group with 250 or more employees has the lowest score when looking at having done or doing business with Germany. Combining the relatively higher representation of this group in the survey sample with their relative low level of doing business, there could be more organisations that do business with Germany in the Netherlands than is shown in this survey sample. The researcher is aware of the influence that the higher representation of this group can have regarding the other results of the survey. The reason for the lower score of the 250 and more employees group is not clear. Combining the results from the last two figures, the researcher considered all responses in the survey as usable and didn't make a difference based upon whether the participant has done or is doing business with Germany.

This research project aims at analysing the current alignment between HEIs and business organisations regarding competencies. Contact is an important factor for alignment; without communication, regardless of the form, alignment is not possible. As stated at the start of this section, alignment can only be successful when key-stakeholders are aware of each other actions and requirements. The researcher has therefore investigated the status quo regarding the contact frequency.

Figure 5.6: Uni-variate analysis contacts with HEI, depicted by researcher (n=392)

The contact frequency with an institute in higher education is reflected in the pie above. One fifth of all survey participants indicated having no contact at all and approximately one third have a contact moment once a year. This shows that 55% are in contact with a HEI once a year or less. What frequency (and quality of the contact) is needed to be able to interact in

such a way that the HEI has a clear understanding regarding the needs of organisations was not investigated.

Having asked the frequency of contacts, the next question asked for the reason for this contact or for these contacts. The participants had the opportunity to give multiple answers.

The options were:

1. Internships;
2. Incidental contacts, such as giving a guest lecture;
3. Teaching role;
4. Recruiting graduates;
5. Participation in Advisory Board;
6. Other

The participants who indicated not having any contact with HEIs were asked to skip this question and go to the next question.

Figure 5.7: Uni-variate analysis contact regarding participation in advisory boards, depicted by researcher (n=392)

Figure 5.8: Uni-variate analysis contact regarding apprentices, depicted by researcher (n=392)

Figure 5.7 shows that less than 1% have contact with a HEI in the form of participation in an advisory board, which means that only 1, 2 or 3 participants are or have any experience participating in an advisory board. This is not a surprise looking at the number of participants in advisory boards as described in section 4.2.2.

The second pie (figure 5.8) shows the results regarding having contacts for the purpose of hiring apprentices, which has almost a 50/50 division. The added value of an internship or apprenticeship is evident according to one of the participants (B145): *“If you do an internship, you learn what the required competencies are and you also learn to apply them.”* This sort of contact has the highest score of all contact forms. Nevertheless, almost half does not have any contact with a HEI regarding apprentices. When extrapolating this to all Dutch

organisations, it means that almost half of all Dutch organisations never look for new apprentices within HEIs. It is unclear whether this is due to the absence of apprentice-positions or whether they look somewhere else.

Incidental contacts, such as a guest lecture, was another option regarding how organisations may have contact with an HEI. Here the results show that approximately a quarter perform guest lectures at HEIs. The majority of the organisations (77%) do not have this kind of contact or other forms of incidental contacts. Teaching roles are the second least used way of having contact with a HEI after taking part in an Advisory Board. A large majority (83%) does not use this method. The interaction between the two stakeholders is mostly based upon the exchange of practical experience. One participant stated (B37): *“We present and share our practical experiences with students that almost graduate”*. This can be done as a guest lecture and as a teacher.

Figure 5.9: Uni-variate analysis contact regarding guest lectures, depicted by researcher (n=392)

Figure 5.10: Uni-variate analysis contact in a teaching role, depicted by researcher (n=392)

There are less contacts with the aim to recruit graduates compared to contacts with the aim to recruit apprenticeships. Two thirds of all participants indicate that they do not have contact with HEIs for this purpose. The difference with contact regarding apprenticeships is remarkable, as graduates provide an immediate benefit by fulfilling job positions for the long term, while apprenticeships do not. Despite this fact, more participants have indicated having contact regarding apprenticeships (53%) than those having contact for the benefit of recruiting new employees (33%).

Figure 5.11: Uni-variate analysis contact regarding graduates, depicted by researcher (n=392)

Figure 5.12: Uni-variate analysis other forms of contact, depicted by researcher (n=392)

Comparing the six options, one might assume that participating in an advisory board is the best option when looking at adding value to alignment between HEIs and business organisations. This option is, however, not used very often.

If none of the above options fit the description how the survey participants have contact with HEIs, they could add their personal role with the option: "other". The researcher wanted to find out if the participants who indicated having other forms of contacts add relevant information to the question of how contacts are organised. One quarter of all participants indicated having other roles and 14 specified what kind of contact.

This resulted in the following roles related to contact with HEIs. These roles can be extra or the only way of having contact with HEIs. The other roles within HEIs in the Netherlands are:

- Advisory board jobs technical business administration;
- Helping to develop new ideas;
- Help guarding alignment with job market;
- Member of several university advisory boards
- Making promotion movies, etc.;
- Advisory board;
- Programme management;
- Advisory board and exam commission;
- Consultant, lecturer;
- Exam commission;
- Works council;
- Employees;
- Conservator;

- E-commerce role.

Some of the roles above can be defined as external or commercial and do not seem to have an effect on alignment, such as “making promotion videos for HEIs”. Other roles can be identified as internal i.e. “employees”. The low number of having the role of employee does not affect the reliability of the results. There are also responses that can be added to the earlier options, such as advisory board member and lecturer. Adding the response frequencies to the number of participants with i.e. a role in advisory board does not really change the former described results.

Summarising how organisations indicated to be in contact with one or more HEIs, the conclusion can be made that the contact percentages vary per method (graduates, teaching role, etc.) from 53% to 17%. As shown in an earlier graph, 21% of all participants are never in contact with an HEI. The organisations that do have contact with HEIs do this with a relatively low frequency. There is a potential risk regarding the validity of the results of these questions. The participants might be unaware of the activities of colleagues in their own organisation regarding these contact possibilities. On the other hand, as most of the participants are senior management, the assumption can be made that they have or at least should have a relative good view on what is happening in their organisation.

Despite this risk, the results show that from a quantitative perspective the alignment between HEIs and organisations is not supported by a high percentage of organisations that are communicating frequently one way or another with higher education institutes. The quality aspects of these contacts have not been researched.

The question regarding employment of BBA-degree holders shows a two-third versus one-third division. Most organisations (66%) reported having employees with a BBA degree. It is unclear whether the participants that indicated “No” have experience with employees with an BBA degree and, more importantly, know which competencies are important for them when working in an international environment. This question was not asked, and could have increased the reliability.

Figure 5.13: Uni-variate analysis employees with a BBA-degree, depicted by researcher (n=392)

Regarding the number of participants (34%) that indicated that there are no employees with a BBA degree in their organisation, the researcher nevertheless assumes that these participants do have enough knowledge of the required competencies for their middle management, have a vision regarding alignment with HEIs, and thus do add value in this survey.

It is unclear whether the participants had their middle management in an international environment in mind when answering the question regarding the awareness of HEIs. There is a chance that a certain percentage thought about general alignment between HEIs and employee requirements and did not think about their middle management. This would certainly be the case when the organisation of the participant does not have middle management positions, or when the participant does not think his or her organisation has them. An extra question asking if the organisation has middle management positions could have helped to increase the validity. Although this helps to make sure middle management is present in the organisation of the participant, it does not guarantee the perspective of the participant when answering this question. It would still be possible to think about general alignment instead of alignment regarding middle management.

Figure 5.14: Uni-variate analysis HEI-awareness, depicted by researcher (n=392)

The awareness of HEIs regarding the requirements for future middle management is considered to be “not good or bad” by almost half (45%) of the participants. Around 40% are of the opinion that the awareness is “good”, while 9% consider the awareness as “bad”. The general perspective seems to be more positive than negative: 43% “good” and “very good” versus 12% “bad” and “very bad”.

As the “not good or bad” group is rather high, the researcher analysed these responses in more detail. The participants were given the opportunity to specify a motivation for their answer in the next open-ended question. One participant indicated the complexity, as according to him there are differences (B2):

It is not good or bad, it differs per college and employee/ contact person and there is no direct link to "desired competencies for your future middle management" with trainees, etc.

Many participants provided an explanation for their choice. Of the total number of 175 participants who gave a “not good or bad” response, 99 did not give extra information. However, the other 76 participants (43%) did provide a motivation for their choice. The researcher analysed the provided qualitative answers of the “not good or bad” group by categorising them into three groups: positive, neutral or negative. Almost none of the 76 answers were positive, less than half were neutral and the majority was negative. The negative motivation was found by looking at words such as: “can be better”, “is low”, “too much”, etc.

Figure 5.15: Uni-variate analysis "not good or bad" answers, depicted by researcher (n=76).

Looking at these results, the initial results regarding the awareness based has to be reconsidered. Assuming that 58% of the 45% score in "not good or bad" can also be included into the "bad" group, this results in another split between good and bad; 43% are now "good" and "very good", 19% are "not good or bad" and 38% are "bad" and "very bad". This calculation does not take into account the opinions of the participants who have not provided motivation for their choice for "not good or bad". One participant described the awareness of HEIs regarding competencies like this (B15): *"A lot is still unclear on which competencies should be developed, despite some experienced teachers."*

The effect of this extra analysis is that the score is more evenly divided and that 38% of all participants state that HEIs do not know which competencies are needed and do not know what organisations need when looking at their future employees. The reason why the participants have chosen to be neutral and still give a negative qualitative comment is unclear. It shows that more details are necessary to be able to achieve a clear view regarding the satisfaction of the organisations on the one hand and the exact reasons why they are satisfied or dissatisfied.

Analysing HEI awareness further, the researcher compared several variables with awareness results. The first comparison is between the size of the organisation regarding the number of employees and HEI-awareness. Although the differences are small, it seems that smaller organisations seem to be less positive than larger organisations. The graph regarding this comparison can be found in Appendix 10, figure 10.2.

When comparing the frequency of contact with the results regarding awareness, the conclusion can be drawn that the participants who have the least contact with HEIs evaluate

their awareness as lower than participants with a higher contact frequency. This indicates that there seems to be a relationship between the contact frequency and the opinion regarding awareness. The graph regarding this comparison can be found in Appendix 10, figure 10.1.

Crossing the results regarding the awareness of required competencies with the organisations that do/ did or do/ did not do business with Germany shows that the organisations who have done or are doing business with Germany are more positive than those who do not when looking at the choice “good”. Doing business with Germany seems to influence the judgement regarding the question if HEIs are aware of the required competencies. The results regarding “Not good or bad” are the other way around; here the companies who have not done business /are not doing business with Germany have a relatively high score. These organisations seem to be more careful regarding this topic. Other differences cannot be identified based upon these results. The graph regarding this comparison can be found in Appendix 10, figure 10.3.

Comparing the employment of someone in the organisation with a BBA degree with the answers regarding the question of the awareness of HEIs regarding required competencies shows that participants from organisations with BBA graduates tend to think more positively about the awareness than employers without BBA graduates. The graph regarding this comparison can be found in Appendix 10, figure 10.4.

Assessing the responses regarding awareness with gender did not lead to any major differences or surprises. In total, 107 women completed the survey and 285 men, leading to a division of 27% and 73%. The graph regarding this comparison can be found in Appendix 10, figure 10.5. However, comparing HEI awareness with the age of the participants, there seems to be a correlation between age and the view regarding HEI awareness.

Figure 5.16: Bi-variate analysis HEI-awareness versus age of respondents, depicted by researcher (n=392)

The group of participants up to 30 years of age shows an increase regarding the question of whether HEIs are aware when looking at the range from “very bad” to “very good”. Except for the “very good” part, the number of participants increases with each step from “very bad”, “bad”, “not good or bad” until “good”. The group between 30 and 40 years of age show a similar positive pattern, including the remarkable point that 46% in this group have the opinion that the awareness of HEIs is very good. The participants that are beyond the age of 59 show the opposite, with a large number (46%) of participants who are very unhappy with the awareness. Almost two thirds (60%) find the awareness “bad” or “very bad”. The reason for this relation between age and awareness has not been investigated.

When comparing the awareness with roles in the organisations, there seems to be another correlation. The participants with a more critical view regarding the awareness of HEIs do not only have a higher age but have top-management positions. Figure 5.17 shows the division of the answers given regarding awareness; i.e. of all participants who chose that the awareness of HEIs is “very bad” 50% comes from the Top management cluster. In total, 44% of all “bad” voters also come from this group.

Figure 5.17: Bi-variate analysis HEI-awareness versus role of respondents, depicted by researcher (n=392)

Of all participants, 28% belong to this “Top management” group. Assuming that age and a top management position can go hand in hand with a more experienced participant, this group seems to have a more critical view regarding the awareness of HEIs than the younger participants. The combination of age, experience and a top position in organisations seems to negatively influence the perspective on HEIs regarding their awareness. One CEO described it as follows (B49):

HEIs do not have enough “feeling” regarding market demands. Learning programmes are insufficiently aligned with practice and do not include enough trends, such as organisational issues with which companies experiment. A little bit of attention is paid to the development of personal skills. However, with a moderate quality.

The second part of the survey contains the assessment of the competencies in the BBA curriculum. The participant was asked to give his or her opinion regarding the described competencies, starting by indicating how important each competency is. The response can vary from “totally not important” with a score “1” until “extremely important” with a score “5”. The scale in the following figures is considered by the researcher to be interval. The rationale behind this is that the researcher assumes a normal distribution; the intervals between the scale values are treated as equal. This results in an interval scale that can be used for parametric tests.

Figure 5.18: Mean per competency regarding importance, depicted by researcher (n=392)

The assessment of the importance of all competencies is included in Figure 5.18. The score varies from 3.37 to 3.95. The scores are clustered; there are no remarkable low or high scores. The highest score is achieved by the competency “communication”, which is approximately 17% higher than 3.37, which are the scores for “act methodically”. The competencies “cooperate/ networking”, “communication” and “act responsible” have remarkable results, as the scores for “extremely important” are relatively very high. The results per competency will not be shown in a graph because the results do not differ very much.

The other question that was included for every competency in the survey is the satisfaction level. The question was asked to what extent the participant believes that the 14 competencies are sufficiently completed during the bachelor programme. Satisfaction in this survey refers to what the students have learned and if the participants think that the average graduate has sufficient knowledge, skills, etc. The response could vary from “very

dissatisfied” with a score “1” until “very satisfied” with a score “5”. With five options, the scores could range from 1 to 5.

Figure 5.19: Mean per competency regarding satisfaction, depicted by researcher (n=392)

The scores regarding the satisfaction per competency do not vary too much (Figure 5.19); the maximum score is 3.44 and the minimum score 3.17, which gives a difference of almost 9%. The results per competency will not be shown in a graph because the results do not differ very much.

The next step is to compare the scores regarding the importance and the satisfaction level per competency and identify possible relationships. Looking at the standard deviations of both ranges (14 competencies assessed regarding importance and 14 regarding satisfaction), the conclusion can be made that both do not exceed 1.0. The results are closely clustered around the mean value, which is in the “not good or bad” answer option. This could mean that the participants are really of the opinion that it is not good or bad or that they found it difficult to judge the competencies.

The scores regarding the importance of each competency vary from 0.842 for competency one being the lowest standard deviation until 0.996 for competency six with the highest score. The results of the assessments of the satisfaction level per competency vary from 0.820 for competency one as the lowest score and 0.970 for competency six as the highest score. When put in a scatter diagram, this conclusion can be visually confirmed as can be seen in figure 5.21 and figure 5.22. The importance and satisfaction scores are all close to each other.

Because the results are all clustered around the mean, the researcher wanted to find out if relationships can be found between the scores regarding the importance of each competency and the satisfaction level. For this reason, the Pearson Correlation test (Field 2018) was executed using SPSS™, using 99% as the starting confidence level. The decision rule for assessing if there is a significant correlation is as follows:

- If $p \leq 0.01$, it means that there is a significant relation between the importance of the competency and the satisfaction level of that same competency.
- If $p > 0.01$, it means that there is no significant relation between the importance of the competency and the satisfaction level of that same competency.

When comparing all competencies on an individual level, the result shows that there is a significant correlation between the perceived importance and significance for all except two of the 14 competencies. The results of the Pearson Correlation test for 12 competencies shows a p -value less than 0.0005, or $p < 0.001$; the two variables are negatively linearly related. However, for competency two and competency six, the p -value is higher than 0.0005; namely 0.024 and 0.080. Competency two is the ability to connect and competency six deals with communication. An explanation for these two exceptions has not been found. The calculation regarding the Pearson Correlation test can be found in Appendix 9.

With the results in graph form, the differences between the importance results and those regarding the satisfaction levels per competency become clear. Figure 5.20 shows the mean per competency for both importance and satisfaction scores; Table 5.3 explains which number represents which competency in the BBA-curriculum.

No.	BBA competencies		
1.	Acting methodically	10.	Organisation sensitivity
2.	Ability to connect	11.	Analysis Skills
3.	Advise	12.	Process Management
4.	Innovation	13.	Change Management
5.	Cooperation / networking	14.	Research Skills
6.	Communication		
7.	Act responsibly		
8.	Act professionally		
9.	ICT knowledge and skills		

Table 5.3: Numbered 14 competencies, depicted by researcher.

Except for one competency, the participants value the importance higher than the satisfaction. The competency ICT-Skills has a comparable mean score in both assessments, with a slightly higher score regarding the satisfaction; 3.41 for importance and 3.43 for satisfaction. The median is 3.0 and separates the data in two parts.

Figure 5.20: Bi-variate analysis importance and satisfaction of 14 competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392).

The scatter diagram in figure 5.21, prove once again that the results are clustered.

Figure 5.21: Bi-variate analysis importance and satisfaction of 14 competencies in scatter diagram, depicted by researcher (n=392).

Zooming in on the results, the differences between the competencies become clearer. The competency communication is relatively high positioned, but there are no significant differences, as described earlier.

Figure 5.22: Bi-variate analysis of importance and satisfaction of 14 competencies zooming in on scatter diagram, depicted by researcher (n=392).

This method of presenting the survey results did not lead to any remarkable conclusions. Another way of analysing the combination of assessing the competencies was sought and found. The results were visualised with the purpose of providing a clearer view regarding the fact that the results regarding importance are almost all higher than the results regarding satisfaction. Translating the scale used in the survey into satisfaction levels, five levels can be identified. The division of the five levels is as follows:

1. Very dissatisfied
2. Dissatisfied
3. Not satisfied or dissatisfied
4. Satisfied
5. Very satisfied

As stated earlier, the scale is considered to be interval. The rationale behind this is that the intervals between the scale values are treated as equal. Each step has a range of 0.8 points on the continuum between 1 and 5. This is based upon the following calculation: the range between 1 and 5 gives 4, divided by 5 is 0.8. Figure 5.23 shows the dispersion of the results against these 5 satisfaction levels. The largest part of the scores can be found in the “Not satisfied or dissatisfied” section, which varies from 2.6 to 3.4 and is centred around the

median 3.0 that divides satisfied and not satisfied. The competencies that fall into the satisfied area ranging from 3.4 until 4.2 are “Analysis Skills” with 3.40, “Act Professionally” with 3.42 and “ICT Knowledge and Skills” with 3.44.

Figure 5.23: Bi-variate analysis satisfaction levels of 14 competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392).

The concentration of all responses just above the median may have two causes. The first possibility is that the participants found it hard to assess the competencies due to the provided definitions and the necessary connection of the competency in their own working environment. The definition used in the BBA curriculum might be too abstract and/ or theoretical for the participant. If the competency description does not spark a recognisable setting of the participant it is difficult to assess this specific competency. The research results regarding the awareness of HEIs confirm this theory; further analysis of the “not good or bad” response indicated that most participants were more negative than positive.

Another possibility is the earlier described average completion time of the survey. Although it cannot be proved in a conclusive way, the risk is that participants clicked on the middle answers of the 1 to 5 Likert scale without reading the questions and/or answers properly and were rushing to finish as quickly as possible.

When looking at the scores from the perspective of the importance of each competency, the results are a bit different (Figure 5.24). The response possibilities are also based upon the 5-point scale. As in the former overview with the satisfaction perspective, the lowest score is 1.0 and the highest is 5.0. Translating this scale to the levels of importance, five levels can be identified. The division of the 5 levels is as follows:

1. Totally not important
2. Not very important
3. Moderately important
4. Very important
5. Extremely important

Figure 5.24: Bi-variate analysis importance levels of 14 competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392).

Each step has a range of 0.8 points on the continuum between 1 and 5. All results are above the median score of 3.0 and most results can be found in the “important” area. Some competencies have a score on the border of “important” and “moderately important” or can be found in the “Moderately important” area. The competency that has a score lower than 3.40 is “Act Methodically” with 3.37. Three other competencies scoring with 3.41 are just above this border; these are “ICT Knowledge and Skills”, “Change management” and “Research skills”. This analysis conforms to the results of Figure 5.20 where the conclusion was drawn that the importance is judged higher than the satisfaction for each competency.

Question 27 of the survey is the open-ended question that asked which competencies are missing in the list of 14 competencies that are being assessed. This question aims not only to obtain information regarding possible missing competencies, but also, to receive input regarding required specific areas that according to their opinion are not covered by the 14 competencies belonging to the BBA curriculum. Of all 392 surveys, 268 participants did not provide any suggestions. Out of the 124 participants who did respond, 161 suggestions were

collected. All usable responses were grouped and coded using the segmentation of the Iceberg model. The 161 answers were linked to one of the six levels of the iceberg by assessing each answer and coding them. A considerable number of suggestions were combined with the remark that the mentioned aspect should ultimately lead to action by the graduate. The suggestions directly related to the verb “act” has a score of 7%. The participants see this as the final goal. Graduates have to be able to act in their roles and thus be successful. Every aspect of the competency should lead to desirable behaviour and especially actions. Or, as one participant stated (B15): *“Knowledge is needed about different business management roles and being able to act accordingly”*.

The coding proved challenging, as the Iceberg model does not have an “Act” segment and it cannot be placed in one of the other segments. However, the intention of the participants was clear: this is the highest goal when looking at the objectives of Higher Education regarding their graduates. As a result, the researcher has added a 7th segment to the Iceberg model: to act. Pie Chart 5.25 gives an overview of the results starting with the highest score “Skills” and ending with the lowest score “Values”. “Act” takes position number four.

Figure 5.25: Uni-variate analysis missing knowledge, skills or behavioural aspects, depicted by researcher (n=124)

The combination of the groups knowledge and skills results in almost two thirds of all responses. This represents the classic observable top of the iceberg. The other one third are labelled as either: “act”, “values”, “self-image”, “traits” or “motives”. This shows that participants indicated that HEIs should also develop less observable parts of the iceberg, such as traits. The student has to know his or her strengths and weaknesses, as stated by one participant (B138): *“Self-knowledge is required first and then wanting to listen to*

experienced experts and include this in the whole”. Another participant related this to the role of the middle manager and all layers of the iceberg (B49):

Self-knowledge: being able to reflect. Being able to name and assess his or her own skills in relation to available competencies with colleagues or in the team. Then use this to deploy people in the right way.

Reflection is important to assess where you are as a student, graduate and employee.

When changing the order of the results and groups and putting them in line with the Iceberg model, the top is represented by “Act” as this is the desired visible result of behaviour for graduates by many participants (Figure 5.26). The two following groups are “Knowledge” and “Skills”. These three are the extended observable top of the iceberg and represent in total 72% of the answers given.

Figure 5.26: Uni-variate analysis missing knowledge, skills or behavioural aspects, depicted by researcher (n=124)

Organising the results using the order of the iceberg segments gives insight into the importance of each segment. Of all aspects below the surface, the traits have by far the highest score. Traits are personal characteristics, such as being a good listener or being able to see patterns represent 54% of all non-visible aspects of competencies. The question that the participants seem to find important when searching for a new employee is: does the graduate have the personal characteristics needed to do this job?

The most remarkable and/ or surprising suggestions regarding the answers to question 27 are listed below. Some suggestions add depth to the input used for the iceberg segments.

The most striking words are underlined and used to look for recurrent themes in the suggestions:

- *Behaviour, loyalty, commitment, recognition of power sources, approach to conflict resolution;*
- *Some competencies require a fairly high level of abstraction. The question is whether it is realistic to expect this from the average higher education professional;*
- *Ambition; without ambition, various skills will not come to full or desired development;*
- *Coaching; it is important to be able to coach others on both personal and business development and growth. It is also important that the professional is open to coaching of others. As a result, you remain open to development and thinking differently, so that the 14 described competencies can flourish;*
- *What is lacking are behavioural skills: being able to deal with sensitivities and conflicts, being able to respond to different thinking and working styles, showing stimulating behaviour, being able to deal with feelings and emotions etc. In an international context, these behavioural characteristics are even more crucial for successful cooperation than in a national context;*
- *Understanding ratio versus intuition, human behaviour, ability to connect and get people moving. When working together the professional has to understand very well what working in a team means, and that a shared interest is more important than the self-interest of your own responsibility;*
- *Self-knowledge: to be able to reflect. The professional must be capable of identifying and estimating his or her own skills in comparison to available skills of colleagues or within the team, and then use this to position people in the right way;*
- *Resilience; being able to cope with resistance, dealing with disappointments.*
- *Independence: dare to have your own opinion and stand for it;*
- *Decisiveness, convincing performance, organisational ability,*
- *Flexibility;*
- *Insight into society!!!;*
- *Character, personality, discipline;*
- *Eyes that see, ears that hear what actually plays;*
- *Down to earth mentality;*
- *Lead instead of rule;*
- *Colleges and universities tend to set their targets too high;*
- *Empathy: not too focused on maximising profit but on sustainability, putting things in perspective, communicating clearly, the eagerness to learn, daring to admit mistakes, cooperating, assertiveness, etc.;*

- *To convert theory into practical usable items, now often not usable or feasible: focus more on practice. The pragmatics of practice are slightly different than the theory of the lecture hall;*
- *A degree in Higher Education does not say anything about the competencies of that graduate; everyone can learn something by heart for an exam, to be able to understand and apply into practice makes a real difference;*
- *All really important competencies / skills were named. Interest and motivation are also very important to be successful;*
- *Young people are less concerned with networks. They focus more on themselves.*
- *It is necessary that people outside their rationality also possess empathy and have to be able to listen well. This is necessary in order to prevent the least possible negative consequences in situations such as reorganisation.*
- *I still miss the streetwise skill. To what extent is a professional able to act based upon his or her feelings, based on his / her knowledge of the market?*
- *Psychological knowledge about cooperation, flexibility and tact;*
- *Human action: the professional can make employees feel that he or she is important as a person and that they can come to him or her with their problems and questions at all times for an open conversation;*
- *Change management is not unimportant, but not so much for people who just enter employment.*

The three major key themes in the suggestions above are (1) personal aspects such as character and motivation, (2) “to act”/ “behaviour” and (3) “skills”. The participants who have mentioned “skills” often relate this to acting and behaviour, which proves that graduates should be able to act and show behaviour that adds value. Furthermore, these results are in line with the segmentation according to the Iceberg model and confirm that skills are more important than knowledge, that HEIs have to pay more attention to the levels below water of the Iceberg model, and that “to act” and “behaviour” are the most important points for organisations in the field when they think of graduates. What is surprising, however, is that “knowledge” is missing. It could be that it is assumed that this is already sufficiently covered.

After assessing the 14 competencies, the participants were asked to give their preference as to whether knowledge or skills are more important in the BBA programme. A choice had to be made between these two options; no other possibilities were given. In a following open-ended question, the participants were asked to explain the motivation for their decision.

Figure 5.27: Uni-variate analysis preference for knowledge or skills, depicted by researcher (n=392)

There is a clear preference for skills; in total 69% of all participants have indicated that they find skills more important than knowledge (Figure 5.27). The participants who indicated preferring knowledge often stated that they made this choice because they are afraid that the HEIs focus too much on skills. They state that a certain knowledge basis is crucial for any graduate when he or she starts to work.

The participants have explained the motivation for their choice of either knowledge or skills. The following text describes the motivation, clustered by knowledge, skills and remarkable topics.

Knowledge

Although participants gave a comparable motivation for their choice, different reasons could be identified. Some have indicated that knowledge is missing. They indicate that graduates do not have all the knowledge their organisation needs or do not have the specific knowledge they expect. Others state that knowledge has more value in practice and that the emphasis on skills is too high. This reflects the attention given to skills over knowledge in the last five to ten years in the Netherlands as described in Section 2.4.6. They are afraid that new employees have less and less concrete knowledge necessary to perform well in practice. According to some, knowledge brings the student closer to the working environment. This implies that relevant knowledge is gathered or should be gathered during the study. Another recurrent theme in the answers is the statement that more knowledge is needed and that experience will be gathered in the professional field. Skills are learnt in practice as opposed to within the HEI; as a result, HEIs should focus on developing more knowledge

with their students. This is confirmed by the following quote of one participant (B29): *“We will teach them the skills. However, a certain knowledge base is required”*.

Some participants clearly indicate the role of the HEI and the role of the organisation where the graduate will start his or her career and thus provide a way to connect both parties to the personal development of the student who will become an employee. The suggestion was made to divide roles and responsibilities in the development of the student/ employee. When doing this, some survey participants suggest that HEIs should make a difference between theoretical knowledge and knowledge with a practical orientation.

The answers given often reflect the relation between knowledge and skills. Although both concepts are related to each other and have to be combined, the participants who preferred knowledge over skills have put knowledge in a leading role. They state that knowledge can always be obtained with the right set of skills. In addition, knowledge can be learned individually and more easily than skills. Some have the opinion that knowledge is more important, and leads to better skills. Without sufficient knowledge, skills are learned more slowly and skills are based upon knowledge.

Skills

The following themes were found regarding the motivation of the participants to choose skills over knowledge. The first quote contradicts the fear of the ones who chose knowledge over skills and is reflected by the following quote (B43): *“Knowledge is obsolete, skills make the difference”*.

Skills are a requirement according to these participants. This group focuses on “being able”; “can do” is important. They have the opinion that the “how” is more important than the “what”. “Getting things done” is crucial in practice and is based more upon skills than upon knowledge. As stated earlier, the choice for skills is often related to acting and expected behaviour. The execution is considered to be the main challenge, not the knowledge of the middle manager. He or she should be able to apply their knowledge and skills in practice and thus show the appropriate behaviour to be successful (B180): *“Applying is key, therefore skills!”*.

Regarding the learning aspect and the role of HEIs, one similarity can be found with the participants who have chosen knowledge as their priority. Learning skills is easier on the job than in HEIs.

Some participants gave statements that are not in favour of knowledge, some examples are (B192): *“Knowledge is obsolete”* and (B349) *“knowledge is too volatile”*. According to these participants, this means that knowledge fluctuates too much and changes too much. The expiration date is never far away. Furthermore, as one participant stated (B263): *“Anyone*

can study for an exam; to understand and apply is more important". Skills, once learnt, are a permanent asset for the graduates.

In addition, participants also stated that most knowledge can relatively easy be accessed anywhere. This is general knowledge, however; some knowledge is sector and company specific and can therefore not be learned in HEIs. Students can only gain practical experience in a limited number of organisations during their study. Participants state that students do not have enough time to learn in practice. This should be recognised and changed.

Regarding the learning of skills versus knowledge, the general opinion is that learning skills is more difficult than knowledge, due to the difficulty of changing skills, for example. This means that the middle manager should be able to adapt his or her style to the actual business situation and challenges in the team or organisation. While acquiring new knowledge is relatively easy, the development of skills is generally considered to be a challenge. As knowledge can be learned in many ways, skills require a specific setting where experience is gained and skills can be learned and/ or developed. The graduates have enough knowledge but lack practical skills. Skills shape students and graduates. One participant emphasises the lack of what he calls behavioural skills (B30):

All these 14 competencies are aimed at "professional" acting. For example, look at the description of "communicate" and "collaborate". What is missing are behavioural skills: being able to deal with sensitivities and conflicts, being able to respond to different thinking and working styles, being able to exhibit stimulating behaviour, being able to deal with feelings and emotions, etc. In an international context, these behavioural characteristics are even more decisive for successful cooperation than in a national context.

The suggestion to divide roles and responsibilities in the development of the student/ employee is also reflected in the answers of the participants who chose skills over knowledge. They state that skills are learned in practice and are therefore difficult to develop during the study period. As such knowledge is dynamic, it evolves and develops. Skills are situational, each situation requires another set of skills and the student/ graduate has to learn when to apply what and why.

As practice is different from theory, only organisations can teach students and graduates to develop their skills. Skills in HEIs are too theoretical and do not match the requirements in the field; practical skills are needed.

Some participants took this suggestion a step further and are the opinion that applying skills in practice may result in knowledge development and in more innovation. Theory and

practice often do not match according to other participants; innovation-oriented and solution-oriented thinking are important.

Some participants consider skills to be a major booster for innovative projects in their organisation.

Interdependent factors of personal development

Because the participants had to make a choice between knowledge and skills and no other options were available in the survey, some participants referred to this by stating that although they had to make a choice, knowledge and skills do belong together. The interdependency of skills and knowledge are also emphasised by some in another way (B20): *“Skills are a requirement to use knowledge, they belong together”*. Others have stated that knowledge has no value without skills.

General

Some of the earlier mentioned reactions already went beyond knowledge and skills into the direction of “being able to do” and “getting things done”. Here the link is made between personal development, the Iceberg model, and the role knowledge and skills have during the study period. One participant stated that both knowledge and skills are important, but that it all starts with awareness (B49): *“It is all about insight, being aware of the own role”*.

This requires attention for personal development. Practical experience from working in organisations and developing empathy are key for success. Students should be able to maximise their personal development during the study period. Theory has to be combined with practice, but in such a way that it is effective. HEIs have to realise their own role and assess what they realistically can and cannot do. One participant stated that the costs of learning differs; the costs for knowledge development is lower than the costs regarding skills development. With this remark, both effectiveness and efficiency become factors to be considered.

Suggestions regarding alignment

The last question of the survey invites the participant to give suggestions regarding the topic of this research project. In total, 39 usable answers were given. All suggestions lean in the direction of giving advice on how to improve. No comments were given in appraisal of the work of HEIs.

Most of the suggestions, more than 30% of the 39 answers, place the focus on more practice. Students should be able to gain more practical experience during his or her study period (B274): *“More focus on practice”* and (B56) *“Come closer to the practice!!”*. They were

almost shouting the message in the response. The students should do work in practice and thus learn more essentials of doing business. The education should have a more practical focus, both in philosophy as in its execution. Practical applications should be emphasised. This does not only mean more practical internships but also the usage of teachers from practice (B350): *“Practice is better than theory”*. According to the participants, many competencies must be taught in practice. Knowledge must be on a good level and tasks must be done quickly. The focal point here is action, getting things done. Students have to gain more relevant knowledge and experience in different roles and jobs to become more *“streetwise”*. The exact meaning of *“streetwise”* was not explained further.

Suggestions were given on how to execute higher education with a more practical focus. Action learning was named as a way to give direction to the philosophy regarding the integration of practice during the study period. If HEIs focus on developing thorough basic knowledge, the students can apply this knowledge during training in a traineeship within an organisation. Another suggestion is to start with an internship, for example in the end of the 1st year or beginning of the 2nd year, so that the students can transfer the knowledge and material they are given better into practical situations. In this way, better connections can be made between theory and practice and the effectiveness of the bachelor programme may increase significantly. One participant stated that it would bring added value to continue to follow graduates in the first years of their working career to see what is left of what they have learned. This way HEIs can improve their programmes in such a way that what was learned fits better with the needed competencies in their working environment. This can improve the alignment between study and practice, or, as one participant described (B88): *“A very well-managed mastery of skills in the economy of today can be developed”*.

The participants implicitly also reacted to the Iceberg model and its visible and non-visible aspects. The integration of knowledge and skills was named related to the business administration study (B57): *“Especially in business administration, more attention should be given to the integral application of knowledge and expertise in the various practices”*. The non-visible aspects were mentioned too, i.e. by addressing the lack of attention for tacit knowledge. Ritesh Chugh (2015) defined tacit knowledge as the set of experiences, ideas, skills and other aspects that everyone has but cannot be described or explained. This refers to the lower, non-visible aspects of the iceberg, as it puts the focus on the traits and motives of the student. Some participants questioned the existence and usage of competencies and conclude that they are based too much on theory and not enough on practice.

A recurrent theme in the reactions reflected upon the personal development of the student during the bachelor study. Some participants stated their worries about this (B20):

Pay attention to the student's competencies. Of course, they can learn a lot, but also take on the practical skills. What are they really good at? Let them grow in this.

Here the emphasis lies on identifying personal strengths and weaknesses and working on this using self-reflection. In this respect, future managers have to understand the human dimension in relation to the 14 competencies of this bachelor of business administration. The human factor in organisations was addressed often. In addition to attention for awareness of one's own skills and talents, organisational aspects are also important, such as recognising cultures in organisations. Linked to this, students have to be taught to think more out of the box. HEIs should invest more in creativity as this leads to innovation.

One participant suggested to work with "*Learning agility*". The participant described this as (B61):

A refreshing trend to update and refresh our old competencies. Let students be curious, let them listen, cooperate and think creatively without loss of research.

Learning agility stands for the ability to quickly and flexibly develop new effective behaviour based on new experiences and to subsequently apply that behaviour successfully (De Meuse 2010).

Another clear thread in the answers given to this last question is communication. One participant stated that (B185): "*Communication is being abandoned, i.e. face-to-face, now working too much on paper*". Students have to act more, especially in communication. Less writing and more discussion, arguing, debating, convincing and motivating. Students have to be taught to be socially skilled. This has to be improved and does not only involve presentation skills but the basic ways of communicating. This was often linked in the responses to being able to motivate employees as a middle manager and getting things done, but also linked with the requirement to focus more on customers. This last focus needs to gain more attention within HEIs (B12): "*Communication skills on how to deal very well with clients. That's what it's all about*".

The relation between organisations and HEIs has also been addressed. Most of the remarks were not very positive (B390):

Our experience is that the initiative for contact usually lies with the student and that communication with the HEI is often difficult. Many steps have to be taken before there is clarity.

The administration within the HEI and many regulations are not considered to be friendly from the perspective of organisations. Although satisfied with the students and their performance, the HEI does not meet the demands (B51):

The trainees who work with us are generally very good. However, they are “stopped” by the many rules from the training. Give them the freedom to learn / experience; theory they learn in school.

These statements are in line with earlier remarks and the results of other questions in this survey.

Cooperation is considered to be a necessity (B54):

I think that there can always be more cooperation between universities of applied sciences and the business community. Efficient organisation of these contacts is of vital importance.

However, the way it is done now is not satisfying in the eyes of many participants. The business environment is moving faster and faster. Change is standard, but the pace of change is increasing. HEIs do not seem to be able to match this pace, one participant described it as follows. (B258):

Due to slow decision-making within HEIs, higher education organisations are unable to move quickly in the changing work landscape.

This means that HEIs have to improve to be able to respond faster. Some have given suggestions on how to improve this cooperation. (B46):

The curriculum must be able to respond better / faster to current developments within the business community and public.

In addition, HEIs should focus on both private and public domains. This increases the learning effect (B46):

Give all students also the possibility to learn within the board and/ or management of public organisations such as municipalities.

A very practical suggestion is to pay more attention to job profiles of companies. In addition to giving a fixed lesson plan, HEIs have to ensure the alignment with real jobs in practice. As described earlier in this research, examples can be found in IT and logistics. A possible next step is the suggested partnership between educational authorities and/ or governments and/or industry. This ensures the realisation of joint goals and provides new possibilities, such as executing training and the supervision of students together (HEIs and organisations in the field). In addition, staff also has to be taught what is needed in practice and where the emphasis of the bachelor programme should be and why. In general, training on the job remains essential. By gaining experience, skills can be developed using the knowledge

gained in the training. A critical remark is the question: what can be expected in terms of professional behaviour and personality of graduates who are between 22 and 24 years old? In line with this, one participant gave an emotional comment by describing a rather negative picture of graduates (the word “Yupper” refers to the “young urban professional”). The researcher has added this description as it supports the view of the group of participants that are not satisfied with the performance of HEIs and that at the same time indicate the challenges with the new generation (B169):

The YUPPER is young, wild and dynamic.

Comes along, with fantastic stories.

Wants something, but throws everything upside down.

Has a helicopter view, but has no attention to details.

Acts, but does not oversee the consequences.

Runs over corpses and throws away valuable assets.

Is overvalued.

Drives a car which is too large and spends too much.

And even though he has left for a long time, you are still in trouble.

You have the ungrateful task of putting things in order again.

Fasten your seatbelts!

Although this is a rather negative view of graduates and young employees, it does reflect the feeling that there is a contradiction between what is needed in business organisations and what the students are taught.

5.2.5 Alignment from a quality perspective

It can be stated that organisations and HEIs have a very low frequency of contact. In addition, contact methods related to teaching or the recruitment of graduates do not indicate that alignment is a topic that is being discussed strategically or even on a tactical level. There are contact moments such as the participation of business representatives in HEI advisory boards. However, the conclusion can be drawn that this number is too low to provide a reliable and representative view regarding the desired competencies in businesses.

To investigate the gaps in alignment as described in the earlier paragraphs, the researcher has analysed the motivation for the answers that were given in the survey regarding the awareness of HEIs. These answers give a good overview of the reasons behind the current status of alignment. In total, 206 usable answers were identified and grouped into topics. 45 groups were identified in this way. These 45 groups were coded based upon the SERVQUAL Model (Parasuraman 1985). The customer gap, was not investigated in this research; this gap is out of scope and no suggestions were given in this area. The perceived service is

therefore the same as the expected service. As a result, the next analysis focuses on four SERVQUAL gaps. When looking at the division of the 45 grouped and labelled topics, the Knowledge Gap prevails with 53% of all groups.

SERVQUAL Gap 1: The Knowledge Gap

Most participants wrote their motivation based upon the need for better alignment. This is Gap 1 and gives a description of the differences between the expected service by the customer (here: business organisations) versus the perceptions of in this case HEI management of that same expected service. Suggestions were given by the participants to improve the alignment via e.g. more practice orientation, more attention for “international competencies”, and more attention for specialisations and behaviour in general. A better customer orientation was mentioned the most. Some participants were very strong in their message, such as:

- “*The Gap is there and will remain there*”. This was mentioned several times by different participants and suggests that this has to be accepted and dealt with.
- “*Further development should take place in the company*”. Here the acceptance of the limitations of Higher Education Institutes were made clear and the fact that some aspects can only be learned in a working environment.

Although the Knowledge Gap is the focal point of this research study and is mentioned most, the suggestions made by the participants confirmed the integrative approach of the SERVQUAL model and indicated that all researched gaps are related and therefore important. For example, good communication is needed to make sure that HEIs have the necessary and correct information to be able to improve alignment.

Figure 5.28: The SERVQUAL Gap analysis, depicted by researcher (n=206)

SERVQUAL Gap 2: The Policy Gap

The Policy Gap is the second largest gap. The described motivation differs from “good HEI Management” to “HEIs have to make too many choices”. This gap includes also some strong statements, such as:

- *“HEIs are not interested in alignment”*. This statement was made several times and means that alignment with business organisations does not seem to have any priority.
- *“HEIs are too much internally focused”*. This relates for example to a lack of customer focus and instead paying more attention to delivering according to the quality rules set in the Netherlands. A related statement is “too much focus on money”.
- *“Generally bad and low awareness”*. This remark relates to the perceived service of HEIs by this participant.

Some reactions indicate that HEIs do not consider organisations to be their customer. This is in line with the results from literature research and the interviews with HEI specialists. The strategy of any organisation required a definition of their main customer, which in itself defines the way sales and marketing have to be executed on a tactical and operational level. This is also true for HEIs. If they do not define their strategy towards their stakeholders (which includes identifying the right customers), tactics and operations will not focus on these customers. It can thus also not be expected that any alignment activities will be successful.

SERVQUAL Gap 3: The Delivery Gap

This gap deals with the performance of employees in HEIs such as teachers and supporting staff, which can be measured via the productivity level of the graduate. The HEI employees are ultimately responsible for the delivery of graduates. Topics that matter for this gap are i.e. training of employees, the design and execution of processes, team performance and HR policies. This gap has the smallest collection of suggestions from participants. A possible explanation for this relatively low number is the low rate of interaction between organisations and HEIs in general, as shown earlier in this research. The management of employees and related self-analysis and reflection of employees were mentioned several times. In addition, improving the HEI organisation was mentioned as being critical. This was related to the statement that the average HEI is too slow keeping up with business innovation. Innovation in practice takes place at an increasing pace and HEIs have difficulties to keep up. This was confirmed by literature research as described earlier. Some participants stated that the education and provided services have to be improved in general.

SERVQUAL Gap 4: The Communication Gap

The communication gap is the third most mentioned gap. From an alignment perspective, this gap is important because information has to flow from the market and customers (business organisations) to the HEI organisation that provides services and back again. Many remarks were made to emphasise the importance of good communication and information exchange. In addition, market research was mentioned very often. HEIs have to identify what is important and why; they also have to analyse their own position in the market. Suggestions were made regarding important topics, such as more personal skills and the focus on behaviour. The HEIs need to gather data and develop information for a correct alignment. In this gap, the following strong statement was mentioned several times:

Communication between business and HEI: there is none, so how are they supposed to know?

This statement makes it clear that, according to some participants, there is no communication and as a result it is not possible to realise alignment at any level.

SERVQUAL Gap 5: The Customer Gap

As stated earlier, Gap 5 is out of scope in this research project. Also, no suggestions were given regarding the Customer Gap in the research results. In the given suggestions, no remarkable differences between expected and perceived service were found. The research focuses on investigating the opinion of representatives of organisations regarding alignment and the importance of the 14 competencies and the satisfaction levels related to the graduate end-level of these 14 competencies.

5.3 Conclusions survey organisations

In line with the conclusions regarding the HEI-interviews a constructionist approach was used when looking at the survey and the analysis of the results. Taking in account the importance of context and the absence of one “truth” on how HEIs are regarded by business organisations, the researcher searched for meaning, which mainly was found by analysing the answers of the open questions.

The contact frequency between HEIs and business organisations is low from a quantitative point of view. More than half of all organisations in this sample are in contact with a HEI once a year or less. In addition, the conclusion can be drawn that from an alignment point of view, the quality of the contacts also has some room for improvement. Exemplary for this is the fact that less than 1% have contact with a HEI in the form of participation in an advisory board.

The quantitative analysis regarding the importance and the satisfaction of the 14 competencies shows clustered results around the median. More research is necessary to be able to get a good view on the importance and satisfaction of the organisations on the one hand and the underlying motivation on the other hand.

The participants did not indicate that working in an international setting required different competencies, which indicates that they are in favour of the context-based approach. The conclusion can also be drawn that knowledge and skills are very important for future jobs. However, research shows that other aspects besides knowledge and skills have to be developed within HEIs. The Iceberg model provides a method to help execute this, as these other aspects fit into the segments of this model. Having analysed the research results, an extra layer had to be added to the Iceberg model. The researcher therefore created a 7th segment in the Iceberg model, which is “to act”. The importance of looking not only at knowledge and skills is confirmed by the three key findings in the qualitative suggestions of the participants regarding missing competencies. These three are: (1) personal aspects such as character and motivation, (2) “to act”/ “behaviour” and (3) “skills”.

It can also be concluded that (more) cooperation is considered to be a necessity. In this sense, both stakeholders bear an equal responsibility. This cooperation should have two aims: to improve the quantity and quality of linking theory with, and to exchange information that may help to improve alignment between HEIs and business organisations. With this improved cooperation, students should be able to learn and develop themselves in such a way that their productivity in their first job may increase.

The most important conclusion is that HEIs have to revise their positioning and strategy. A redefinition of their main stakeholders is a necessity; students are an important stakeholder, but not the most important one. Students must have the chance to develop themselves in such a way that they obtain the competencies that are required in their future working environment. Organisations know exactly what is required and are therefore the major stakeholder for HEIs. Without recognising this strategic aspect, it cannot be expected that any alignment activity will be successful.

6.0 Discussion

6.1 Introduction

This chapter includes further analyses and development of theory, leading to a new developed Alignment Model, designed by the researcher. After the presentation of the findings from empirical research in chapters three and four, the aim of this chapter is to establish the link between these findings and the results of literature research of chapter two. The researcher will answer the field research questions as defined in section 1.2. All literature and field research sub-questions will be used to answer the main research question of this research: How should the gap between offered competencies by HEIs and the competencies needed when working as a middle manager in a Dutch German business environment be managed?

6.2 What competencies are considered internationally important looking at the BBA programme offered by HEIs in the Netherlands?

The general description given by most HEI-representatives during the interviews is that competency is a combination of knowledge, skills and attitudes. The development of particular behaviours is described by some as an important goal of a BBA programme. In contrast to knowledge and skills, which were mentioned by most participants in this research, “attitudes” and “to act” were notably absent from discussions, leading the research to conclude that the definition of competency is not always comprehensively defined. In addition, there is no consensus or agreed definition of competencies required for an international environment, neither is there a framework or approach that can help evaluate which competencies are internationally important and why. It is therefore recommended to develop a framework or approach and an agreed definition of competencies in a global or international setting.

The research in this thesis highlights that the researched Universities of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands differ in their views how the ongoing internationalisation in the future working environment of graduates should be integrated into their BBA programme. Furthermore, the question of what internationalisation means for the curriculum and which potential international roles and positions are available as targets for graduate employment is not discussed in HEIs. Executed literature research shows the same lack of definitions. Also, in the literature it is not clear what the definition of a competency is beyond the very basic level. Moreover, literature does not provide details of a definition of competencies for global or international contexts. Although de Wit (2015) and Knight (2003) have provided definitions regarding “internationalisation in higher education” that are still used, both have overlooked

identifying who the customers of HEIs are or should be, and how quality should be defined. Both definitions focus on delivery and process and students and staff but do not talk about the future working environment of graduates or how to measure quality. This is crucial since alignment starts with identifying who the stakeholders are on a strategic level. This should therefore be the first priority.

Although the importance of alignment between HEIs and business organisations is clear, it appears that accreditation of academic programmes is ranked higher in priority than alignment with the future working environment of graduates (European Commission 2014b; Teichler 2009). In addition, this research shows that HEIs do not seem to acknowledge business organisations as stakeholders nor do they ask them for their opinion regarding required competencies in a structured way. Perhaps because of this, HEIs have difficulties matching the requirements of business organisations. This may be due to a lack of knowledge of the desired competencies, but seems to also be caused by more internal issues such as a lack of money, a bureaucratic organisation and the absence of a political willingness to invest. It was stated several times by HEI as well as by business participants in this research that bureaucratic and budgeting issues can be a barrier for innovation.

It can be concluded that the existing ways of identifying the needs of business organisations such as advisory boards and surveys for students and alumni are insufficient. This is in line with Aggarwal and Goodell (2014) who argue that alignment is a challenge for universities of applied sciences due to culture and conflicts between global demand and national rules regarding quality assurance. Other sources in literature (Abraham 2009; Aggarwal, R 2011) indicate that HEIs are slow and not very successful regarding this alignment.

Representatives of business organisations who participated in this research share this opinion.

This research shows that for successful alignment it is important to focus on the cooperation and creation of links between HEIs and organisations where graduates are going to work. Not following the changes in the business environment and failing to be in line with the requirements of international business may result in problems for both the HEI and for organisations. Working across borders, i.e. collaboration among teams in different geographies, is increasing and international reporting lines and talent flows between countries have become more common (Economist Intelligence Unit 2012). If HEIs do not follow these developments, they may lose “contact” with the job market and educate graduates that have a lower fit with their future jobs. The consequence is that organisations potentially have to invest more and more to increase the productivity of their new employees.

From the perspective of the organisations that recruit graduates the best performance of a new employee can be reached by engaging the levels below water of the iceberg in the hiring process (Hay Group 2003; Rudman 2016). One of the conclusions of the literature research in Section 2.5.7 showed the importance of assessing all levels of the Iceberg model. Representatives of organisations who participated in this research also share this opinion. HEIs may wish to consider addressing all levels of the Iceberg model in their programmes. To execute this well, it is important to involve business organisations, as they can provide access to practice and provide the necessary connection with the required competencies in practice.

The research results suggest that HEI specialists have different views regarding which competencies are internationally important. Two perspectives emerged which the researcher has called the “competency-based approach” and the “context-based approach”. In the “competency-based approach”, the focus is on individual competencies. Each competency is assessed for its international value. The “context-based approach” has a different starting point; here the context of the competency defines its value. Each competency is internationally important; differences are identified depending on the context.

In the competency-approach, the competencies “cooperate/ networking”, “communication” and “the ability to connect” are considered internationally important by almost all participants. Different views exist regarding the competencies “act professionally” and “innovation”. Some HEI research participants consider them to be important when working in an international environment. Other participants do not share this opinion. The motivation was not always very clear or fact-based and the “yes” and “no” votes were in balance. Internationally less important are “act methodically”, “ICT knowledge and skills”, “advice”, and “act responsibly”. The competency approach provides difficulties when used for alignment purposes because it stimulates discussion on a competency level and does not support a more holistic perspective of the future working environment of the graduate. The curriculum is more than “just” the sum of all competencies.

This research indicates that participants of business organisations find it difficult to comprehend the definitions of the 14 competencies in the BBA curriculum. The HEI representatives had similar difficulties, proven by the decision of one HEI to add one more “international competency” to the curriculum. This led to the conclusion that the discussion regarding the definition of a competency should relate to the context where the competency will be used. Sharing the results of this research with business and higher education could

provide a good platform for discussions of differences and mutual understanding. Using this context, the defined competency may become clearer and therefore easier to understand.

In the context-based perspective, all competencies are considered to be important by the HEI-respondents for working in an international environment. Here it does not matter which competency is assessed; all are important. Differences in competencies are defined by the context of the job position; the context defines the importance of the competency (Deardorff 2006; Korthagen 2004). This is a holistic approach and can help to improve alignment. When the competencies of job profiles within business organisations are identified and used in the curriculum of higher education programmes, the gap between what is learned and developed in HEIs and what is required in the business field may decrease.

6.3 What are the required competencies for middle managers working in the German-Dutch business environment?

In their answers, research participants of both HEIs and business organisations tended to mix competencies when working in an international environment with general required competencies. Not recognising or identifying differences could implicate that there either are no differences between competencies in a national or international setting, or that the definition of competencies in an international environment is not recognised. The latter is supported by the view of Kedia and English (2011a, 2011b), who state that the definition of what a global manager is, or should be, is unclear. This makes it difficult in this research project to differentiate between what is internationally important or not. The researcher has therefore decided not to focus on internationally important competencies. However, the international perspective will be highlighted whenever possible.

Participants were just as likely to view that HEIs were aware of required business competencies as not. More research is necessary to be able to understand the degree of satisfaction of the organisations on the one hand and to explore the reasons why they are satisfied or dissatisfied on the other hand. Looking in more detail at the assessed 14 competencies in the curriculum, the answers given by the participants of the survey regarding the importance of BBA competencies did not provide a clear preference for one or the other. Regarding the satisfaction levels of each graduate competency, the differences are even smaller. Most of the scores can be found in the “Not satisfied or dissatisfied” section and just three competencies fall into the satisfied area. Research results show that the participants of business organisations have a neutral perspective regarding the delivered quality. However, another explanation could be that the current competency definitions are too descriptive and therefore not clear enough for the participants. This could mean that

there is too much room for speculation and for different individual interpretations, possibly leading to a neutral choice. This is supported by the given qualitative comments of the participants; there are many different views on what competencies are and most participants have used the context of the own organisation for their definition. Combining the confusion in literature and the results of the field research in this project, one might conclude that the current definitions of competency in general and more specific the 14 competencies in this BBA curriculum are probably not clear enough and therefore not yet suitable for discussion with business organisations. This has to be discussed by the stakeholders before using them as the common denominator for future alignment activities. As stated earlier, sharing the results of this research can be a good starting point for discussion from which definitions can emerge. This research identifies the problem and could be a platform for the solution.

The HEI perspective regarding “competencies important in an international context” differs compared with the suggestions given by representatives of business organisations. The latter have not indicated that working in an international setting required different competencies. It seems that business organisations give priority to the context-based approach as described in section 4.2.2 and not to the competency-based approach. As a consequence, all aspects that are important for the working environment must be included in the relevant competencies. When looking at the preferences regarding competencies, more than two thirds of all survey participants have indicated that they find skills more important than knowledge. The participants also underline the importance of not looking only at knowledge and skills; they share the opinion that all layers of the iceberg are important. This view is confirmed in the three key themes emerging from discourse analysis. Participants indicated that the following competencies were missing:

- (1) personal aspects, such as character, motivation, empathy and sensitivity.
- (2) “to act”/ “behaviour”, such as acting independently and problem solving.
- (3) “skills”, such as coaching, leadership, steering, influencing and convincing.

Literature and field research results suggest focussing more on the “Does” and “Is” in the curriculum as described in Millers Pyramid (Cruess 2016). Many participants suggested that the developed competencies finally should lead to action by the graduate; the suggestions directly related to the verb “act”. The participants see this as the final goal. Graduates have to be able to act in their roles and thus be successful. Every aspect of any competency should lead to desirable behaviour. The researcher used the Iceberg model to structure field research results, which provided a challenge as this model does not have an “Act” segment and it cannot be placed in one of the other segments. The intention of the participants was clear: this is the highest goal when looking at the objectives of higher education regarding graduates. The researcher therefore added a 7th segment on top of the Iceberg model: “to

act". The importance of "acting" expressed by those in business organisations contrasts with the opinions of HEI specialists where "to act" is mostly notably absent in the discussions.

Using the Iceberg model perspective, the classical basis of knowledge and skills represents two thirds of all answers. One out of every three survey participants found that further aspects other than knowledge and skills have to be developed within HEIs. Of all aspects below water, the traits have by far the highest score; these personal characteristics, such as being a good listener, represent more than half of all non-visible or below water aspects of competencies. Participants of the survey also stated that theory has to be combined with practice, but in such a way that it is effective. Practice is key (Packard 2014). This perspective is supported by literature findings; according to Kedia (2011a), there is a disconnection between international reality and the ability and speed of HEIs. The degree of mismatch between skills acquired and skills needed is a major cause of the perceived lack of employability (Azevedo 2012). This also means that organisations have to get more involved in student learning processes. Higher education institutes in collaboration with key stakeholders should execute structured market research to identify trends in defined sectors related to the curriculum and the relevant job requirements (Teichler 2009). Methods for alignment have to be developed that are accepted by all stakeholders.

This research suggests the need for HEIs and business organisations to acknowledge each other as major stakeholders in relation to the competencies in the BBA curriculum (Azevedo 2012; Knowles 2011; Milhauser 2010; Packard 2014; Rubin 2009). The number of contact moments and the quality of the communication between HEIs and business organisations must thereafter be improved. Participants from business organisations state that the business environment is moving faster and faster, and that change is standard and has an ever-increasing pace. However, according to literature and representatives of business organisations, HEIs do not seem to be able to match this pace. A practical suggestion given by one participant is to pay more attention to job profiles within companies. In addition to giving a fixed lesson plan, job profiles can help to ensure the alignment of competencies in study programmes with real jobs in practice. Students, HEI representatives and representatives of business organisations form a network triangle from which actions can be initiated. A suggested strategic step by another participant is to develop partnerships between educational authorities and/ or governments and/or industry. This would pave the way towards the realisation of joint goals and provides new possibilities, such as executing training in practice and the supervision of students by HEIs and business organisations.

6.4 What are the similarities and discrepancies between the BBA competencies offered in the Netherlands and the required competencies for middle managers working in the German-Dutch business environment?

6.4.1 Gap analysis results

The following sections will describe the similarities and discrepancies by identifying the gaps as described in section 1.3 and figure 6.1. The most important gap is the gap between competencies in the BBA and competencies considered important by business organisations, as here the results of alignment activities between HEIs and business organisations can be identified.

Figure 6.1: Gap analysis overview, depicted by researcher.

The SERVQUAL-model, as described in section 2.5.8, is used to structure the analysis results of the interviews and the survey. Based upon these results, the researcher developed a model that may help assess alignment from a quality perspective. This newly developed model is offered by the researcher as a novel approach to improve alignment between organisations and HEIs.

6.4.2 Literature and HEI perspective on competencies

The aim of this section is to describe the gaps between literature and practice when looking at competencies (Gap 1, figure 6.1). The identified gaps are:

1. Literature results indicate that HEIs have to redefine their focus and identify business organisations as a key stakeholder, however, HEIs do not identify organisations as the key stakeholder.
2. HEIs, while aligned to an approved quality system, do not align with business. Literature findings have indicated that alignment between HEIs and business organisations is required.

All HEIs define their students as their main stakeholders. Their satisfaction is measured. Only a few HEIs ask also their alumni regarding their view about alignment. Although individual specialists from business organisations are asked to give input regarding curricula of new higher education programmes, no HEI measures the requirements and demand of the business organisations in a structural way. Literature research has shown that organisations expect behaviour that adds value within the organisation. According to Milhauser (2010) and as described in Section 2.4.7, the needs of industry regarding knowledge, skills and abilities do not match the competencies of graduates. This means that alignment is not executed in a good way. The gap is clear; literature results indicate that HEIs have to redefine their focus, identify organisations as a key-stakeholder and start doing research regarding desired competencies.

In addition to the gaps, similarities are identified:

1. Both literature and HEIs use “competencies” and “competences” and “global competencies” and “international competencies” interchangeably; there are no prevailing definitions.
2. The competencies in the BBA curriculum do not match all prevailing ideas and future ideals of HEI representatives, nor of the participants from business organisations.
3. Both literature and HEI representatives indicate that bureaucratic organisations, culture and the absence of political willingness are one of the main reasons that HEIs are slow in their alignment activities.
4. No framework or approach is found in literature nor in the researched HEIs that can help evaluate which competencies are internationally important and why.

The first similarity states that “competencies” are used interchangeably in literature with “competences” and seems to indicate that for some authors there are no differences. However, it can also be concluded that there are different definitions in literature regarding “competency”. Because researchers have not yet come to an agreement, there is no prevailing definition. The same unclear situation was found within the researched HEIs in the Netherlands. Discussing the concept in more detail, the field experts show the same challenges as authors in literature when trying to provide a clear definition of competencies.

Instead of a gap, a similarity is found: both literature and HEI specialists cannot provide one prevailing definition regarding competencies.

Furthermore, internationalisation is used interchangeably with globalisation in both literature and HEIs, which can provide problems as there are major differences between the two as described in section 1.1.2. There is a lack of clear and generally accepted definitions for both concepts in relation to higher education. This was recognised by some authors in literature and in practice by some HEIs. However, there appear to be no efforts to rectify this situation. In line with this, also global competencies and international competencies are used interchangeably. This causes confusion and can obstruct alignment; without accepted definitions, a dialogue between HEIs and business organisations may be difficult. This research has shown that the current definitions of competencies seem to be difficult to comprehend by representatives of business organisations. The researcher therefore concludes that the concepts “global competencies” and “international competencies” can only be used in literature and in practice when the author explains the intended meaning. The researcher advises to use: “competencies important in an international environment”, thus using the context-based approach as described in Section 4.2.2.

The second similarity deals with the indication of participants in HEIs that the competencies in the BBA curriculum do not match all ideas and wishes. One example is the failure to comply with potential demands based upon the geographical location of one HEI. Internal rules and policies prevented adding competency development based upon German-Dutch business. Although HEIs have the possibility to develop and add their own vision regarding internationalisation of the shared BBA curriculum, internal rules, policies and their programme portfolio prevent innovative actions. A curriculum can only contain a certain number of modules; choices have to be made, and these are not always in favour of internationalisation or local requirements.

Literature research results indicate that culture is one of the major reasons that HEIs are slow in their alignment activities regarding the demand of organisations. The expert interviews confirm these findings in literature and show a comparable view. This is the third similarity. Participants have indicated that bureaucratic organisations, culture and the absence of political willingness to invest are blocking initiatives to improve alignment.

As described in Section 5.2, no framework or approach is found in literature nor in the researched HEIs that can help evaluate which competencies are internationally important and why. This is the fourth similarity and would be the next step after the realisation of clear and accepted definitions as described above in the first similarity. Best practice examples as

described in Section 2.4.7, which are the ELA Standards competence profiles and the European ICT Profile Family Tree, can help regarding development. Further research is needed to develop a framework and a guiding approach that help assess and define competencies in an international and/ or global environment.

6.4.3 HEI perspective and competencies in BBA - HEI perspective and perspective organisations

The gap between competencies considered internationally important by HEIs compared with the actual competencies in the BBA curriculum (Gap 2, Figure 6.1) cannot be identified.

The vision of the HEI specialists and the actual competencies in the BBA did not reveal any differences. The interviews did trigger some questions that might lead to new discussions; for example, what internationalisation really means and how it should be used in the BBA curriculum. In general, the conclusion can be drawn that, in the light of internationalisation, competencies are sometimes addressed in HEIs but not in a structured or detailed way. The researched HEIs did not indicate that there is formal discussion taking place about globalisation, internationalisation and their impact on competencies and the curriculum. It seems there is no clear vision regarding this topic at any of the researched HEIs. As a result, the gap between the vision that HEIs have regarding competencies in an international environment and the actual competencies in the BBA curriculum cannot be identified. It is necessary for higher education institutes, in collaboration with key stakeholders, to execute structured market research to identify trends in defined sectors that relate to the curriculum and the relevant job requirements and use the obtained information. Only then can the gap be identified and actions be initiated to reduce the gap. This is not the current situation, however, which is why the competencies in the BBA are the same as the competencies that are considered important by HEIs, which means that no gaps nor similarities can be identified.

The decision by the researcher to consider the competencies in the BBA as equal to the competencies that are found important by HEIs has consequences for Gaps three and four (figure 6.1). The researcher decided that Gaps three and four are the same.

6.4.4 Competencies in BBA and perspective of organisations

The aim of this paragraph is to describe the gap between competencies in the BBA vs. competencies considered important by organisations (Gap four, figure 6.1).

The identified gaps are:

1. HEIs are not focusing enough on practice according to the participants of business organisations.
2. HEIs do not focus on all layers of the Iceberg model.
3. Business organisations state that “to act” and “getting things done” are missing in the current focus of the HEI curriculum.

The quantitative analysis of the survey results shows that the participants of business organisations have a neutral perspective regarding the perceived quality of the 14 competencies in the BBA-curriculum, leading to the conclusion that a gap cannot easily be identified. This may be due to unclear descriptions of the competencies or may have another reason. However, there is criticism towards the connection with practice. The participants of the survey state that HEIs should orientate themselves more towards the future working environment of their students. Practice is key according to most participants; they support this by suggesting i.e. to arrange/ facilitate more internships and to use more teachers from practice.

The second gap is the difference between the existing competencies in the BBA curriculum and the suggestion given by the survey participants that HEIs have to focus on all layers of the iceberg. Due to the absence of clear definitions, a detailed analysis per competency is not possible, but the general conclusion can be drawn that the curriculum does not address all layers. This point can be considered as the major gap between the competencies in the BBA and the required competencies; organisations find all layers of the iceberg important, which stands in contrast with the fact that no real attention to the lower aspects of the iceberg is given within the BBA curriculum.

Section 4.3.4 provides a list with grouped suggestions that are given by the participants regarding missing competencies. As the suggestions and groups are very diverse, it is difficult to identify one or more competencies. Clear described competencies can therefore not be retrieved. The overall view is that “to act” and “getting things done” are the prevailing goals. The research results show that it is very important that the graduates act and get things done when they start working. This means that they have to be productive direct from the start, and also that productivity can be used as a way to measure alignment. No graduate or any other new employee can be 100% productive as the organisation and the related sector require specific knowledge and skills that can only be learned on the job. However, the productivity of the graduate at the start of his or her professional career can be increased if HEIs focus more on teaching their students “to get things done”.

6.5 The Alignment model

Summarising the results of the analysis using the SERVQUAL model in Section 5.2.5, the conclusion can be drawn that alignment is very difficult due to the fact that the basic foundations are lacking, such as generally accepted definitions of e.g. competency, and knowing what business organisations want. The researcher recommends HEIs to initiate three steps. The first step and foundation of any alignment is to acknowledge who the stakeholders are and how communication has to be organised. In addition to students, organisations are important stakeholders; together with HEIs they form the stakeholder triangle. Assuming that the “why” question is clear to everyone, as all stakeholders will benefit from better alignment, the second step is to deal with the “how” and “what” question. For this purpose, it is recommended to use the six layers of the Iceberg model and to add “act” on top, which represents the work that has to be done and what is expected from graduates when they start working in their first job. This will be a challenge for both organisations and HEIs as decisions have to be made regarding what, why, where and how learning should take place within the HEI and/ or the related organisations. The third step deals with organisation; both stakeholders have to answer the question how alignment will be organised. Particularly the layers below water of the iceberg need attention. The focal point of student development has to shift to all iceberg levels, thus providing more possibilities for students and more added value for future employers. In close cooperation with representatives of selected business sectors, HEIs can discuss how the seven layers should be managed in any relevant curriculum and which definition regarding productivity will be used to link with practice and measure results. Section 2.4.4 provides a definition of productivity by the OECD, that has been used in this research.

Literature and field research results suggest focussing more in the curriculum on the “Does” and “Is” as described in Millers Pyramid and the social roles, self-image, traits and motives described in the Iceberg model. This has to be done by assessing the abilities of students by applying a holistic approach to all iceberg levels. This way the quality of the performance of students and professionals may increase. An important aspect is to use a clear and realistic description of the international role(s) and the attached competencies, which are accepted by all stakeholders.

The researcher has used the model from Spencer & Spencer as described in Section 2.4.4. as the basis for a model for alignment.

Figure 6.2: Alignment model, depicted by researcher and modified from Spencer & Spencer (Spencer 1993)

Description of the Alignment model and approach

The original model of Spencer & Spencer focuses on the (potential) productivity of new employees. The researcher put the focus in this new model on the (potential) productivity of graduates. As stated earlier, the researcher has not given a final definition of productivity, as this is something that has to be defined by the stakeholders. To be able to work on alignment it is important to include HEIs in the model as they execute the education programmes and aim to educate and develop students to be productive employees. With this first change, the model shows the time spend in HEIs and the time spend as a graduate/ new employee in an organisation. The result is that both periods and all stakeholders are considered to be important and that stakeholders should consider what needs to be done in which time period. Student learning can thus be more connected and embedded with developments in practice; the model contains a continuum into practice.

The second change is that the new model adds an additional dynamic factor; in addition to the possible changes in the productivity curve due to selection and/ or training, the new model also shows the possible movement of the productivity curve towards the study period within HEIs. This curve is influenced by activities that increase or decrease alignment. As a result, the productivity curve of the graduate/ new employee can move to the left towards HEIs or to the right away from the HEIs. When done well and if the alignment activities are effective and related to a defined working environment, students can already increase their productivity levels during their studies. The current starting phase of the model defines the

productivity level to be zero. Further research is needed to identify the starting point for productivity in every alignment project.

The third major change to the Spencer & Spencer model are the added competencies of the Iceberg model. Research has shown that all aspects of the iceberg and the additional “Act” component (light blue square in Figure 6.2) are important for the working environment of new employees. All competency aspects that are underneath the surface affect how knowledge and skills (white square in Figure 6.2) are used and thus influence job effectiveness (Spencer 1993). The visible competencies are relatively easy to develop by knowledge transfer and skill development training. The competencies underneath the surface (dark blue squares in Figure 6.2) are more difficult to develop and need different methods such as coaching, mentoring and counselling. The requirements of the future working environment are changing, which is signalled by a change towards e.g. more hidden behavioural aspects of the candidate. For this reason, all levels have to be part of the Alignment model. Which levels will be used and how depends on the context and i.e. the related job profile. The involved sector or organisation has to define their required competencies, which has to go beyond the basic knowledge and skills. In addition, they also have to describe how these competencies can be measured in productivity. Depending on specific job requirements and the related curriculum, stakeholders not only have to discuss which competencies are important, but also how and where they will be developed and how progress can be measured. Here the HEIs have an important role as they can advise on learning and development methodology; organisations, on the other hand, have to indicate which roles and responsibilities they can take regarding competency development.

Implementation of the alignment model and approach

The implementation of the Alignment model consists of three steps, using a structured approach.

Setting up a methodology for alignment that is accepted by all partners is the first step. It is also probably the most challenging step, but a critical success factor regarding alignment. Even if the described implications for HEIs and organisations as described in chapter six are handled and realised, it will still be a challenge to realise an effective cooperation. European initiatives as described in Section 2.4.7 indicate that business organisations tend to take matters into their own hands when cooperation is difficult due to timing, quality perspectives, culture, or other reasons. This is, however, not the best way forward. The null curriculum, that what is not taught (chapter 2.2.6), has to be avoided. It should be clear which competencies are required and why. In addition, the necessary change of the customer focus

within HEIs will probably have a big impact and requires major changes. Both stakeholders have to realise that alignment is not possible without working together. This cooperation has to be facilitated by the Dutch state, they have to create the environment for a structured and long-term alignment process, taking into account the current quality assessment regulations in the Netherlands.

After the acceptance of the methodology, the second step is to define the focal point: which scope will be chosen and why, and how productivity is defined and measured. The focus can be, for example, on a certain job profile and/ or on a certain business sector. This job profile must be described using all layers of the Iceberg model (figure 6.2). It is crucial to define the scope in a clear way; when the focus is too large it can be difficult, for instance, to agree on the definition of productivity and how this can be measured. Having a clear and accepted definition of productivity is therefore another critical success factor. Both HEIs and business organisations must agree on who pays how and when attention to which competency. After this step, alignment has to be improved on a continuous basis. It is imperative that progress is measured by performance indicators, thus enabling the stakeholders to take corrective actions regarding the development of competencies. When executed correctly, the productivity curve of the graduate as illustrated in Figure 6.2 will start to improve and move away from the baseline. The benefits can be identified and measured as the learning curve is shortened by using pre-defined performance indicators regarding productivity. Although productivity is a concept used by many organisations, it is probably safe to say that the way it is defined will differ depending on the context.

The third step would be to move this improved learning curve and higher productivity rates towards the learning period within HEIs. The better the alignment works between organisations and HEIs, the more the curve can move to the left and the losses of productivity can be reduced over time. How far the curve can go to the left depends on the subject of the education programme, the level of cooperation, and the context where it all takes place.

The researcher decided not to develop the model further because additional research is needed. This can be done by combining theory and practice. The researcher suggests starting with a pilot and use one selected job description within one organisation as the main object for this alignment pilot. The participating HEI and organisation have to agree on definitions regarding concepts such as competencies in an international environment and productivity. This pilot can also help developing a detailed implementation plan, which is needed once the model and approach is further developed and accepted. This plan should

contain agreed identified critical success factors and attached key performance indicators that can be used to work on a successful project implementation. The Alignment model provides flexibility, i.e. the stakeholders may decide upon a development period that goes beyond the HEI study period and continues during the first year(s) as a new employee.

7.0 Conclusion

7.1 Contribution to knowledge

This research provides two main contributions to knowledge that are described in the following chapter. The “competency framework” as described in section 4.2.2 is the first main contribution, this concept contains several other related subsidiary contributions. The second contribution is the “Alignment Model” as described in section 6.5, in which also several other related subsidiary contributions are embedded.

Contribution I

Although there is a distinct difference between “competence” and “competency”, this research shows that they are used interchangeably in literature; there is no prevailing definition. In this research, the choice was made to use competency, as this refers to behaviour and is related to context. The same occurs when looking at the usage of “global competencies” and “international competencies” and the usage of “internationalisation” and “globalisation” in literature, these are also often used interchangeably. In addition, no models or approaches were found in literature that can help assess which competencies are internationally important and why. Clear definitions are missing, and these are needed to develop a common basis regarding the research areas in higher education and alignment. The researcher recommends that the concepts “global competencies” and “international competencies” should only be used in literature when the author explains the intended meaning. A better solution is to use “competencies important in an international environment” as concluded in section 6.4.2.

When looking at the situation in the researched HEIs in the Netherlands and related to the BBA curriculum, the statement can be made that there is no common way of dealing with “internationalisation” and there are no models or approaches in place that can help measure which competencies are internationally important. This means that internationalisation cannot be measured in the curriculum as it does not have any quality references. Combined with the conclusion that there are no international or global competencies but instead only competencies in an international environment, two perspectives emerged which the researcher has called the “competency-based approach” and the “context-based approach”. In the “competency-based approach”, the focus is on individual competencies; in the context-based approach, all competencies are important for working in an international environment as the context defines the importance. The two approaches are described in section 4.2.2.

Contribution II

There is a structural gap regarding competencies which exists between higher education and the field where their graduates are going to work. There are no actions in place to bridge the gap. Literature confirms that alignment is a challenge for HEIs but does not provide solutions to overcome this gap. Research shows that there is no theory or model that addresses this topic in literature. It seems that no author has created a model that includes both HEIs and organisations for the purpose of alignment. The model from Spencer & Spencer (1993) addresses the productivity problem of new employees such as graduates, but does not involve HEIs nor the implications of improved alignment. Synthesising all research results and research analysis, the researcher suggests a new model based upon Spencer & Spencer, which is described in section 6.5. This “Alignment Model” is the second main contribution and can help enhance (the quality of) alignment. When alignment is sought, it is important to involve all relevant stakeholders and to work with agreed definitions. However, identifying the major stakeholders and using agreed definitions is merely the foundation. It is important to identify different sorts of competencies. For this purpose, the researcher suggests using all levels of the iceberg. Although the importance of skills versus knowledge is a continuous discussion in the Netherlands, this research shows that these two are not sufficient to match requirements of business organisations. This discussion has to include all levels of the Iceberg model. For this reason, input is needed from organisations, as they are a major stakeholder. Working with all levels of the iceberg as described in sections 2.4.2 and 6.5 may help to improve the productivity of the graduate, which is likely to be an important factor for organisations when they hire new employees. Organisations want to have new employees that add value. The level of performance during the first year of working could be improved during the study period when HEIs and organisations are working together using competencies related to specified job profiles. This is why the researcher has used the structure of the Iceberg model and combined this with the model as described above to develop a dynamic model that may help to improve alignment.

For this reason, HEIs should link their education processes and goals in a better way with practice. Although some researchers do emphasise the importance of practice for HEIs, the way this should be done needs further research. Both HEIs and organisations have a responsibility and have to find a way to work together; they can use competencies, job profiles and productivity to improve alignment between HEIs and organisations. The researcher identifies three levels of cooperation. The first alignment level is the way alignment between HEIs and organisations is done now: based upon a general curriculum that does not focus on specific sectors or specific job profiles. The current curriculum approach can serve many sectors and many job profiles and requires further action within the organisation, because they have to develop the competencies of the graduates further

and in such a way that they meet the requirements of that same organisation. The second level zooms in on existing job profiles that are in place in relevant sectors and organisations. Here the gap between what is taught and what is required with organisations is reduced, job profiles describe the competencies that HEIs should develop. The optimal situation is level three; here job profiles of one specific organisation are used, thus giving HEIs the possibility to develop their students towards existing jobs in practice.

However, one major hurdle should be taken first to be successful with alignment: finding a definition of quality that is accepted by all stakeholders. This research shows that literature does not identify who the customers of HEIs are or should be and how quality should be defined. Existing definitions regarding “internationalisation in higher education” focus mainly on delivery and process and students and staff, but do not talk about the future working environment of graduates or how to measure quality related to this. HEIs define quality by aligning with an approved national quality system; they do not really align with business. In addition to this and according to literature, HEIs have problems keeping up with the changes in business environments. This was confirmed by participants from organisations. They stated that HEIs do not seem to be aware of their requirements and do not have the strategy neither the means to obtain this information. It is advisable to work on closing this gap, develop a fit-strategy, improve the alignment and work with students/ graduates to improve their productivity.

7.2 Implications for HEIs

The research and its results also have implications for HEIs which are described in this section. The first implication is a required action, which is to initiate a project to develop one definition of the concepts “competency” and “internationalisation” with the major stakeholders. A shared language and meaning is needed to provide all stakeholders with a clear understanding and, as stated earlier, to support the usage of shared and agreed definitions. With this definition, HEIs and their customers can work on a mutual approach towards alignment and how to deliver the desired quality.

The second implication relates to the current customer orientation of HEIs. Instead of defining students as their major stakeholder HEIs should define organisations as their major stakeholder. Students are a very important stakeholder, but are not likely to have knowledge of the required competencies in their future field of work.

Representatives of organisations in the field do have this knowledge. Although HEIs cooperate in some fields with representatives in the field, the approach and results do not lead to desired results. This will probably mean that most HEIs should adapt their mission,

vision and strategy (including SMART defined strategic objectives). The next step is to translate these changes into tactical and operational goals, which may lead to new and more intensive ways of cooperation and communication with practice. The researcher does realise the challenge that come with this required change.

The third implication is the need for more communication and cooperation. It is advisable to initiate more cooperation and communication between universities of applied sciences and the business community. Research shows that both parties do want to work together, but are not able to organise this in a good way. As the business environment is moving faster and faster and change has become the standard, both parties should discuss how to handle this since HEIs do not seem to be able to match this pace in business. Joining forces with practice can lead to work-based learning possibilities that match the requirements of all stakeholders (European Commission 2010; Lowden 2011). The discussion should include the curriculum, the desired and detailed competencies on different levels of the iceberg as described earlier, and the job profiles in companies. The BBA profile is a rather generic profile, nevertheless there are possibilities to improve alignment. Partnerships such as in IT and logistics, as described in this research, are best practices that can be used. The realisation of joint goals provides new possibilities, such as executing training and the supervision of students by HEIs and organisations in the field. The pitfall of HEIs is that they may have the opinion that organisations only want to earn money and that higher education has a higher purpose. The culture within HEIs and current quality regulations are barriers that should be managed.

The view of the Dutch government as an important stakeholder was out of scope in this research. However, they do play a role from a regulation point of view. It is advisable not to let HEIs lead their own initiatives regarding internationalisation as a result of lack of national guidance (The British Council 2016). In addition, the current way of defining quality conflicts with the definition of quality as defined in the SERVQUAL model. To be successful, the Dutch government should facilitate the necessary change in customer orientation within HEIs by stimulating a dialogue between HEIs and organisations. This could be organised in different ways, e.g. per sector or field of expertise, but should be decided upon by the involved stakeholders.

Universities of applied sciences and research universities in the Netherlands have defined three ambitions regarding internationalisation in 2018. One of these ambitions is to deliver a meaningful contribution to the labour market by helping to reduce deficits. The universities are committed to realise this ambition, but also add a call for action. They state that they are

not able to realise these ambitions without help and commitment of stakeholders in Higher Education, the professional community and the Dutch government (Netherlands Association of Universities of Applied Sciences & Association of Universities in the Netherlands 2018).

7.3 Implications for business organisations

The research had a practice orientation; both HEIs and organisations were asked for their opinion and both have an important role in improving alignment. The described three implications for HEIs in section 7.2 are related to the implications for organisations and vice versa.

The first implication is comparable to the first implication for HEIs: to define and share one definition of the concepts “competency” and “internationalisation”. To speak one language is the basis for any communication and is therefore the first step and should be discussed with HEIs.

The second implication deals with the responsibility of organisations to understand the position and dynamics of higher education in the Netherlands. This is the second necessary step to be successful when cooperating with HEIs. Representatives of organisations should accept and understand that HEIs have a different culture, have a different position in society and are subject to different rules and regulations compared with the business arena. As stated earlier, this research shows that organisations do want to cooperate with HEIs and have also suggested possibilities to realise. For instance, they have suggested partnerships between educational institutes and/or governments and/or industry, which should ensure the realisation of joint goals. The next step are long-term initiatives that could improve alignment in a structural way.

In this research, not a lot of comments were given in appraisal of the work of HEIs regarding alignment. A pitfall of organisations could be that they may keep their current position regarding their complaints about the difficulties of working together with HEIs. Organisations should be more proactive and take more initiative to support cooperation. Those who complain about the lack of practice-orientation should take responsibility. This is why joint goals are needed, as they will support joint activities and more cooperation. Another pitfall is that they focus too much on costs regarding the alignment topic. Higher education should be regarded as an investment and not as costs that require a return on investment.

7.4 Limitations and opportunities for further research

The main challenge of any researcher is to be objective. This relates to the problem analysis, the definition of the goals and research questions, research design and execution, analysis and drawing conclusions. Being the starting point of research, the main research questions and research objectives must be unbiased (Verhoeven 2012). According to Saunders (2012b), objectivity is an ethical principle, which means that the researcher has to collect the data accurately and fully and that subjective influences have to be avoided during research.

The researcher was able to obtain sufficient reliable data from the interviews with HEI specialists. The validity of the interview results was proven to be high.

The decision to focus in the HEI interviews on the nine generic competencies and thus excluding the five task competencies is from this reflective point of view questionable. It would have been better to include all 14 competencies; discussing the five task-competencies regarding their international importance could have had added value.

However, the research results from the survey with business organisations made clear that discussing amongst others the importance of each of the 14 competencies was less important than the alignment between HEIs and organisations.

The lack of support from the “Duits Nederlandse Handelskamer” (DNHK) led to a survey with a new population: all organisations in the Netherlands. The response of the survey in this population was sufficient to meet the required confidence interval of 95% and confidence level of 5%. As a consequence, the research obtained had the targeted reliability. Although limitations regarding objectivity can never be excluded and no researcher can be 100% objective, the credibility and reliability are high. Other limitations were described in earlier chapters.

The researcher defines two important opportunities for further research. The first topic for further research deals with identifying areas and possible forms for cooperation as described earlier. The alignment model should ideally be used with one or a small set of job profiles. This way the scope is limited and the competencies can be described in a detailed way. For this reason, stakeholders have to identify and agree upon a specific sector or business field and its related job profiles. The second topic for further research is the usability and further development of the proposed alignment model and its approach.

7.5 Reflection

This final section reflects on the research project and the personal development of the researcher.

Research project

Despite the existence of literature on competencies and internationalisation, I find it remarkable that this research reveals gaps in literature and gaps between theory and practice. Most of the gaps that were planned to be investigated are identified and described. These gaps are described in section 5.2.5 and section 6.4 and show all areas for improvement regarding the alignment challenge in higher education in the Netherlands. The survey with 392 usable questionnaires formed the basis for a SERVQUAL analysis regarding the quality of services offered by HEIs of which the knowledge gap was the most important one. This gap indicates that there should be more communication between the stakeholders. Communication is a two-way street and both higher education institutes and organisations have to take their responsibility. However, a risk is that a lack of urgency or other reasons may block or postpone initiatives to improve alignment in the upcoming years, leading to a larger gap that may no longer be able to be bridged. In line with this, another risk is that one stakeholder could conclude that the gap is too large to close. This may lead to actions by business organisations to solve the problem by themselves. At the moment, graduates who lack certain competencies are helped to develop these during the first months or year in their first job(s) in their first organisations(s). Organisations may realise that their development costs regarding new employees can increase, thus reducing their competitiveness in the market. This in itself might cause a reaction to organise competency development within the own organisations and thus make HEIs and their higher education programmes redundant to a certain extent. This can have its effect on HEIs. When higher education institutes educate and develop students in such a way that they do not match the required job profiles, their social role in society and their “raison d’être” can diminish. HEIs have a social responsibility in society and should carry out this role. Furthermore, organisations also have responsibilities regarding their environment and higher education in particular and should support HEIs.

The aim of this research project is achieved. Insight is given in the different gaps regarding this topic and suggestions are made to manage the gaps. The structure of the mixed-method approach was intentionally designed in such a way that one phase informed the other, that quantitative research influenced the qualitative approach and vice versa (figure 3.1 in section 3.1). In addition, a new model is developed based upon an existing model in literature, thus deepening its usability, which when applied will increase the knowledge regarding alignment. This suggested Alignment model and the attached approach needs to be explored further as the current status is not yet detailed enough. The researcher would like to prevent ambiguity and suggests executing research regarding the alignment process and the ways to measure

progress via performance indicators and success factors related to the defined productivity. The first priority is to focus on the awareness regarding the current status of alignment; this awareness should be present with all major stakeholders. Without awareness, alignment activities will not be successful.

In conclusion, this research presents a basis for further research and several new research areas regarding the alignment of business competencies in higher education degrees and the requirements for employment in an international arena. In addition, the research identifies several risks that need to be addressed by all stakeholders.

Personal development

The choice for this topic was not difficult. I have been working in the field of higher education since 2002 and in international higher education since 2005. I have seen and recognised the struggle from within several HEIs in the Netherlands but also the inertness of some business organisations who only complain but take no initiative to help solve the problem. By the year 2002, I had had different positions in the Netherlands and in France that resulted in working with many different countries and various different cultures in Europe.

This experience has helped me very much in my current business role, where I connect German HEIs with Dutch HEIs, offering academic programmes to German students in the Netherlands. Being one of the first to offer a Dutch state recognised bachelor degree programme in Germany, my knowledge regarding internationalisation of the curriculum increased. I knew there was a gap between HEIs and business organisations in the field of competencies, but did not have the facts to back this up. With this research, I wanted to support my personal experience regarding alignment with scientific research and had the aim to develop a model/ approach that would help bring the major stakeholders together, improve alignment and reduce the gaps. I have thought about this a lot. I recognised the risk of being subjective and already having an opinion and solution before the start, but also during my research project. Trying to be objective was probably my biggest challenge. Although my personal experience regarding alignment based upon my work experience was largely confirmed, it was imperative that I do not jump to conclusions. On the other hand, my experience in (International) Higher Education helped me to understand and identify issues and challenges in both organisations and HEIs and made for example the HEI interviews more effective. My experience and knowledge was also helpful regarding the translation from Dutch to English of the interview and survey results. Translation is a risk regarding objectivity in this research. The conclusions and recommendations in this research project are based upon enough sufficient reliable and valid data.

In conclusion, I can state that my view on this topic has changed during the last years. I came as a practitioner and took a journey to learn academic writing and how to design academic research. To remain in the topic of this research; my competencies have developed and the international setting definitely contributed to this. People often ask me if I would take this journey again; my answer is yes!

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Appendices

Appendix 1: Ethics approval

Ref: SEC/SHNM/AUG16/095

25 November 2016

Jan-Kees van Dijk

School of Health, Nursing and Midwifery
Hamilton Campus
Caird Building
HAMILTON
ML3 0QA
Tel +44 (0)1698 283100
Fax +44 (0)1698 282131

Dear Jan-Kees,

Outcome of School of Health Nursing and Midwifery Ethics Committee

Thank you for your recent submission to the above Committee.

I can confirm your submission was reviewed by the Committee, where the outcome has been:

- **APPROVED - subject to required (compulsory) changes (Under guidance of supervisor)***

Feedback from the Committee is attached for your information.

On behalf of the School Ethics Committee, I take this opportunity to wish you well with your study.

Yours sincerely

Dr W G Mackay
Chair
School of Health Nursing & Midwifery Ethics Committee

cc

Karen Wilson MSc, RGN, RM, DipDN, RNT
Dean of School

University of the West of Scotland is a registered Scottish charity, Charity number 50003520

Appendix 2: Invitation mail HEI interviews (Dutch)

Van: Jan-Kees van Dijk <jkvandijk@aa-europe.eu>

Datum: donderdag 17 maart 2016 13:41

Aan: [REDACTED]

Onderwerp: Participatie PhD onderzoek

Geachte heer [REDACTED],

Mijn naam is Jan-Kees van Dijk, ik ben sinds 2002 actief in het Hoger onderwijs en sinds 2005 in het internationale Hoger Onderwijs. In deze periode heb ik veel ervaring opgebouwd op het gebied van hoger onderwijs in en tussen Duitsland en Nederland. Nadat ik 'lang' geleden in 2001 mijn MBA bij de Universiteit Twente had behaald ben ik eind 2014 begonnen aan een PhD study. Mijn universiteit in Schotland is The University of the West of Scotland (UWS). Deze Universiteit werkt hierin nauw samen met de Hochschule für Angewandte Wissenschaften (HAW) in Hamburg.

In januari 2016 heb ik contact opgenomen met Drs. Danny Brouwer, bij u bekend als voorzitter LOO Bedrijfskunde MER. Ik heb bij hem het verzoek neergelegd of ik de opleidingsmanagers of verantwoordelijke personen met andere functies voor de bachelor opleiding(-en) met CROHO nummer 34139 van LOO Bedrijfskunde zou mogen benaderen voor mijn onderzoek. De heer Brouwer heeft mijn verzoek besproken in het bestuur, en heeft afgelopen maandag via onderstaande mail akkoord gegeven. Maar, natuurlijk kan iedereen voor zichzelf beslissen of hij of zij in dit onderzoek wil participeren :-)

Het onderwerp van mijn PhD study is: "A study to explore the alignment of business competencies in Higher Education degrees and the requirements for employment in an international arena". Graag verwijs ik naar onderstaande mail die ik in januari naar de heer Brouwer heb gestuurd waarin de hoofdlijnen van het onderzoek staan beschreven.

Mijn concrete vraag aan u is of ik met u, als verantwoordelijke van CROHO nummer 34139, een interview mag plannen. Dit interview zal niet meer dan 2 uur in beslag nemen. Indien mogelijk zou ik dit interview of in de laatste week van maart, of in de eerste week april willen inplannen. Hiervoor wil ik u in de komende dagen telefonisch benaderen om dit verzoek te bespreken en naar ik hoop een interview in te plannen.

Naar mijn bescheiden mening kan dit onderzoek alle betrokken Hogescholen helpen op het gebied van de inzet van competenties voor (toekomstige) management voor internationale posities.

Indien er interesse bestaat zal ik voor alle respondenten een groepsessie organiseren waarin de resultaten uit het onderzoek worden gedeeld en besproken. Tijdens deze sessie kan ik mijn bevindingen met de participanten delen. Dit kan eventueel ook tijdens een al gepland LOO overleg.

Indien gewenst kan ik meer informatie geven omtrent mijn onderzoek tijdens de ledenvergadering die naar ik heb begrepen binnenkort plaats gaat vinden. Tijdens dit overleg kan ik ook in gaan op individuele vragen. Mocht hier behoefte aan zijn verzoek ik u mij toch toe te staan alvast een interview in te plannen, en niet te wachten tot deze vergadering. Dit in verband met de strakke planning van mijn onderzoek :-)

Wat meer informatie over ondergetekende:

<https://www.linkedin.com/in/jankeesvandijk?trk=hp-identity-name>

Alvast heel erg bedankt voor uw aandacht, en naar ik hoop uw participatie!

--

met vriendelijke groet,
mit freundlichen Grüßen,
with kind regards,

Jan-Kees van Dijk

Appendix 3: Participant Information form HEI interviews (English)

Participant Information Sheet

Date: 30th March 2016
Version: 1

Dear Sir/Madam,

I plan to conduct a study within the organisation where you work and I kindly would like to invite you to participate. The information sheet below outlines all the essential information you may require to decide if you wish to participate or not. The researcher will answer any questions you may have via email. To protect your identity, you may submit questions anonymously.

Study Title:

A study to explore the alignment of business competencies in Higher Education degrees and the requirements for employment in an international arena.

What is the purpose of the study?

Previous research has suggested that there is no clear definition of competencies and clear view on what competencies are needed when working as a middle manager in an international environment. The aim of this study is two-fold. The first aim is to identify competencies that define success in an international environment. The second aim is to identify the differences between offered competency development in the BBA (with CROHO number 34139) in The Netherlands and the prior identified competencies. This study forms an integral part of a PhD thesis.

Why have you been chosen?

As you are working in the field of Dutch Higher Education, your honest feedback would be most valuable for the research.

What will happen if you participate?

1. I would like to plan a moment for an interview. This interview will take approximately 1,5 hrs.
2. The interview will be registered digitally.
3. No personal identifying data pertaining to yourself will be included during the interviews, your responses will be completely anonymous.

The responses collected within this research will be included in the researcher's PhD thesis.

It is important to note that you are under no obligation to participate and are free to withdraw from the study at any point.

What happens to the information provided by you?

All received data are anonymous therefore maintaining your confidentiality. No response you provide can be traced back to you. You will receive a written report of the results of the interview with the question to correct or add when necessary. The results will be used to explore the alignment of business competencies in Higher Education degrees.

Do you have to participate in this study?

No. Your decision to participate (or not) is purely voluntary. Once you have read this information sheet and any/all your questions have been answered to your satisfaction a meeting will be planned.

How will you benefit from participating in this study?

After the interview you will receive a written report of the results of the interview with the question to correct or add when necessary.

Although there are no direct personal gains from participating in this study, your honest answers will provide a clearer picture to inform future curriculum development.

What happens to the data uncovered in this study?

The findings will be shared with the University of the West of Scotland (UWS) via the researcher's submitted thesis. The data may be presented at a conference or in a peer reviewed journal but you will not be identified.

Participation consent:

By signing the consent form, it is understood that you have consented to participate in the study. If you choose not to participate after signing the consent form please inform the researcher as soon as possible.

Thank you for reading this information. Below are the contact details of the researcher and their respective research supervisor at UWS.

Researcher Name: Jan-Kees van Dijk MBA
[REDACTED]

Research Supervisor Name: Dr Maria Pollard - Assistant Dean (Education)
Email [REDACTED]

Appendix 4: Participation Consent Form HEI-Interviews

PARTICIPANT CONSENT FORM

Participant's Identification Number for this study:

Title of Study: *A study to explore the alignment of business competencies in Higher Education degrees and the requirements for employment in an international arena.*

Name of Researcher: Jan-Kees van Dijk MBA

1. I confirm that I have read and understand the Participant Information Sheet for the above study. I have had the opportunity to consider the information, ask questions and have had these answered satisfactorily.
2. I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw at any time without giving any reason.
3. I agree to take part in the above study.

*Please
initial box*

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Name of Person taking
consent

Date

Signature

Appendix 5: Questionnaire semi-structured interviews HEIs (Dutch)

Interview fase 2

Date: 31 maart 2016
Version: 1.4 NL

Introductie

Nogmaals **dank** voor uw participatie in dit PhD onderzoekstraject.

U bent de expert op het gebied van competenties en de bachelor programma's gebaseerd op het BBA curriculum met **CROHO nummer 34139**. Dit is de reden waarom ik u – als vertegenwoordiger van deze Hogeschool – heb gevraagd te participeren.

Ik ga u verschillende vragen stellen; **de duur van het interview is maximaal 1,5 uur**.

Zoals afgesproken geeft u wel / geen toestemming om dit interview digitaal op te nemen.

Voor zover u dit nog niet heeft gedaan wil ik u hierbij uitnodigen het **'consent' formulier** te ondertekenen.

Deel 1: betekenis en definitie van "competentie"

- 1.1. Wat is uw (uw = Hogeschool) definitie van competentie / competenties?
- 1.2. Bestaat er zoiets als een internationale competentie, zo ja, waarom?
- 1.3. Wat zijn volgens u specifieke competenties voor een internationale omgeving en waarom?

Part 2: gebruik van competenties

2.1 Welke bachelor programma's (namen) zijn gebaseerd op het relevante curriculum met CROHO nummer 34139?

2.2 Hoeveel studenten studeren momenteel in deze programma's?

2.3. Welke competenties worden hoe in welke bachelor programma gebruikt?

- a. 9 generieke competenties?
- b. 5 taakcompetenties?
- c. wat is de rol van de kennis uit vakgebieden?
- d. hoe verhouden deze 3 soorten zich tot de taakopdracht – actie student versus facilitering vanuit programma?

2.4 Waarom worden deze competenties gebruikt (motivatie per competentie)?

2.5. Zou u mij aan kunnen geven hoe deze competenties vertaald zijn / worden in deze bachelor programma's?

2.6. Kunt u mij aangeven welke methoden gebruikt worden om te meten om vast te stellen dat de vertaling succesvol is geweest?

Part 3: markt vraag

3.1. Hoe zou u de doelgroep(-en) beschrijven of definiëren voor elk relevant bachelor programma? Voor welke beroepen wordt er per bachelor opgeleid?

3.2. Wat is uw definitie van middelmanagement ofwel 'middle managers'?

Part 4: competenties en de definitie van succes

4.1. Welke competenties van het relevante curriculum definiëren volgens u succes in een internationale omgeving kijkende naar deze doelgroepen?

4.2. Hoe zijn deze anders voor middelmanagement ofwel 'middle managers' die met internationale teams werken of in een andersoortige internationale omgeving werkzaam zijn?

Part 5: afrondend

5.1. Heeft u hier nog iets aan toe te voegen wat volgens u belangrijk is?

Bijvoorbeeld:

- Internationalisering en competenties?
- Voorbereiding student op werk in een internationale omgeving?
- Internationale competenties hebben 4 clusters volgens het handboek internationalisering in België, wat vindt u? 1. Intercultureel 1. Taal 3. Relatie student en maatschappij (o.a. global awareness) 4. Persoonlijke groei
- Learning objectives versus International learning objectives?
- Consensus over begrippen zoals internationalisering, interculturele of internationale competenties, andere?
- Wat is uw mening over international competence frameworks zoals die voor ICT?

Heel veel dank voor uw bijdrage.

Jan-Kees van Dijk MBA

Questionnaire semi-structured interviews HEIs (English)

Interview phase 2

Date: 31 March 2016
Version: 1.4 ENG

Introduction

Thank you very much for your participation in this PhD research.

You are the expert in your University of Applied Sciences regarding the competencies and bachelor programmes based on the BBA-curriculum with **CROHO number 34139**, which is the reason why I have asked you to participate.

I would like to ask you several questions; **it will take approximately 1,5 hours**

You do / do not agree that this interview will be recorded digitally.

I would like to request you to sign the 'consent' formular if you did not do this before.

Part 1: meaning and definition of the term "competentie"

- 1.1. What is your (your = University of Applied Sciences) definition of "competentie" / "competenties"?
- 1.2. According to your opinion, do international competencies exist? If so, why?
- 1.3. What are specific competencies for international working environment? Why?

Part 2: competencies and their usage

- 2.1 Which bachelor programmes (names) are based on the curriculum with CROHO number 34139?
- 2.2 How many students are participating in these programmes?
- 2.3. Which competencies are how used in which bachelor programme?
 - a. 9 generic competencies?
 - b. 5 task competencies?
 - c. what is the role of knowledge in the modules?
 - d. how compare could these 3 be compared to the tasks – action student versus facilitation from programme?
- 2.4 Why are these competencies used (motivation per competency)?
- 2.5. Could you please tell me how these competencies were or are translated/ used in these bachelor programmes?
- 2.6. Could you please tell me which methods are used to measure the success of this translation/ usage?

Part 3: market questions

- 3.1. How would you describe the target group for every relevant bachelor programme? Which jobs are linked to these studies and why?
- 3.2. What is your definition of middle management, 'middle managers'?

Part 4: competencies and the definition of success

- 4.1. Which competencies of this curriculum and related to these target groups, define according to your opinion success in an international environment?
- 4.2. How do these competencies differ when compared with 'middle managers' working in international teams or in other international environments?

Part 5: final questions

- 5.1. Do you have anything to add that you personally find important?

Examples:

- Internationalisations and competencies?
- How students prepare themselves for working in an international environment?
- According to the Internationalisation Handbook in Belgium international competencies have 4 clusters; how do you react to these clusters? 1. Intercultural 2. Language 3. Relation student and society (e.g. global awareness) 4. Personal growth.
- Learning objectives versus international learning objectives?
- Consensus regarding concepts: internationalisation, intercultural of international competencies, other?
- Wat is your opinion regarding international competence frameworks, like the one of ICT?

I would like to thank you very much for your contribution.

|

Appendix 6: Example interview frequency analysis "culture" (31 hits)

	D...	Doc...	Code	Beginning	End	Wei...	Preview
		11	cultuur of culturele	27	27	0	Jan-Kees: Oké. Maar dat is een combinatie van. Als je praat ove
		11	cultuur of culturele	58	58	0	Spreker 2: Ja, dan adviseren betekent, dat je dat heel duidelijk
		11	cultuur of culturele	84	84	0	Spreker 2: Ja, daar kan je ook weer boeken over zeggen. Want al
		11	cultuur of culturele	104	104	0	Spreker 2: Ja, maar niet alleen te opleiding. Om maar een voorb
		11	cultuur of culturele	188	188	0	Spreker 2: Oké. Dan denk ik weleens, ja, dat wordt tegenwoordig
		11	cultuur of culturele	202	202	0	Spreker 2: Dat heeft misschien ook een beetje met de culturele
		11	cultuur of culturele	350	350	0	Spreker 2: We hebben een blok internationale bedrijfskunde van
		13	cultuur of culturele	131	131	0	Spreker 2: Het is interessant, hé. Ik ben vroeger dus in Engels
		13	cultuur of culturele	135	135	0	Spreker 2: En toen zei de, daar zat ook een Indiër in de auto,
		13	cultuur of culturele	315	315	0	Spreker 2: Ik zeg, dat er geen consensus is ten aanzien van bel
		13	cultuur of culturele	328	328	0	Jan-Kees: ... hier ontstaan, die IT, daar hebben zich verschil
		12	cultuur of culturele	80	80	0	Spreker 2: Dus wel echt geredeneerd vanuit de, wat heb je nodig
		14	cultuur of culturele	269	269	0	Jan-Kees: Naja, goed, dat roept weer een andere vraag op. Als j
		15	cultuur of culturele	49	49	0	Jan-Kees: Ja. En hoe wordt het dan ingevuld? Ik bedoel, er is n
		15	cultuur of culturele	66	66	0	Spreker 2: Internationalisering is vooral, dat je begrijpt, dat

Appendix 7: Questionnaire Dutch business organisations (Dutch)

De afstemming van competenties tussen hogescholen en orga...

<https://www.surveio.com/survey/d/W7M9W9D8H4H5P2V7H...>

Deel 1

Het eerste deel van dit onderzoek heeft als doel die competenties (een competentie is een set van kennis, vaardigheden en gedrag) te identificeren die uw middenmanagement naar uw mening nodig heeft. Denk bij middenmanagement aan rollen zoals teamleider, afdelingsmanager, verkoopleider of marketingmanager. Het is bij het beantwoorden van onderstaande vragen van belang te denken aan medewerkers met een bedrijfskundige achtergrond die in een internationale werkomgeving actief zijn. Dit kan zijn omdat ze leiding moeten geven aan een internationaal team, in andere landen inkopen, handeldrijven met buitenlandse klanten of anderszins internationale invloeden tijdens hun werk ervaren. De focus ligt hierbij op het vanuit Nederland zakendoen met Duitsland en vice versa. De vragenlijst begint met een paar algemene vragen.

1 In welke branche is uw organisatie actief? *

Wij volgen hier de SBI-indeling van de Kamer van Koophandel (2008 - versie 2017)

- Landbouw, bosbouw en visserij
- Winning van delfstoffen
- Industrie
- Productie en distributie van en handel in elektriciteit, aardgas, stoom en gekoelde lucht
- Winning en distributie van water; afval- en afvalwaterbeheer en sanering
- Bouwnijverheid
- Groot- en detailhandel; reparatie van auto's
- Vervoer en opslag
- Logies-, maaltijd- en drankverstreking
- Informatie en communicatie
- Financiële instellingen
- Verhuur van en handel in onroerend goed
- Advisering, onderzoek en overige specialistische zakelijke dienstverlening
- Verhuur van roerende goederen en overige zakelijke dienstverlening
- Openbaar bestuur, overheidsdiensten en verplichte sociale verzekeringen
- Onderwijs
- Gezondheids- en welzijnszorg
- Cultuur, sport en recreatie
- Overige dienstverlening
- Huishoudens als werkgever; niet-gedifferentieerde productie van goederen en diensten door huishoudens voor eigen gebruik
- Extraterritoriale organisaties en lichamen

② **Hoeveel medewerkers werken in uw organisatie? ***

- 1 werkzame persoon
- 2 tot 10 werkzame personen
- 10 tot 50 werkzame personen
- 50 tot 250 werkzame personen
- 250 of meer werkzame personen

③ **Wat is uw geslacht? ***

- Man
- Vrouw

④ **Wat is uw leeftijd? ***

- <30 jaar
- 30 - <40 jaar
- 40 - <50 jaar
- 50 - <60 jaar
- > 59 jaar

⑤ **Wat is uw rol in de organisatie? ***

U kunt hierbij denken aan rollen zoals HRM directeur of CEO. Hierbij zijn meerdere rollen mogelijk, bijvoorbeeld financieel directeur en HRM manager.

Schrijf een antwoord...

500

⑥ **Voor welke aandachtsgebieden bent u verantwoordelijk? ***

Graag invullen; meerdere gebieden mogelijk, denk hierbij aan inkoop, verkoop, marketing, algemeen, personeel, etc.

Schrijf een antwoord...

500

⑦ **Doet u zaken of heeft u zaken gedaan in Duitsland? ***

Heeft u of had u zakelijke relaties met Duitsland? Dit kan betrekking hebben op inkoop, verkoop, en/ of andere vormen van samenwerking.

- Ja
- Nee

- 8 **Heeft u medewerkers in dienst die een bachelor bedrijfskunde hebben afgerond? ***
Denk hierbij bijvoorbeeld aan de opleidingen: Bedrijfskunde (BK), BK Management Economie en Recht (MER), International Business and Languages (IBL), International Business Management Studies (IBMS) of andere varianten. Indien u dit niet weet willen we u vragen HBO bachelor opleidingen en alumni als referentie te hanteren voor het beantwoorden van de overige vragen.
- Ja
- Nee
- 9 **Hoe vaak heeft u of iemand in uw organisatie contact met een hogeschool of meerdere hogescholen in Nederland? ***
Indien 'nooit', gaat u dan na deze vraag door naar vraag 11
- Nooit
- 1 keer per jaar
- 1 keer per maand
- Meer dan 12 keer per jaar
- 10 **Wat is de aanleiding van dit contact? ***
Waarom is er contact? Meerdere antwoorden mogelijk!
- Stagiaires
- Gastoptreden; bijvoorbeeld als gastdocent
- Docentenrol(-len)
- Afstudeerders
- Participatie in (werkveld-)adviesraad
- Anders
- 11 **In welke mate zijn hogescholen naar uw mening in algemene zin op de hoogte van uw wensen ten aanzien van gewenste competenties voor uw toekomstig middenmanagement? ***
- Zeer slecht
- Slecht
- Niet goed of slecht
- Goed
- Zeer goed
- 12 **Wat is uw motivatie voor het in vraag 11 gegeven antwoord? ***
- Schrijf een antwoord...

500

De Bachelor of Business Administration is een bacheloropleiding gericht op management, organisatie en bedrijfseconomie. Het doel is de studenten tot bedrijfskundig professional op te leiden. 14 Hogescholen in Nederland maken gebruik van 1 identiek leerplan (curriculum) om hun studenten op te leiden en klaar te stomen voor een baan in de profit of non-profit sector. Hieronder staat een lijst met 14 competenties die bij dit Nederlandse bachelor-programma horen. Wij stellen u 2 vragen per competentie. Wij vragen u nu eerst om de belangrijkheid van elke competentie voor uw middenmanagement aan te geven.

13 **Competentie 1: Methodisch handelen** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat in een (multidisciplinaire) omgeving methoden en technieken op het gebied van onderzoek en projectmanagement te selecteren en toe te passen voor het doelgericht aanpakken van organisatievraagstukken.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

14 **Competentie 2: Schakelen en verbinden** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat om bij de aanpak van bedrijfskundige vraagstukken te schakelen tussen en verbindingen te maken tussen de verschillende functionele gebieden en -niveaus. Hij hanteert hierbij een integrale aanpak en werkt multi- en interdisciplinair vanuit verschillende rollen.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

15 **Competentie 3: Adviseren** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat veranderingen of verbeteringen aan te bevelen, waarmee de opdrachtgever en de overige stakeholders geholpen zijn, gericht op de effectiviteit van de organisatie.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

16 **Competentie 4: Innoveren** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat met een onderzoekende en nieuwsgierige geest nieuwe en originele ideeën te signaleren, genereren en uit te voeren bij de vernieuwing van strategie, producten, processen en markten.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

17 **Competentie 5: Samenwerken/ netwerken** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional kan (internationale) samenwerkingscontacten aangaan gericht op het behalen van gemeenschappelijke doelstellingen en profileert en legitimeert zich binnen die contacten. Hij kan relaties, allianties en coalities binnen en buiten de eigen organisatie ontwikkelen en bestendigen en deze benutten voor het verkrijgen van informatie, steun en medewerking.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

18 **Competentie 6: Communiceren** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional kan, zowel in de Nederlandse als Engelse taal, ideeën, meningen, standpunten en besluiten begrijpelijk mondeling verwoorden en afstemmen op de toehoorder en in begrijpelijke en correcte taal op schrift stellen en afstemmen op de lezer.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

19 **Competentie 7: Verantwoord handelen** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is zich bewust van de ethische aspecten van de context waarin hij opereert, en signaleert maatschappelijk, cultureel en moreel gevoelige punten en past zijn gedrag en/of zijn adviezen hierop aan.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

20 **Competentie 8: Professionaliseren ***

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat via de weg van reflectie zich professioneel te blijven ontwikkelen en een bijdrage te leveren aan de ontwikkeling van de organisatie en de beroepsgroep door opgedane kennis te borgen, over te dragen en te verspreiden.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

21 **Competentie 9: ICT-vaardig ***

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat om ICT-applicaties en ICT-toepassingen effectief en efficiënt in te zetten in de uitvoering van zijn professionele taken en/of toe te passen bij het verbeteren van bedrijfsprocessen.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

22 **Competentie 10: Organisatie sensitiviteit ***

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is door problemen van organisatorische aard ter herkennen, te formuleren, uit te werken in een organisatievraagstuk en dit bij beslissers onder de aandacht te brengen

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

23 **Competentie 11: Analyse vaardigheden ***

Toelichting: De bedrijfskundige professional is door onderzoek in staat een diagnose te stellen over de effectiviteit van een organisatie en de achtergronden, oorzaken en samenhangen van het disfunctioneren.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

24 **Competentie 12: Procesmanagement ***

De BKM-professional is in staat om de effectiviteit van een organisatie te verbeteren door op basis een programma van eisen en evidence based practice bedrijfsprocessen te (her) ontwerpen.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

25 **Competentie 13: Veranderingsmanagement ***

De BKM-professional is in staat om (complexe) veranderingsprocessen vorm te geven en te (bege)leiden, waardoor de gewenste situatie voor de organisatie wordt gecreëerd. Hij hanteert hierbij een integrale en op draagvlak gerichte aanpak.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

26 **Competentie 14: Onderzoeksvaardigheden ***

Toelichting: de BKM-professional is in staat om door onderzoek de effectiviteit van verbeteracties te beoordelen en advies te geven over eventueel vervolgonderzoek. De evaluatie is gericht op de juistheid van de diagnose, oplossingsrichting (ontwerp) en de implementatie.

- Helemaal niet belangrijk
- Niet erg belangrijk
- Redelijk belangrijk
- Zeer belangrijk
- Uitermate belangrijk

27 **Welke kennis, vaardigheden of gedragskenmerk(en) mist u nog? ***

Wij horen graag van u welke kennis, vaardigheden en/of gedragskenmerken u belangrijk vindt die u NIET in voorgaande vragen heeft kunnen vinden. De 14 competenties die zijn opgenomen in dit leerplan (curriculum) zijn: methodisch handelen, schakelen en verbinden, adviseren, innoveren, samenwerken/ netwerken, communiceren, verantwoord handelen, professionaliseren, ICT-vaardig, organisatie sensitiviteit, analyse vaardigheden, procesmanagement, veranderingsmanagement en onderzoeksvaardigheden.

Schrijf een antwoord...

500

Deel 2

Vervolgens horen we tenslotte nog graag van u in hoeverre deze 14 competenties volgens u in voldoende mate tijdens de opleiding worden ingevuld. Ofwel, wat hebben de studenten geleerd als ze van de Hogeschool af komen en klaar zijn met hun bachelor studie. Heeft de gemiddelde student(e) volgens u voldoende kennis en vaardigheden om goed in uw organisatie te kunnen functioneren en vertoont hij of zij in voldoende mate het door u en uw organisatie gewenste gedrag? Kortom, voldoet de bachelor opleiding in uw ogen?

Let bij het beantwoorden van de vragen a.u.b. erop dat het in deze vragenlijst over HBO bachelors gaat. Graag uw mening per competentie.

28 **Competentie 1: Methodisch handelen ***

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat in een (multidisciplinaire) omgeving methoden en technieken op het gebied van onderzoek en projectmanagement te selecteren en toe te passen voor het doelgericht aanpakken van organisatievraagstukken.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

29 **Competentie 2: Schakelen en verbinden ***

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat om bij de aanpak van bedrijfskundige vraagstukken te schakelen tussen en verbindingen te maken tussen de verschillende functionele gebieden en -niveaus. Hij hanteert hierbij een integrale aanpak en werkt multi- en interdisciplinair vanuit verschillende rollen.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

30 **Competentie 3: Adviseren ***

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat veranderingen of verbeteringen aan te bevelen, waarmee de opdrachtgever en de overige stakeholders geholpen zijn, gericht op de effectiviteit van de organisatie.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

31 **Competentie 4: Innoveren** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat met een onderzoekende en nieuwsgierige geest nieuwe en originele ideeën te signaleren, genereren en uit te voeren bij de vernieuwing van strategie, producten, processen en markten.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

32 **Competentie 5: Samenwerken/ netwerken** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional kan (internationale) samenwerkingscontacten aangaan gericht op het behalen van gemeenschappelijke doelstellingen en profileert en legitimeert zich binnen die contacten. Hij kan relaties, allianties en coalities binnen en buiten de eigen organisatie ontwikkelen en bestendigen en deze benutten voor het verkrijgen van informatie, steun en medewerking.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

33 **Competentie 6: Communiceren** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional kan, zowel in de Nederlandse als Engelse taal, ideeën, meningen, standpunten en besluiten begrijpelijk mondeling verwoorden en afstemmen op de toehoorder en in begrijpelijke en correcte taal op schrift stellen en afstemmen op de lezer.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

34 **Competentie 7: Verantwoord handelen** *

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is zich bewust van de ethische aspecten van de context waarin hij opereert, en signaleert maatschappelijk, cultureel en moreel gevoelige punten en past zijn gedrag en/of zijn adviezen hierop aan.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

35 **Competentie 8: Professionaliseren ***

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat via de weg van reflectie zich professioneel te blijven ontwikkelen en een bijdrage te leveren aan de ontwikkeling van de organisatie en de beroepsgroep door opgedane kennis te borgen, over te dragen en te verspreiden.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

36 **Competentie 9: ICT-vaardig ***

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat om ICT-applicaties en ICT-toepassingen effectief en efficiënt in te zetten in de uitvoering van zijn professionele taken en/of toe te passen bij het verbeteren van bedrijfsprocessen.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

37 **Competentie 10: Organisatie sensitiviteit ***

Toelichting: de bedrijfskundige professional is in staat problemen van organisatorische aard te herkennen, te formuleren, uit te werken in een organisatievraagstuk en dit bij beslissers onder de aandacht te brengen

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

38 **Competentie 11: Analyse vaardigheden ***

Toelichting: De bedrijfskundige professional is door onderzoek in staat een diagnose te stellen over de effectiviteit van een organisatie en de achtergronden, oorzaken en samenhangen van het disfunctioneren.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

39 **Competentie 12: Procesmanagement ***

De BKM-professional is in staat om de effectiviteit van een organisatie te verbeteren door op basis een programma van eisen en evidence based practice bedrijfsprocessen te (her) ontwerpen.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

40 **Competentie 13: Veranderingsmanagement ***

De BKM-professional is in staat om (complexe) veranderingsprocessen vorm te geven en te (bege)leiden, waardoor de gewenste situatie voor de organisatie wordt gecreëerd. Hij hanteert hierbij een integrale en op draagvlak gerichte aanpak.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

41 **Competentie 14: Onderzoeksvaardigheden ***

Toelichting: de BKM-professional is in staat om door onderzoek de effectiviteit van verbeteracties te beoordelen en advies te geven over eventueel vervolgonderzoek. De evaluatie is gericht op de juistheid van de diagnose, oplossingsrichting (ontwerp) en de implementatie.

- Voldoet niet
- Voldoet in mindere mate
- Voldoet in redelijke mate
- Voldoet in hoge mate
- Voldoet helemaal

42 **Als u zou moeten kiezen tussen kennis of vaardigheden, waar moeten hogescholen volgens u de komende jaren de nadruk op leggen? ***

Wij horen graag van u of hogescholen in Nederland meer aan kennisontwikkeling moeten doen, of juist studenten meer vaardigheden moeten bijbrengen?

- Kennis
- Vaardigheden

43 **Wat is uw motivatie voor het in vraag 42 gegeven antwoord? ***

Waarom kiest u voor kennis of voor vaardigheden?

500

44 Heeft u nog suggesties of aanbevelingen? Zo ja, dan horen wij die graag! *

Schrijf een antwoord...

500

Heel veel dank voor uw medewerking!

De resultaten van dit onderzoek zullen in 2018 te vinden zijn op de website van Academic Alliance Europe: www.aa-europe.eu (<http://www.aa-europe.eu>)

Indien u interesse heeft in een terugkoppeling van de onderzoeksresultaten kunt u een mail sturen naar: info@aa-europe.eu

ENQUÊTE INDIENEN

Enquête maken (/nl/?utm_source=frontend&utm_campaign=footer&utm_medium=link&utm_term=v1) gratis ✓ Aangeboden door Survio (/nl/funcities/?utm_source=frontend&utm_campaign=footer&utm_medium=brand&utm_term=v1)

Questionnaire Dutch business organisations (English)

Survey business organisations – English version **(this version contains the questions of the survey)**

Part 1

The first part of this study aims to identify those competencies (a competency is a set of knowledge, skills and behaviour) that your middle management needs in your opinion. In middle management, think of roles such as team leader, department manager, sales manager or marketing manager. When answering the questions below, it is important to think of employees with a business background who are active in an international work environment. This could be because they have to lead an international team, purchase in other countries, trade with foreign customers or otherwise experience international influences in their work. The focus is on doing business with Germany from the Netherlands and vice versa. The questionnaire starts with a few general questions.

1. In which industry is your organisation active? *
*Here we follow the SBI classification of the Chamber of Commerce (2008 - version 2017)
2. How many employees work in your organisation?
3. What is your gender?
4. What is your age?
5. What is your role in the organisation?
6. Which focus areas are you responsible for?
7. Are you doing or have you done business with Germany?
8. Do you employ employees who have completed a bachelor's degree in business administration?
9. How often do you or someone in your organisation contact a University of Applied Sciences in the Netherlands?
10. What is the motivation for this contact?
11. In your opinion, to what extent are Universities of Applied Sciences generally aware of your wishes regarding the desired competencies for your future middle management?
12. What is your motivation for the answer given in question 11?

The Bachelor of Business Administration is a bachelor's degree focused on management, organisation and business economics. The aim is to train the students as business professionals. 14 Colleges in the Netherlands use one identical curriculum to train their students and prepare them for a job in the profit or non-profit sector. Below you will find a list of 14 competencies that belong to this Dutch bachelor program. We ask you two questions per competency. We first ask you to indicate the importance of each competency for your middle management.

Answers can be given via a 5-points Likert scale.

13. Competency 1: Acting methodically

Explanation: the business professional is capable in a (multidisciplinary) environment of research methods and techniques to select and apply project management for a targeted approach to organisational issues.

14. Competency 2: Switch and connect

Explanation: the business professional is able to switch and make connections between the various functional areas and levels when tackling business administration issues. He uses an integral approach and works multi- and interdisciplinary from different roles.

15. Competency 3: Advise

Explanation: the business professional is able to recommend changes or improvements, which help the client and the other stakeholders, aimed at the effectiveness of the organisation.

16. Competency 4: Innovate

Explanation: the business professional is able to identify, generate and execute new and original ideas with an inquiring and curious mind when renewing strategy, products, processes and markets.

17. Competency 5: Cooperation / networking

Explanation: the business professional can enter into (international) cooperation contacts aimed at achieving common objectives and will profile and identify himself within those contacts. He can develop and perpetuate relationships, alliances and coalitions within and outside his own organisation and use them to obtain information, support and cooperation.

18. Competency 6: Communication

Explanation: the business professional can, in both the Dutch and English language, verbally articulate ideas, opinions, positions and decisions and attune them to the listener and write them in writing in understandable and correct language and attune them to the reader.

19. Competency 7: Act responsibly

Explanation: the business professional is aware of the ethical aspects of the context in which he operates, and identifies social, cultural and morally sensitive points and adjusts his behaviour and / or his advice accordingly.

20. Competency 8: Professionalisation

Explanation: the business professional is able to continue to develop professionally by means of reflection and to contribute to the development of the organisation and the professional group by securing, transferring and disseminating acquired knowledge.

21. Competency 9: ICT-skilled

Explanation: the business professional is able to use ICT applications and ICT applications effectively and efficiently in the execution of his professional tasks and / or to apply them in improving business processes.

22. Competency 10: Organisation sensitivity

Explanation: The business professional is capable of recognising organisational problems, formulating them and working them out consistently operationally into an organisational issue and bringing this to the attention of decision-makers.

23. Competency 11: Analysis Skills

Explanation: By conducting research, the business professional is able to make a diagnosis about the effectiveness of an organisation and the backgrounds, causes and correlations of areas of dysfunction.

24. Competency 12: Process Management

Explanation: The business professional is capable of improving the effectiveness of an organisation by (re-)designing business processes based on a programme of requirements and evidence based practice.

25. Competency 13: Change Management

Explanation: The business professional is capable of shaping and leading (complex) change processes, thereby creating the desired situation for the organisation. He uses an integral approach based on support.

26. Competency 14: Research Skills

Explanation: The business professional is capable of assessing the effectiveness of improvement actions through research and advising on possible follow-up research. The evaluation focuses on the correctness of the diagnosis, solution direction (design) and implementation.

27. What knowledge, skills or behavioural characteristic(s) are you still missing?

We would like to hear from you, which knowledge, skills and/ or behavioural characteristics you find important that you have NOT found in previous questions. The 14 competencies that are included in this curriculum (curriculum) are: acting methodically, switching and connecting, advising, innovating, collaborating/ networking, communicating, acting responsibly, professionalising, IT skills, organisational sensitivity, analysis skills, process management, change management and research skills.

Part 2

Finally, we would like to hear from you to what extent you think these 14 competencies are sufficiently filled in during the training. In other words, what have the students learned when they leave the University of Applied Sciences and have finished their bachelor studies. Do you think the average student has sufficient knowledge and skills to function properly in your organisation and does he or she exhibit the desired behaviour by you and your organisation? In short, in your view, is the bachelor's degree sufficient?

When answering the questions, please note that this questionnaire is about [bachelors](#) of Universities of Applied Sciences. Please give your opinion per competency.

Answers can be given via a 5-points Likert scale.

28. Competency 1: Acting methodically

Explanation: the business professional is capable in a (multidisciplinary) environment of research methods and techniques to select and apply project management for a targeted approach to organisational issues.

29. Competency 2: Switch and connect

Explanation: the business professional is able to switch and make connections between the various functional areas and levels when tackling business administration issues. He uses an integral approach and works multi- and interdisciplinary from different roles.

30. Competency 3: Advise

Explanation: the business professional is able to recommend changes or improvements, which help the client and the other stakeholders, aimed at the effectiveness of the organisation.

31. Competency 4: Innovate

Explanation: the business professional is able to identify, generate and execute new and original ideas with an inquiring and curious mind when renewing strategy, products, processes and markets.

32. Competency 5: Cooperation / networking

Explanation: the business professional can enter into (international) cooperation contacts aimed at achieving common objectives and will profile and identify himself within those contacts. He can develop and perpetuate relationships, alliances and coalitions within and outside his own organisation and use them to obtain information, support and cooperation.

33. Competency 6: Communication

Explanation: the business professional can, in both the Dutch and English language, verbally articulate ideas, opinions, positions and decisions and attune them to the listener and write them in an understandable and correct language and attune them to the reader.

34. Competency 7: Act responsibly

Explanation: the business professional is aware of the ethical aspects of the context in which he operates, and identifies social, cultural and morally sensitive points and adjusts his behaviour and / or his advice accordingly.

35. Competency 8: Professionalisation

Explanation: the business professional is able to continue to develop professionally by means of reflection and to contribute to the development of the organisation and the professional group by securing, transferring and disseminating acquired knowledge.

36. Competency 9: ICT-skilled

Explanation: the business professional is able to use ICT applications and ICT applications effectively and efficiently in the execution of his professional tasks and / or to apply them in improving business processes.

37. Competency 10: Organisation sensitivity

Explanation: The business professional is capable of recognising organisational problems, formulating them and working them out consistently operationally into an organisational issue and bringing this to the attention of decision-makers.

38. Competency 11: Analysis Skills

Explanation: By conducting research, the business professional is able to make a diagnosis about the effectiveness of an organisation and the backgrounds, causes and correlations of areas of dysfunction.

39. Competency 12: Process Management

Explanation: The business professional is capable of improving the effectiveness of an organisation by (re-)designing business processes based on a programme of requirements and evidence based practice.

40. Competency 13: Change Management

Explanation: The business professional is capable of shaping and leading (complex) change processes, thereby creating the desired situation for the organisation. He uses an integral approach based on support.

41. Competency 14: Research Skills

Explanation: The business professional is capable of assessing the effectiveness of improvement actions through research and advising on possible follow-up research. The evaluation focuses on the correctness of the diagnosis, solution direction (design) and implementation.

42. If you had to choose between knowledge or skills what do you think Universities of Applied Sciences should emphasise in the coming years?

We would like to hear from you whether universities of applied sciences in the Netherlands should increase knowledge development or teach students more skills?

43. What is your motivation for the answer given in question 42?
Why do you choose knowledge or skills?

44. Do you have any suggestions or recommendations? If so, please let us know.

Thank you very much for your cooperation!

Appendix 8: Example of survey analysis, question 12 that deals with the motivation of the given answers regarding the awareness of HEIs.

Wat is uw motivatie voor het in vraag 11 gegeven antwoord?	Translation to English	Summarising words, concepts: grouping	Positive, negative or neutral
hogeschool en medewerker/contactpersoon en er is bij stagiaires ed niet direct een link naar "gewenste competenties voor uw toekomstig middenmanagement"	Interns do not show desired competencies	Better alignment, better competency development	Negative
onderwijs.	Supplier	NA	NA
Ik heb geen idee.	NA	NA	NA
informatie uitwisseling	Information exchange is bad	Communication/ information exchange	Negative
net	NA	NA	NA
Aparte tak van dienst	NA	NA	NA
Meer aansluiting van talent op de juiste plek in plaats van gewoon toelaten.	The right talent for the right position, selection	Better alignment	Negative
Een student de kans geven een stage te lopen	Give the student the chance to do an internship	Practical experience/ internships	Neutral
het eigen curriculum	Every HEI steers only on own curriculum	Customer orientation (business)	Negative
met goed uitgebalanceerde werkveldadviesraden (beroepenveldcommissies) om feeling te houden met de praktijk. Deze input weegt zwaar bij ontwikkelen/aanpassen curricula. Specifieke focus op internationalisering, interculturele competenties, taalvaardigheid en 21st century skills passeren met Werven van de juiste verkopers en adviseurs.	Hiring the right employees	Alignment	Neutral
met meerder hogescholen; om kennis te halen en te brengen	Supplier	NA	NA
Praktijkervaringen presenteren bij bijna afgestudeerden.	Sharing practice with students	Practical experience/ sharing experiences with students	Negative
ondanks veel ervaring in het bedrijfsleven bij de verschillende docenten en beroepenveldcommissies, toch nog veel onduidelijkheid welke te ontwikkelen	A lot is still unclear on which competencies should be developed, despite some experienced teachers	Customer orientation (business)	Negative
op de ontwikkeling van de competenties bij de individuele student. Daarnaast wordt er geregeld contact gelegd over de inhoud van de opleiding op medisch gebied en nog te weinig op competentie ontwikkeling. Ook bij het aanname	More individual focus, more 1-on-1 / customer focus regarding individual students. More steering based upon	More 1-on-1 towards students, more	

Appendix 9: Cronbach's Alpha split-half and Pearson correlation analysis

1. Cronbach's Alpha, as discussed in section 5.2.2:

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	392	100,0
	Excluded ^a	0	,0
	Total	392	100,0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Case Processing Summary

		N	%
Cases	Valid	392	100,0
	Excluded ^a	0	,0
	Total	392	100,0

a. Listwise deletion based on all variables in the procedure.

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
,898	,899	14

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	N of Items
,911	,911	14

Importance 14 competencies

Satisfaction 14 competencies

2. Split-half reliability, as discussed in section 5.2.2:

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Part 1	Value	,853
		N of Items	7 ^a
	Part 2	Value	,817
		N of Items	7 ^b
Total N of Items			14
Correlation Between Forms			,711
Spearman-Brown Coefficient	Equal Length		,831
	Unequal Length		,831
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient			,830

a. The items are: Competentie1belanggecodeerd, Competentie2belanggecodeerd, Competentie3belanggecodeerd, Competentie4belanggecodeerd, Competentie5belanggecodeerd, Competentie6belanggecodeerd, Competentie7belanggecodeerd.

b. The items are: Competentie8belanggecodeerd, Competentie9belanggecodeerd, Competentie10belanggecodeerd, Competentie11belanggecodeerd, Competentie12belanggecodeerd, Competentie13belanggecodeerd, Competentie14belanggecodeerd.

3. Split-half analysis importance 14 competencies, as discussed in section 5.2.2:

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Part 1	Value	,853
		N of Items	7 ^a
	Part 2	Value	,817
		N of Items	7 ^b
Total N of Items			14
Correlation Between Forms			,711
Spearman-Brown Coefficient	Equal Length		,831
	Unequal Length		,831
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient			,830

a. The items are: Competentie1belanggecodeerd, Competentie2belanggecodeerd, Competentie3belanggecodeerd, Competentie4belanggecodeerd, Competentie5belanggecodeerd, Competentie6belanggecodeerd, Competentie7belanggecodeerd.

b. The items are: Competentie8belanggecodeerd, Competentie9belanggecodeerd, Competentie10belanggecodeerd, Competentie11belanggecodeerd, Competentie12belanggecodeerd, Competentie13belanggecodeerd, Competentie14belanggecodeerd.

4. Split-half analysis satisfaction 14 competencies, as discussed in section 5.2.2:

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Part 1	Value	,851
		N of Items	7 ^a
	Part 2	Value	,840
		N of Items	7 ^b
Total N of Items			14
Correlation Between Forms			,785
Spearman-Brown Coefficient	Equal Length		,880
	Unequal Length		,880
Guttman Split-Half Coefficient			,880

a. The items are: Competentie1voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie2voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie3voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie4voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie5voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie6voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie7voldoetgecodeerd.

b. The items are: Competentie8voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie9voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie10voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie11voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie12voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie13voldoetgecodeerd, Competentie14voldoetgecodeerd.

5. Pearson Correlation competency 1 importance and satisfaction, as discussed in section 5.2.4

Correlations

		Competentie1 belanggecode erd	Competentie1 voldoetgecode erd
Competentie1belanggeco deerd	Pearson Correlation	1	,282 **
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,000
	N	392	392
Competentie1voldoetgeco deerd	Pearson Correlation	,282 **	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	
	N	392	392

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Appendix 10: graphs and tables field survey organisations

1. Frequency of contact versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, as discussed in chapter 5.2.4:

Figure 10.1: Bi-variate analysis frequency of contact versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)

2. Size of organisation versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, as discussed in chapter 5.2.4:

Figure 10.2: Bi-variate analysis size of organisation versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)

3. Doing business with Germany versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, as discussed in chapter 5.2.4:

Figure 10.3: Doing business with Germany versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)

4. Employees with a BBA degree versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, as discussed in chapter 5.2.4:

Figure 10.4: Employees with a BBA degree versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)

5. Gender versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, as discussed in chapter 5.2.4:

Figure 10.5: Gender versus HEI awareness of desired competencies, depicted by researcher (n=392)